

Improving welfare in the ornamental fish trade

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Thesis submitted to the University of the West of Scotland in partial fulfilment of the requirements for an award of Doctor of Philosophy.

School of Health and Life Sciences
Institute of Biomedical and Environmental Health Research

September 2023

Funding provided by Mars WALTHAM Petcare Science Institute, Aquasense Ltd and the University of the West of Scotland

Acknowledgements

Firstly, I would like to extend my sincere thanks to all of my academic and industrial supervisors: Prof. Katherine Sloman, Dr Mhairi Alexander, Dr Donna Snellgrove, Mr Peter Smith, Dr Iain McLellan and Prof. Fiona Henriquez. But I would especially like to thank Kath for her support, I would not have been able to achieve this without her imparting so much knowledge and being one of the most patient people I have ever met. I would also like to thank the financial support that WALTHAM Petcare Science Institute and Aquasense Ltd. provided and for being given the opportunity to conduct one of my experiments in their facilities. I would also like to thank the biological technicians at UWS, Edith and Deirdre, for their help and hard work when it came to the husbandry of the fish. I would especially like to thank my “bubble- buddy”, Edith, for all of her help and for being a genuinely lovely human being.

Although COVID-19 got in the way of being able to have a “normal” Ph.D. experience. I will always be grateful to the colleagues, now forever friends, I made along the way. I am especially grateful to Dr Emily Moore and Dr Heather Clements for their friendship and Sunday walking trips. I would also like to express my sincere thanks to the amazing women I get the privilege to call my friends: Jessica Hurley, Hannah Stephens, Hannah Austin and Leigh Biddiscombe.

Without the unwavering support of my parents, Liz and Chris, absolutely none of this would have been possible. They have been my constant throughout the many highs and lows of this whole experience; there are not enough words to say how grateful I am, how much they mean to me and how much I love them both. To my amazing partner, Alex. I don’t know what I did to deserve someone as special as you. I could say thank you a million times but that would never be enough. Your belief in me kept me going even when we were miles apart. I would like to dedicate this thesis to all of them.

Author's declaration

At no point during the registration for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy has the author been enrolled or registered at any other university for an award. The chapters presented within this thesis are entirely the author's own work.

Publications:

Jones, M., Alexander, M.E., Snellgrove, D., Smith, P., Bramhall, S., Carey, P., Henriquez, F.L., McLellan, I. and Sloman, K.A. (2021) How should we monitor welfare in the ornamental fish trade? *Reviews in Aquaculture*. **14(2)** 770-790. DOI: 10.1111/raq.12624

Jones, M., Alexander, M.E., Lightbody, S., Snellgrove, D., Smith, P., Bramhall, S., Henriquez, F.L., McLellan, I. and Sloman, K.A. (2023) Influence of social enrichment on transport stress in fish: a behavioural approach. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*. **262**. DOI:10.1016/j.applanim.2023.105920

Jones, M. Welfare in the ornamental fish trade. *International Petfood Magazine*. August edition 2022.

Presentations and conferences attended:

Jones, M., Alexander, M.E., Lightbody, S., Snellgrove, D., Smith, P., Bramhall, S., Henriquez, F.L., McLellan, I. and Sloman, K.A. Influence of social enrichment on transport stress in fish: a behavioural approach. Oral Presentation. International Congress on the Biology of Fish, 2022. Montpellier (28th June – 1st July), France.

Jones, M., Alexander, M.E., Snellgrove, D., Smith, P., Bramhall, S., Carey, P., Henriquez, F.L., McLellan, I. and Sloman, K.A., 2020. Improving welfare in the ornamental fish trade. Oral Presentation. Transfer event, University of the West of Scotland (17th March), United Kingdom.

Word count of main body of thesis: 41,019

Signed: Megan Jones

Dated: 24.09.2023

1 Abstract

2 The global ornamental fish trade is a multibillion-dollar industry, with legal trade estimated to be worth
3 \$15-20 billion *per annum*. Although there is existing legislation concerning fish welfare in aquaculture
4 and research, there is little legislation surrounding the welfare of pet fishes. Ornamental fishes are
5 routinely transported over long distances from origin to destination country, potentially exposing fishes
6 to biotic and abiotic conditions which compromise welfare. Existing research has identified multiple
7 stressors that can occur during the acquisition process of ornamental fishes, which may culminate in
8 poor welfare or even death. Therefore, a better understanding of the conditions that ornamental fishes
9 are exposed to and research into interventions that may mitigate compromising conditions is necessary
10 to improve ornamental fish welfare. This thesis focussed on potential methods of improving fish welfare
11 either during or post-transport at both a group and individual level. Chapter 1 of this thesis focussed on
12 ways in which welfare can be monitored and measured *via* the use of operational welfare indicators
13 (OWIs), a method routinely used in commercial food-fish aquaculture, with a specific focus on non-
14 invasive measures. Chapters 2 and 5 went on to experimentally test whether using either novel or
15 commercially-available water conditioners could improve welfare during transport. In Chapter 2, the
16 main active ingredients in the newly-developed water conditioner were aimed at targeting welfare-
17 compromising components found in poor quality water. The water conditioner used in Chapter 5 had
18 previously been found to mitigate some negative behavioural effects when used during long-term
19 transport. In Chapter 5, it was tested to identify if similar results occurred when fish were exposed to
20 the conditioner during recovery after long term transport, and whether any effects persisted following
21 an onward short-term transport. However, no significant effects of either water conditioner on
22 behaviour or water quality were found. Chapter 4 determined the potential benefits of adding a natural
23 compound, cannabidiol (CBD), to the water during transport. CBD had a significant effect on the
24 behaviour of fish post-transport, with the fish exposed to CBD exhibiting significantly fewer anxiety-
25 or stress-like behaviours. As there are no current water conditioners available containing CBD; this
26 represents an interesting ingredient for future commercial development. Chapter 3 investigated the
27 behavioural effects of social enrichment of fish post-transport. While many studies have considered
28 methods of improving welfare for food fishes through physical and social enrichment, few have
29 considered the use of enrichment to improve welfare of ornamental fishes post-transport. It was
30 identified that fish introduced into tanks without conspecifics or into tanks containing heterospecifics
31 aided behavioural recovery post-transport, compared to when fish were introduced to tanks containing
32 conspecifics. The work undertaken in this thesis highlights a range of interventions and methods that
33 could be used within the trade to improve welfare for ornamental fishes, specifically during and
34 immediately post-transport. It also demonstrates that non-invasive welfare indicators such as behaviour
35 can be an efficient metric when attempting to measure welfare.

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138 Table of Abbreviations

CBD	Cannabidiol
Cl	Chlorine
dB	Decibels
Dm	Dorsomedial telencephalon
DO	Dissolved Oxygen
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
EtOH	Ethanol
FBI	Fish Behaviour Index
FMG	Formalin Malachite Green
HPLC	High Performance Liquid Chromatography
kHz	Kilohertz
LC-MS	Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry
LD	Light-Dark (tests)
LOEC	Lowest Observable Effect Concentration
MS-222	Tricaine mesylate
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₂	Sodium dithionate
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₅	Sodium metabisulfite
NaCl	Sodium chloride
NaHCO ₃	Sodium bicarbonate
NH ₃	Ammonia
NH ₄ ⁺	Ammonium
NO ₂ ⁻	Nitrite
NO ₃ ⁻	Nitrate
NOEC	No Observable Effect Concentration
NOR	Novel Object Recognition
NTT	Novel Tank Test
OATA	Ornamental Aquatic Trade Association
OBR	Opercular Beat Rate
OF	Open Field (tests)
OFI	Ornamental Fish International
OWI	Operational Welfare Indicators
PPT	Place Preference Test
PVC	Polyvinylchloride
PVP-I	Polyvinylpyrrolidone
SEM	Standard Error Mean
UHQ	Ultra-high quality
Y/N	Yes/No
Δ ⁹ - THC	Δ ⁹ - tetrahydrocannabinol

139 Chapter 1: How should we monitor welfare in the ornamental fish
140 trade?

141 Published as: Jones, M., Alexander, M.E., Snellgrove, D., Smith, P., Bramhall, S., Carey, P., Henriquez,
142 F.L., McLellan, I. and Sloman, K.A. (2021) How should we monitor welfare in the ornamental fish
143 trade? *Reviews in Aquaculture*. **14(2)** 770-790. DOI: 10.1111/raq.12624

144 1.1 Abstract

145 The global ornamental fish trade is a multibillion-dollar industry, with legal trade estimated to be worth
146 between \$15-20 billion *per annum*. Although there is existing legislation concerning the improvement
147 of fish welfare in aquaculture and research, there is little legislation surrounding the welfare of pet
148 fishes. The four distinct phases of the ornamental fish trade, curation, transportation, time spent at
149 wholesalers/retailers and time spent in domestic/public aquaria, represent different welfare concerns.
150 Within the animal welfare field there is increasing interest in improving welfare through the creation of
151 operational welfare indicators (OWIs), where individual indicators are aggregated to assess animal
152 welfare. OWIs can be morphological, behavioural, physiological, metabolic or abiotic in nature, with
153 behaviour often considered as the foremost non-invasive method of elucidating welfare in fishes.
154 Currently, while OWIs exist for food fish species, there are no OWIs for use within the ornamental fish
155 trade. This review looks briefly at the stressors experienced by fishes within the ornamental trade, and
156 then, following a systematic review of existing behavioural measures of welfare used for ornamental
157 fish species, considers the potential development of OWIs for the ornamental trade.

158 1.2 Introduction

159 The global ornamental fish trade is a multibillion-dollar industry, with legal trade estimated to be worth
160 between \$15-20 billion *per annum* (King, 2019; Pouil *et al.*, 2019). It is thought that more than 125
161 countries participate in the trade of live fishes, highlighting the global nature of the industry (Raja *et*
162 *al.*, 2019). The primary exporters of ornamental fishes, both directly caught, and captive bred, are Asia
163 Pacific countries (Philippines, Japan, Burma, Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, Sri Lanka), the
164 Netherlands, Germany, Spain, the United States of America (US; Hawaii), Czech Republic and Russia.
165 The primary purchasing countries of ornamental fishes are the US, Japan and in Europe (Raja *et al.*,
166 2019). The ornamental fish trade is dominated by freshwater fish species (~2,000 spp), accounting for
167 90% of the market, with the remaining 10% comprising marine species (~2,500 spp) (King *et al.*, 2019).
168 Of the 2 billion fishes transported *per annum*, 99% of them are for hobbyist aquaria, with the remaining
169 1% destined for public aquaria or research laboratories (Raja *et al.*, 2019). Due to the increasing
170 popularity of keeping home aquaria over recent decades, a substantial increase in trade and demand for
171 ornamental fishes has developed, with the trade growing by 14% annually since the 1970s (Maceda-
172 Veiga *et al.*, 2016; Metar *et al.*, 2018).

173 Ornamental fishes are exposed to stressors and environments which may negatively affect their welfare
174 (Rose *et al.*, 2014) such as poor water quality, inappropriate stocking densities, diseases and injury
175 (Stevens *et al.*, 2017), with issues comparable to those experienced in food fish aquaculture
176 (Huntingford *et al.*, 2006; Stevens *et al.*, 2017). Fishes within the ornamental trade can experience long
177 transport times (up to 72 h in some instances) and a large number of individual stages in their supply
178 chain (Fig. 1.1). The ornamental fish supply chain comprises many different phases including curation,
179 transportation, time spent at wholesalers/retailers and time spent in domestic/public aquaria, with each
180 phase having very different welfare concerns (Fig. 1.1) (Muyot *et al.*, 2018). A typical supply chain
181 starts in the origin country *via* capture of wild fishes or breeding in aquaculture (Iqbal & Shalij, 2019;
182 King, 2019). Fishes may then be held in a holding facility either with the exporter or a middleman
183 broker prior to transportation, usually by air, to their destination country. Depending on the country,
184 fishes may be subject to border inspection (e.g. within the European Union (EU)) and be collected either
185 directly by a retailer or *via* a wholesaler. At the retailer, fishes will normally reside in display tanks
186 prior to being purchased and transported to their final destination. Due to the length of the acquisition
187 process of ornamental fishes there is a cumulative potential for decreased welfare and accountability
188 (Masud *et al.*, 2019). Although there is existing European legislation concerning fish welfare in
189 aquaculture and research (EU, 1998 and 2010, respectively), there is little legislation surrounding the
190 welfare of pet fishes (Stevens *et al.*, 2017; Toni *et al.*, 2019) and many countries do not have any
191 legislation at all. Membership of organisations who aim to improve welfare within the trade e.g.
192 Ornamental Fish International (OFI) and the Ornamental Aquatic Trade Association (OATA) is

193 available for retailers but is voluntary, leaving the global trade with no regulatory body that monitors
194 welfare (Stevens *et al.*, 2017; Toni *et al.*, 2019).

195 One of the primary problems facing the regulation of the ornamental trade is the difficulty in monitoring
196 ornamental fish welfare. Farmed food-fishes tend to be larger in size than their ornamental counterparts
197 making it easier to identify any welfare issues. Technological advances (see below: *Can we use current*
198 *aquaculture technologies in an ornamental-setting?*) within food-fish aquaculture allow monitoring of
199 different welfare aspects including changes in condition and subtle, complex behaviours associated with
200 poor welfare (Zion, 2012). Within food-fish aquaculture, there has been an emergence of Operational
201 Welfare Indicators (OWIs), which are behavioural and physical indicators that provide an overall
202 welfare assessment (Martins *et al.*, 2012; Noble *et al.*, 2018; Saraiva *et al.*, 2019). Current published
203 OWIs are either commercial-species-specific, for example Precision Fish Farming (salmonids) (Føre *et*
204 *al.*, 2018), laboratory-species-specific, for example the Fish Behaviour Index (FBI) (Deakin *et al.*,
205 2019) or generalised across species primarily used in aquaculture, such as The FishEthoBase (Saraiva
206 *et al.*, 2019). To date, there are no OWIs published or used commercially regarding the welfare of
207 ornamental fishes. The diversity of ornamental fish species traded, the small physical size of the fishes,
208 and the international nature of the supply chain make technology used in food-fish welfare monitoring,
209 and many of the food-fish OWIs, unsuitable for ornamental fishes. Within the ornamental trade, fishes
210 can be more easily inspected visually (e.g. for behaviour, colouration, injuries) as they are generally
211 housed in glass tanks making behaviour and non-invasive observations more likely candidates for
212 ornamental fish OWIs. Therefore, following a brief overview of fish welfare and the stressors
213 encountered by fish in the ornamental trade, the aim of this review is to consider the potential for
214 developing OWIs for the ornamental trade, including a review of existing behavioural measures of
215 welfare in ornamental fishes. Identified behavioural measures are then combined with other non-
216 invasive potential indicators that may be beneficial when developing an ornamental fish OWI
217 monitoring tool.

218

219 Figure 1.1. Transportation process for ornamental fishes with a summary of welfare concerns at each stage. Rectangular boxes, with small, dashed borders indicate when fishes
 220 are curated either from wild sources or from ornamental fish breeders. Rectangular and diamond shaped boxes with continuous borders and arrows indicate when fishes are
 221 confined in plastic bags with individuals of the same species. Rectangular boxes with large, dashed borders indicate when fishes are confined in tanks of the same species.
 222 Rectangular and oval boxes with fine dotted borders indicates when fishes are in tanks potentially with mixed species.

223 1.2.1 Fish welfare and the ornamental trade

224 Defining and assessing fish welfare is challenging as definitions can vary considerably. For fishes,
225 welfare has been particularly difficult to define from a scientific perspective as whether fish experience
226 pain has been an area of controversy within the literature (Brown, 2015; Rose *et al.*, 2014; Sneddon *et*
227 *al.*, 2018; Browman *et al.*, 2019; Chatigny, 2019). There is now a large body of evidence demonstrating
228 that fish are self-aware, can become distressed, experience pain through nociceptors and to some extent
229 experience emotions (Silva *et al.*, 2019; Sneddon & Brown, 2020), however their sentience is not
230 accepted by all (Rose, 2002; Rose *et al.*, 2014). Fish welfare is increasingly acknowledged as a societal
231 issue (Chandroo *et al.*, 2004; Conte, 2004; Veldhuizen *et al.*, 2018) and over the past decade, fish
232 welfare issues have raised scientific, political and public concern worldwide (Bayvel & Cross, 2010;
233 Ingenbleek & Immink, 2010; Segner *et al.*, 2012).

234 In terms of measurement, animal welfare is most often framed within the ‘Five Freedoms’ (Webster,
235 2016), and more recently the ‘Five Domains’ (Mellor *et al.*, 2020), both of which have been considered
236 in the context of fishes (Huntingford *et al.*, 2006; Mellor *et al.*, 2020). The integration of behavioural,
237 physiological and cognitive measures for determining fish welfare, particularly in relation to food-
238 fishes, has been reviewed extensively (Relić *et al.*, 2010; Stevens *et al.*, 2017; Saraiva *et al.*, 2019). The
239 FishEthoBase (www.fishethobase.net) suggests that ‘fish welfare is guaranteed if a fish can live up to
240 the potential of the species and develop its individuality’. When considering the welfare of fishes within
241 the ornamental trade, the stressors they encounter need to be understood (Barton, 2002; Acrete *et al.*,
242 2004; Harmon, 2009; Omeji *et al.*, 2017), along with interaction between these multifactorial stressors
243 (Segner *et al.*, 2012). The stressors experienced by fishes in the ornamental trade have been reviewed
244 extensively (e.g. Portz *et al.*, 2006; Harmon, 2009; Omeji *et al.*, 2017; Stevens *et al.*, 2017; Veldhuizen
245 *et al.*, 2018; King, 2019; Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2019) thus for context only a brief summary of the
246 main stressors is given here.

247 1.2.1.1. Mechanical disturbance: In the ornamental trade, the transport of live fishes coupled with
248 pre- and post- handling procedures can represent a significant stress for the fish (Stevens *et al.*, 2017;
249 Dhanasiri *et al.*, 2013; Masud *et al.*, 2019). Mortalities relating to mechanical disturbance within the
250 ornamental fish trade are primarily based on estimates as opposed to empirical studies and differ
251 drastically in number (Stevens *et al.*, 2017; Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2019). Ornamental fishes are usually
252 transported in polythene bags filled with water and oxygen (air or pure oxygen) in a 1:4 ratio,
253 respectively (Conte, 2004). Air pockets within bags increase the risk of mechanical disturbance which
254 can lead to immunosuppression (Masud *et al.*, 2019) and an increased incidence of disease (Ramsay *et*
255 *al.*, 2009; Masud *et al.*, 2019). Through the supply chain (Fig. 1.1), multiple stages of transport can
256 compound the stressors experienced.

257 1.2.1.2. Inappropriate stocking densities: Appropriate stocking densities vary between species
258 (Chambel *et al.*, 2015; Tibile *et al.*, 2016). For some species, high stocking densities, either during
259 transport or holding can lead to reduced water quality from increased nitrogenous waste accumulation,
260 oxygen consumption and suspended organic solids, as well as increased aggression (Manley *et al.*,
261 2014; Liu *et al.*, 2019). Whereas in other species, low stocking densities can lead to increased
262 territoriality through having an unstable social group which can result in an increase in aggressive
263 behaviours from dominant fish repeatedly targeting subordinate individuals, as well as having a
264 negative effect on physiology (Sloman & Armstrong, 2002; Champneys *et al.*, 2019; Ramee *et al.*,
265 2020). Highly territorial fish species should not be housed together due to the increased potential for
266 aggression and injury (Pleeging & Moons, 2017) and species that are gregarious should be housed in
267 groups (Nadler *et al.*, 2016). Within all stages of the ornamental trade supply chain, fishes can be
268 exposed to variable stocking densities, with stocking density changing, sometimes abruptly, between
269 different stages. Physiological effects of inappropriate stocking density have been documented in
270 ornamental fishes. For example, stocking density has been suggested as a contributing factor in cortisol
271 mediated masculinisation in larval and juvenile zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) through increased endogenous
272 cortisol levels, with a larger proportion of males found in tanks with higher stocking densities (Ribas *et al.*,
273 2017; Ramee *et al.*, 2020). Further, zebrafish (*D. rerio*) housed at a higher density (40 fish/l) had
274 significantly higher cortisol concentrations than those housed at a lower density (0.2 fish/l) (Ramsay *et al.*,
275 2006). Fishes may additionally be placed in mixed-species assemblages which can affect behaviour
276 and welfare (Sloman *et al.*, 2011) and understanding the behavioural compatibility of different
277 ornamental fish species is essential (Sneddon & Brown, 2020).

278 1.2.1.3. Poor water quality: Confinement of fishes in an enclosed volume of water, particularly during
279 transport, but also in holding conditions, can result in deterioration of water quality (in particular,
280 elevated ammonia (NH₃) and carbon dioxide (CO₂), and reduction in dissolved (O₂)) which can lead to
281 increased stress and negative effects on welfare (Pottinger *et al.*, 1992). The main water quality
282 parameters that need to be controlled are ammonia (NH₃), ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrite (NO₂⁻), nitrate
283 (NO₃⁻), dissolved oxygen (DO), carbon dioxide (CO₂) and chlorine (Cl), and salinity if the species are
284 marine (Dhanasiri *et al.*, 2011). Poor water quality can negatively impact fish growth through reduced
285 feed consumption and/or feed conversion ratios (Pichavant *et al.*, 2001; Santos *et al.*, 2010), suggesting
286 that water quality may affect energy partitioning and subsequent growth (Person-Le Ruyet *et al.*, 2003).
287 The capacity to transport ornamental fishes without negatively impacting their welfare requires in-depth
288 knowledge of specific species in terms of stress tolerance, metabolism and water quality requirements
289 (Oliveira *et al.*, 2008; Sampaio & Freire, 2016). Although there has been significant effort to control
290 overall water quality within the ornamental supply chain, changes in water quality between each stage
291 can expose fishes to significant stress and are often overlooked when assessing welfare. Prior to
292 transport, water is often super-saturated with pure oxygen to compensate for oxygen deficiency and

293 deterioration in combination with an increased ammonia build-up (Espmark & Baeverfjord, 2009).
294 Water conditioners and additives have been created to mitigate any problems that may arise from poor
295 water quality (see review by Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2019). For example, some wholesalers add zeolite,
296 a microporous adsorbent mineral, to maintain water quality.

297 1.2.1.4. Inappropriate water temperature: Within the supply chain, ornamental fishes may be
298 exposed to temperatures out-with their thermal tolerance range, with suboptimal temperatures affecting
299 fish metabolism and related physiological processes such as hepatic intracellular activity and cardiac
300 muscle contractility (Schmidt-Nielson, 1975; Dzikowski *et al.*, 2001; Natarajan *et al.*, 2009). Low
301 temperatures (<19.6° C) during transport compromise cardinal tetra (*Paracheirodon axelrodi*) survival
302 (Oliveira *et al.*, 2008) and changes in temperature can exacerbate declines in water quality (Harvey *et*
303 *al.*, 2011; Paul *et al.*, 2019). As fishes are ectotherms, the temperature of their physical environment is
304 directly correlated to physiological reactions, meaning that with increasing temperature the rate of
305 biochemical reactions increases (Harmon, 2009). Consequently, it is common practice to reduce the
306 temperature of water for transport of live fishes, for example through the addition of cool blocks in the
307 insulated boxes and transporting fishes in temperature controlled vehicles. However, optimal transport
308 temperatures vary between species and caution must be taken so that the cooling process does not incur
309 thermal stress in the fish (Harmon, 2009).

310 1.2.1.5. Poor feed management: Particularly prior to transport, fishes may be food-deprived to reduce
311 water quality deterioration through uneaten food and to reduce the amount of physical waste produced
312 by the fish which may further compromise water quality (Mørkøre *et al.*, 2008; Waagbø *et al.*, 2017).
313 During these food-deprivation periods, fishes can meet energy requirements from nutrient stores (Azodi
314 *et al.*, 2015) but long-term under-feeding in home aquaria (Mondal & Mohsin, 2014) could have
315 detrimental effects including malnutrition and excessive competition for food. However, in home
316 aquaria, the potential for overfeeding is more likely, with negative knock-on effects for water quality
317 (Priestley *et al.*, 2006; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2012; Walster *et al.*, 2015; Pleeing, & Moons, 2017). Poor
318 management of feeding conditions can result in abnormal behavioural patterns, poor overall
319 performance and increased disease susceptibility (Kulczykowska and Vázquez, 2010).

320 1.2.1.6. Inappropriate photoperiod: Photoperiod can affect fish welfare by influencing feeding
321 strategy, condition factor and feed conversion efficiency (Oppedal *et al.*, 2007; Døskeland, 2015). Not
322 only is photoperiod a main component in the synchronisation of endogenous rhythms, it also affects
323 internal processes such as metabolic rate, growth, epithelial pigmentation, reproduction and locomotor
324 activity (Boeuf & Le Bail, 1999; El-Sayed & Kawanna, 2004; Veras *et al.*, 2013; Veras *et al.*, 2014).
325 Photoperiod is often manipulated for breeding, with significant effects on growth and reproduction
326 (Giannecchini *et al.*, 2012; Arvedlund *et al.*, 2000). Light intensity is also an important consideration
327 at retail stores and for home aquaria where a trade-off exists between an intensity that optimises fish

328 colouration to the human eye (Saxena, 1994; Uthayasiva *et al.*, 2014) but that is also conducive to good
329 fish welfare.

330 1.2.1.7. Noise and vibration: Human-generated noise pollution affects fish behaviour (Sarà *et al.*,
331 2007; Neo *et al.*, 2015; Cox *et al.*, 2018) and elicits stress in fishes. For example, in zebrafish, sound
332 exposure (112 dB re 1 μ Pa) altered group cohesion, swimming velocity and location of fish in the water
333 column (Neo *et al.*, 2015). There is little existing research documenting the effect of noise during
334 transport of ornamental fishes, but oscillatory movements during transport have the potential to
335 compromise fish health (Rebouças *et al.*, 2019). A multitude of sounds and vibrations are likely to be
336 experienced by fishes in the ornamental trade including engine noise, human speech and noise from
337 aquarium filters as well as vibrations associated with noise. Aquarium filters mask auditory hearing of
338 goldfish (*Carassius auratus*), specifically when filter frequency noises are at 15-19 dB (0.1-0.3 kHz)
339 and recommendations have been made for hobbyists to purchase quiet filter setups to improve welfare
340 conditions within home aquaria (Gutscher *et al.*, 2011).

341 1.2.1.8. Medical treatments: Some chemicals that are used to eliminate potential pathogenic
342 microorganisms in ornamental fishes may be stressors in their own right. Three of the most commonly
343 used treatments for fungal, parasitic and bacterial diseases are formalin, malachite green and acriflavine,
344 all of which are routinely used prophylactically. Malachite green can lead to mortality if used at high
345 concentrations (Sudova *et al.*, 2007) and also negatively affects physiological functioning (specifically
346 carbohydrate metabolism) and behaviour in stinging catfish (*Heteropneustes fossilis*) (Srivastav &
347 Chaturvedi, 2012; Srivastav & Roy, 2018). Although it has a relatively low toxicity for fishes, formalin
348 (37% formaldehyde) can have sublethal physical effects, such as gill hyperplasia in bluespotted coridora
349 (*Corydoras melanistius*), which may have subsequent behavioural effects (Santos *et al.*, 2012).
350 Acriflavine (acriflavinium chloride) is an acridine dye that is used in some non-EU fisheries and
351 occasionally placed in transport bags with fishes coming from outside of the EU to treat external
352 protozoan and bacterial diseases (Lieke *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, acriflavine can cause fish sterility as
353 well as other species-specific differences in sensitivity (Lieke *et al.*, 2020). Consequently, some
354 chemical treatments for ornamental fishes may provoke negative biological and behavioural effects.

355 1.2.2. Operational Welfare Indicators (OWIs)

356 With increasing concern regarding animal production and animal use over recent years, there has been
357 a move to improve welfare and production systems through creating OWIs (Bonde *et al.*, 2001; Fraser,
358 2003). OWIs are individual indicators of welfare, which can be morphological, behavioural,
359 physiological, metabolic or abiotic in nature, and can be aggregated to fully assess all aspects of animal
360 welfare. To be classified as 'operational', OWIs need to be multi-faceted in nature (Segner *et al.*, 2012),

361 provide insight into an aspect of animal welfare and be easy to use without requiring laboratory analysis,
362 otherwise they may not be used by individuals involved (North *et al.*, 2008; van de Vis *et al.*, 2012;
363 Gutierrez Rabadan *et al.*, 2020). Suites of OWIs and welfare measurement methods have been
364 developed for a range of animals such as equids (Raw *et al.*, 2020), livestock (Rousing *et al.*, 2007;
365 Gladden *et al.*, 2020; Grant *et al.*, 2020; von Jasmund *et al.*, 2020), rabbits (Botelho *et al.*, 2020),
366 laboratory animals (Hawkins *et al.*, 2011), birds (Rose & O'Brien, 2020; Tremolada *et al.*, 2020),
367 mammalian companion animals (Vojtkovská *et al.*, 2020) and some species of food and cleaner fishes
368 (Martins *et al.*, 2012; Petterson *et al.*, 2013; Stein *et al.*, 2013; Imsland *et al.*, 2020; Gutierrez Rabadan
369 *et al.*, 2020). Existing welfare monitoring tools that use OWIs have created methods to quantify welfare,
370 including allocating a score/grade to quantify welfare (de Graaf *et al.*, 2018), a ranking system
371 (Kubasiewicz *et al.*, 2020), computational modelling based on attribute levels (De Mol *et al.*, 2006),
372 and needs or welfare indices (Bartussek, 1999 and Gutierrez Rabadan *et al.*, 2020 respectively).
373 Kubasiewicz *et al.* (2020) used a novel strategy of combining expert opinion of what classifies as 'most
374 important' welfare indicators and creating specific questions to address them. These questions were
375 then formulated to create a flow-chart, with scores/grades given depending on the answers, with the
376 flow chart being intuitive and understandable for both researchers and lay-people.

377 OWIs have been created for food fishes in aquaculture (see Føre *et al.*, 2018 and Sariaiva *et al.*, 2019),
378 which aim to incorporate aspects of their physiology, morphology and behaviour as well as information
379 about their environment (Ashley, 2007; Sneddon, 2007; Bovenkerk and Meijboom, 2013; Stein *et al.*,
380 2013; Noble *et al.*, 2018; Saraiva *et al.*, 2019). Recently, a combination of OWIs have been used to
381 assess lumpfish (*Cyclopterus lumpus*) welfare, including species-specific welfare indicators (external
382 body damage, relative mass and cortisol/plasma analysis). These OWIs have been validated by a range
383 of interested parties (e.g. farmers, scientists, wholesalers/importer/exporters) (Gutierrez Rabadan *et al.*,
384 2020). Noble *et al.* (2018) suggests that for OWIs to be robust and all-encompassing they need to be (i)
385 fit for purpose, (ii) species-specific, (iii) life stage and biologically specific, and (iv) realistic for
386 utilisation in specific settings. For example, the FISHWELL OWIs use the 'Five Domains' model for
387 animal welfare and apply them to salmon, employing five different categories to evaluate welfare status:
388 resource availability, environment, health, behaviour and feelings (Noble *et al.*, 2018). Essentially, the
389 evaluation of welfare depends upon an unequivocal comprehension of welfare and defined, robust
390 indicators that unambiguously quantify the variables they are measuring. To date, there are no
391 aggregated OWIs or welfare assessment matrices published on the welfare of ornamental fishes.
392 However, there is the potential for a similar strategy to those used for food-fishes to be used within the
393 ornamental fish trade due to the broad range of stakeholders, including, curators, wholesalers, retailers
394 and farmers.

395 1.2.3. Can we use current aquaculture technologies in an ornamental-setting?

396 Technological advances over the past few decades, in commercial aquaculture, have drastically
397 improved the array of techniques that are available to monitor fishes (Lucas & Baras, 2000) and many
398 of these have been applied from a welfare monitoring perspective. However, these techniques have
399 species and environment-specific limitations and do not all perform equally well. For example, the use
400 of sentinel robotics to monitor water quality within large cage food-fish aquaculture (Von Borstel *et al.*,
401 2013) would not be suitable for use in home aquaria. In food fishes, telemetry technology advances,
402 such as SmartTags, have been developed to measure OBR and be used as a fish welfare indicator
403 (Damsgård, 2008). However, for smaller fishes, one would need to consider the size of the tag relative
404 to the size of the fish. Telemetry can also be used to assess welfare in a fish farm setting by analysing
405 swimming behaviour through remote sensors and cameras in tanks, cages or ponds (Martins *et al.*,
406 2012). Electromyogram (EMG) radio transmitters can be used to indicate welfare status. In European
407 sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*), muscle activity was analysed at different stocking densities through
408 EMG and findings confirmed through haematological and serological analyses (Carbonara *et al.*, 2015).
409 Muscle activity was significantly higher at high densities (50 kg m⁻³) resulting in a higher use of
410 anaerobic substrates and energetic reserves which, consequently, reduces the ability of the fish to
411 manage additional stressors (Chandroo *et al.*, 2005; Lembo *et al.*, 2007; Carbonara *et al.*, 2015). Results
412 from telemetry technology for food fishes can therefore be used as welfare indicators in conjunction
413 with functional, behavioural and physiological analyses to create a suite of OWIs for farmed fishes.
414 However, these technologies are unlikely to be viable for ornamental fish culturing facilities,
415 wholesalers or retail stores due to the small size of ornamental fishes themselves, the small size of tanks
416 they are held in, the invasive nature of some technological approaches and relative high financial cost
417 compared to other welfare monitoring methods. With alternative methods for monitoring ornamental
418 fish welfare there is a lack of impetus to further advance these technologies for the ornamental fish
419 trade.

420 1.2.4. Identifying appropriate OWIs for the ornamental fish trade

421 Behaviour has been suggested as one of the most pertinent welfare indicators of captive animals as it
422 provides a non-invasive indication of the biological state of an organism including the animal's
423 physiological and mental state (Dawkins, 2003; Sejian *et al.*, 2011; Martins *et al.*, 2012; Cerqueira *et al.*,
424 2017; Bui *et al.*, 2019; Saraiva *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, studies have found that behaviour can be
425 reliably assessed by observers from different social backgrounds (e.g. veterinarians and farmers)
426 (Wemelsfelder *et al.*, 2001), which further validates behaviour being used as a welfare indicator. Using

427 behaviour to monitor fish welfare has the potential to improve animal health, nutrition and social
428 interactions and has the additional benefit of being non-invasive (Ashley, 2007; Huntingford *et al.*,
429 2006; Castanheira *et al.*, 2017). The use of behaviour as a tool to monitor welfare in food-fish
430 aquaculture has been reviewed previously (Sneddon, 2007; Bui *et al.*, 2019), however, despite the
431 potential use of behaviour as a monitoring tool in a broad array of settings (Ashley, 2007; Huntingford
432 *et al.*, 2006; Castanheira *et al.*, 2017), it is still considered under-utilised (Bui *et al.*, 2019). In an
433 ornamental fish-keeping setting, behavioural measurements of stress are significantly easier to obtain
434 and assess compared to physiological measures (Stevens *et al.*, 2017; Kane *et al.*, 2004; Stevens *et al.*,
435 2017). To identify potential behaviours that could be included as OWIs for the ornamental trade a
436 systematic search was carried out to identify behaviours previously measured in relation to welfare of
437 ornamental species.

438 A systematic search method using one search engine (Web of Science (Core Collection)) was used
439 (August/September 2020) to identify a range of peer-reviewed studies that monitored the effects of
440 stressors relevant to the ornamental fish trade on behaviour. Additionally, references of the identified
441 papers were searched manually to include any other relevant papers. The search terms used to identify
442 the papers were “behavio*”, “fish*” and “welfare”, with Boolean operators used. Original search terms
443 included the term “ornamental”, but this resulted in very limited search results and was therefore
444 removed. Due to the broad range of studies analysing the welfare of food fishes, the inclusion criteria
445 were refined to only include studies that monitored the effects of stressors associated with the
446 ornamental fish trade in an ornamental fish species and focussed on behaviour as a measurable
447 parameter. Only peer-reviewed primary research was included and was further limited by only including
448 quantitative studies. Initially, titles and abstracts were assessed for relevance by MJ and once identified,
449 full papers were analysed for relevance against the inclusion/exclusion criteria ($n = 23$). Through
450 manually searching references of relevant papers, additional papers were included ($n = 13$) with a total
451 of 36 relevant papers identified. While a systematic-type search method was used, the aim was to
452 identify a wide range of behavioural measures that have been previously used in ornamental fishes,
453 rather than to provide an exhaustive list of previous studies.

454 The results identified fish behaviours that have been widely measured in ornamental fishes and are
455 commonly accepted as indicators of welfare (Table 1.1). These include feeding/foraging behaviour
456 (Leal *et al.*, 2011), aggression (Earley *et al.*, 2006; Portz *et al.*, 2006), neophobia (Martins *et al.*, 2011;
457 Champneys *et al.*, 2018), gasping at the water surface (Small *et al.*, 2014) and locomotor activity
458 (Begum *et al.*, 2006; Navarro *et al.*, 2014). Although not included within the systematic search inclusion
459 criteria, changes in ventilation rate (Berschick *et al.*, 1987; Mikheev *et al.*, 2014), and observations of
460 physical damage (e.g. to fins, scale loss) represent non-invasive measures that could be combined with
461 behavioural observations as suitable OWIs. Each of these potential indicators is discussed below.

462 Table 1.1. Studies that have monitored the effects of stressors relevant to the ornamental trade on ornamental fish behaviours. These studies were found using a systematic-type
 463 approach whereby keywords (behavio* AND fish* AND welfare) were used to identify relevant publications within the Web of Science search engine. In addition to this, the
 464 references of the identified papers were searched manually to include any relevant papers that were not found using the search terms.

Stressor	Species	Behavioural parameters measured	Outcome	Reference
Handling methods/ physical habitat	Three-spined sticklebacks (<i>Gasterosteus aculeatus</i>)	Assays: scototaxis (black/white), diving, scototaxis and diving combined, novel object recognition (NOR) and open-field (OF) tests. Behaviours analysed in NOR and OF: exploratory behaviour, mean distance from centre of tank, mean swimming speed, latency to enter central zone. Diving and scototaxis: mean time spent in bottom of tank, mean time spent in black side of tank, mean distance from bottom corner of black tank (safest area), mean swimming speed.	Fish preferred black areas of tank than white tanks. In the open field test, handling method had no significant effect on behaviour, but some measured behaviours differed over time. In the NOR, net handled fish had a lower mean distance from the novel object than box handled fish when tested in the black tank. Fish significantly decreased mean speed after introduction of novel object, however, speed increased during the 5 minutes post-introduction. Diving and scototaxis testing: Net handled fish spent a significantly longer time in the black side of the test tank - however preference varied over the duration of the experiment. Time spent at the bottom of the tank decreased over time.	Thompson <i>et al.</i> , 2016
Handling methods	Three-spined sticklebacks (<i>Gasterosteus aculeatus</i>); Panamanian bishops (<i>Brachyraphis episcopi</i>); rainbow trout (<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>)	Behavioural temperament assays (motivation to leave shelter) and neophobia analysis through novel object avoidance. Only <i>G. aculeatus</i> and <i>B. episcopi</i> were used for behavioural assays.	There were species-dependent and size-dependent differences in shelter emergence times depending on handling method (net/scoop). Handling method did not have a significant effect on neophobia in <i>G. aculeatus</i> . However, net-handled <i>B. episcopi</i> spent significantly longer near the novel object, with size-dependent difference in novel object proximity also found.	Brydges <i>et al.</i> , 2009
Light intensity	Acará tinga (<i>Geophagus proximus</i>), Nile	Chasing, circling, frontal display, lateral fight, lateral	High light intensity resulted in an increase in fighting latency in <i>G. proximus</i> and <i>O. niloticus</i> but not <i>P. scalare</i> . High light intensity	Carvalho <i>et al.</i> , 2012

	tilapia (<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>), angelfish (<i>Pterophyllum scalare</i>)	threat, mouth fight, nipping and undulation.	decreased chasing, circling and lateral fighting in <i>O. niloticus</i> ; increased frontal display and mouth fight in <i>P. scalare</i> and had no effect on <i>G. proximus</i> agonistic behaviours.	
Light intensity	Amazonian cichlid (<i>Laetacara fulvipinnis</i>)	Specific agonistic behaviours: frontal display, mouth fight, nipping, chasing, parallel display, threat, undulation and flight.	Light intensity increases agonistic behaviours, and interferes with social hierarchy stability which, consequently, may result in a stressful environment which may compromise welfare. High light intensity decreased fighting latency, increased threat frequency, number of attacks and flight number, which resulted in a destabilised social hierarchy.	Sarmiento <i>et al.</i> , 2017
Noise	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Acoustic response tendency in relation to sound field conditions.	No correlation between behavioural response intensity, quality, or directionality and sound pressure or ellipticity and directivity of particle motion. However, there was a negative correlation found between freezing tendency and particle velocity level.	Campbell <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Noise	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Assays: novel tank test and light-dark test. NTT behaviours observed: Time at top, middle and bottom zones of tank, number of bottom entries, distance travelled in each zone, absolute turn angle in each zone, total time mobile. LDT behaviours observed: light zone rotations, distance travelled, mean speed and time spent in each zone.	Overall, fish exposed to music displayed less anxiety-like behaviours during the NTT and were less active and calmer during the LDT.	Barcellos <i>et al.</i> , 2018
Noise	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Swimming behaviour: startle frequency, swimming speed and depth variance. Foraging behaviour: food discrimination and food handling errors.	Sound exposure affects swimming behaviour and foraging efficiency, with intermittent sound having a more profound effect than continuous sound.	Shafiei Sabet <i>et al.</i> , 2015

Noise	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>) and Lake Victoria cichlid (<i>Haplochromis piceatus</i>)	Exploration and frequency of freezing, rapid turns and erratic swimming.	Swimming speed was species-dependent. In both species, sound exposure reduced prolonged swimming speed. Zebrafish exploratory behaviour was not affected by sound, but cichlids did change their vertical distribution and spent longer in the bottom of the tank. Overall, sound exposure can result in both similar and species-specific behavioural responses with responses not being related to hearing ability.	Shafiei Sabet <i>et al.</i> , 2016
Novel environment	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Group structure, proximity, shoaling, social and spatial metrics.	Under acute stress, fish shoaled in significantly higher densities, with a lower variation in neighbour distances with increased proximity to walls compared to the same group tested 24 hours later, therefore suggesting that there was a reduction in acute stress.	Kleinhappel <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Nutrition	<i>Simochromis pleurospilus</i>	Cognitive performance testing. Behaviours measured: latency to leave neutral shelter, latency to enter choice area and visual cue by fish.	Fish that had a change in food ration amount in early life significantly outperformed their constant ration counterparts during the learning test, irrespective of the direction of food ration change.	Kotrschal & Taborsky, 2010
Physical habitat	Amazonian zebra pleco (<i>Hypancistrus zebra</i>)	Preference tests depending on time within refuges.	Fish spent the longest in clay shelters followed by the natural rock shelter, outside the shelter and in the PVC shelter, with there being a significant difference amongst shelter types.	Ramos <i>et al.</i> , 2012
Physical habitat	Dwarf cichlid (<i>Apistogramma agassizii</i>)	Agonistic behaviours – chases, tail beats, bites and shelter use.	Shelter use was not influenced by enrichment conditions but was monopolised by dominant individuals. Biting frequency changed in response to habitat enrichment.	Kochhann & Val, 2016
Physical habitat	Goldfish (<i>Carassius auratus</i>)	Motivation testing (novel) through swimming against flow and preference tests.	Fish preferred planted areas but did not discriminate between real/artificial plants. Water currents can be used as a novel method of identifying fish motivation.	Sullivan <i>et al.</i> , 2016
Physical habitat	Goldfish (<i>Carassius auratus</i>)	Foraging, foraging bout number and mean foraging bout length.	Foraging was significantly affected by enrichment particle size, with there being particle-size dependent preferences in certain substrates.	Smith & Gray, 2011

Physical habitat	Three-spined sticklebacks (<i>Gasterosteus aculeatus</i>)	Learning and memory assays using 3 foraging compartments: latency to feed and compartment preference recorded. Temperament assay: boldness, neophobia, activity.	No effect of housing environment on learning or behaviour, but there was a significant effect on memory retention.	Brydges & Braithwaite, 2009
Physical habitat	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Novel tank test and environmental preference choice tank, with associated observed behaviours, such as aggression.	There was no significant difference found between fish in enriched and non-enriched tanks in relation to latency to enter the top half of the tank. However, overall, fish from enriched tanks spent longer in the top of the tank compared to fish from barren tanks. There was no significant preference observed in relation to choice tank test.	Lee <i>et al.</i> , 2018
Physical habitat	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Preference tests in relation to differing enrichment cues.	Dominant individuals in pairs significantly preferred substrate and also behaviourally excluded the subordinate individual. In groups, there were significant preferences for substrates and plants compared to barren conditions.	Schroeder <i>et al.</i> , 2014
Physical habitat	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Activity level, shoaling density, aggression and time spent in bottom of tank.	Activity levels and shoaling density were not significantly affected by structure presence. In structured tanks, aggression remained high during days 1-5, with it reducing by day 7. In control tanks, reduced aggression levels were observed 2 days earlier which suggests the presence of structures reduces the time it takes for dominance/subordinate establishment.	Wilkes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
Physical habitat	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Feeding and chasing behaviours.	Aggression exhibited by dominant fish was higher in simple habitats compared to the complex habitats. The number of prey items eaten did not differ between habitats. Fish that conducted more aggressive behaviours (chase rate) ate more food in both habitats.	Basquill & Grant, 1997
Physical habitat	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Aggression, foraging (latency to feed – feed motivation), shoaling distances, feeding motivation.	Vegetation presence increases aggression whereas water flow decreased feeding latency after disturbance - however, behavioural patterns were population dependent.	Bhat <i>et al.</i> , 2015

			Environmental conditions had a significant effect on shoal cohesion, but population did not.	
Physical habitat	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Aggression, nipping and chasing.	Fish showed reduced aggression levels in tanks with enrichment compared to bare tanks. Spatial complexity affected aggression, additionally, where high aggression levels affected fecundity.	Carfagnini <i>et al.</i> , 2009
Physical habitat	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Preference scores from Jacobs; preference index.	A significant preference for enriched + swimming zones, with fish significantly avoiding swimming only and plain zones.	DePasquale <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Physical habitat	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Preference test. Time in each compartment, latency to exit respective compartment.	There was a significant preference for the dark chamber during the place-preference test. In the latency experiment, fish placed in the dark environment took longer to exit than fish placed in the light compartment.	Serra <i>et al.</i> , 1999
Physical habitat	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>) and three-spined sticklebacks (<i>Gasterosteus aculeatus</i>)	Scan counts of presence in each zone which were used to calculate Jacobs' preference index (preference/ avoidance).	There were species-dependent preferences for enrichment, with <i>D. rerio</i> showing no significant preference and <i>G. aculeatus</i> showing significant preference for both shelter types.	Jones <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Physical habitat	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>), checker barbs (<i>Puntius oligolepis</i>)	Behavioural diversity, exploration, foraging, resting, locomotion, socio-positive behaviour, socio-negative behaviour, mating behaviour, comfort behaviour and "stereotypy". Preference tests and space usage was also analysed.	Fish showed similar behavioural diversity between the structured and non-structured tanks. However, there were significantly higher levels of "stereotypy" in barren tanks, indicating a significant preference for tanks with environmental complexity.	Kistler <i>et al.</i> , 2011
Physical habitat/ stocking density	Goldfish (<i>Carassius auratus</i>)	Foraging, position relative to cover (simple/ complex) and orientation relative to cover.	The presence of cover significantly affected the position and orientation of the fish. However, the presence of protective cover had no effect on fish positioning or orientation. Coverage had no effect on foraging behaviours.	Ingrum <i>et al.</i> , 2010
Physical habitat/ habitat/	Midas cichlid (<i>Amphilophus citrinellus</i>)	Biting, chasing, charging, lateral displays, operculum flares, territoriality, foraging,	Dominant individuals exhibited increased aggressive bouts in relation to increased number of competitors. In subordinate fish, cowering	Oldfield, 2011

stocking density		cowering, escaping, resting, hovering, hiding, digging and swimming behaviour.	behaviours had a strong negative correlation with increasing group size, but not habitat complexity. Aggressive behaviours were not associated with varying stocking density; however, aggression was lower in complex tank environments.	
Physical habitat/ stocking density	<i>Serrapinnus notomelas</i>	Attack, foraging, <i>per capita</i> aggressiveness and foraging.	Environmental enrichment had no effect on aggression, but larger group sizes reduced aggressiveness.	da Silva <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Social composition/ physical habitat	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Behavioural assays: novel tank test, light-dark, and place-preference tests. Behaviours measured: NTT - number of transitions into top of tank, total time in top of tank, erratic movements. LD: number of transitions into white zone, total time in white zone, and number of shuttling exploration. PPT: number of transitions into enrichment, number of transitions into zone with conspecifics, erratic movements, duration and number of times spent immobile.	Fish that were housed in barren tanks on their own significantly increased anxiety-like behaviours in the NTT and dark-light preference test. This treatment group, as well as both group-housed treatment groups spent a significantly longer time interacting with conspecifics than the enrichment in the place-preference test.	Collymore <i>et al.</i> , 2015
Species composition	Blunthead cichlid (<i>Tropheus moorii</i>)	Agonistic behaviours, hierarchy linearity index and aggression socio-matrices.	Aggression reduced immediately after the introduction of the novel individuals, with linearity and steepness levels decreasing alongside an increase in unknown relationships.	Palagi <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Stocking density/ light intensity/ nutrition	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Fin displays, fluttering, aggression, mouth gaping, chatter.	Stocking density and light spectra had no effect on behaviour. Food deprivation only had a significant effect on fluttering frequency, with fluttering increasing significantly in fish deprived of food for 72/ 216 h compared to 24 h.	Gronquist & Berges, 2012

Stocking density/ species composition	Neon tetras (<i>Paracheirodon innesi</i>); white cloud mountain minnows (<i>Tanichthys albonubes</i>); angelfish (<i>Pterophyllum scalare</i>); tiger barbs (<i>Barbus tetrazona</i>)	Darting, aggression, shoaling, neighbour index and interaction with tank enrichment (intra and interspecific).	Angelfish reduced aggressive behaviours in small shoals; white cloud mountain minnows and neon tetras increased natural behaviours.	Slovan <i>et al.</i> , 2011
Stocking density/species composition	Neon tetras (<i>Paracheirodon innesi</i>); white cloud mountain minnows (<i>Tanichthys albonubes</i>); angelfish (<i>Pterophyllum scalare</i>); tiger barbs (<i>Barbus tetrazona</i>)	Darting, aggression, shoaling, latency to feed, neighbour index and time in tank enrichment.	Group size on behaviour is species-specific. Combinations of behavioural indicators within principal components analysis identifies group sizes which improve welfare.	Saxby <i>et al.</i> , 2010
Transportation/ physical habitat	Variatus platy (<i>Xiphophorus variatus</i>)	Biting, chasing, erratic swimming. Behavioural observations measured manually and through video analysis.	Significantly lower numbers of erratic swimming and chases observed immediately post-transport in fish transported in bags with enrichment.	Vanderzwalmen <i>et al.</i> , 2020b
Transportation/ water quality	Variatus platy (<i>Xiphophorus variatus</i>)	Chases, biting, erratic swimming, ventilation rate. Behavioural observations measured manually and through video analysis.	No significant effect of Stress Coat® on mortality during actual transport or body condition but did improve behavioural indicators.	Vanderzwalmen <i>et al.</i> , 2020a
Water quality/ Water renewal	Angelfish (<i>Pterophyllum scalare</i>)	Attack frequency and aggressive displays.	Aggressive behaviours reduced significantly faster in tanks that had only 25% of their water changed compared to tanks that had 50% of their water changed.	dos Santos Gauy <i>et al.</i> , 2018

466 1.2.5. Behavioural OWIs

467 1.2.5.1. Feeding/Foraging

468 Twenty-seven percent ($n=10$) of the 36 papers found during the systematic review (Table 1) used
469 changes in foraging and/or feeding behaviours as an indicator of welfare. Foraging is defined as
470 exploration for and exploitation of resources (Turnbull & Kadri, 2007), and in fishes, the behaviours
471 associated with this can be influenced by both abiotic and biotic conditions (Kittilsen *et al.*, 2009;
472 Catano *et al.*, 2016; Murray *et al.*, 2016; Pimentel *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, feeding and foraging
473 behaviours could be used to detect welfare problems within the different stages of the ornamental fish
474 trade (Øverli *et al.*, 2006; Martins *et al.*, 2009), although this would likely not be appropriate during
475 transport. In addition to changes to feeding motivation, feed intake is also routinely used in aquaculture
476 as a direct indicator of poor welfare (Santos *et al.*, 2010). For example, after transportation when fishes
477 are placed in retail tanks, analysing the latency to begin feeding (feed motivation) and how much is
478 consumed (feed intake) could elucidate whether there are any welfare problems that need addressing
479 such as disease, injury or poor water quality.

480 1.2.5.2. Aggression

481 In both captivity and natural habitats, many fish species aggressively defend available resources, such
482 as food, mates or territory, and may establish dominance hierarchies (Peake & McGregor, 2004). In
483 natural environments, fishes may be able to escape their attacker but this is often not possible in
484 captivity. Behaviours such as attacking (chase, bite, charge, mouth wrestling/locking) or displaying
485 (operculum flare, lateral displaying, colouration change, vocalisation, electric organ discharges) are
486 indicators of direct aggression in fishes (Peake & McGregor, 2004; Oldfield, 2011). Aggressive
487 behaviours are frequently measured to provide insight into fish welfare; of the 36 papers identified
488 (Table 1.1), 50% ($n=18$) used aggression as a behavioural parameter measurement. Aggressive
489 behaviours can increase when a feeding technique is unsuitable for the species (for instance if fishes are
490 fed too little it can result in resource competition and guarding) (Andrew *et al.*, 2002), social
491 compositions and/ or densities are incompatible (for example placing two highly territorial species
492 together or too many fishes in the same tank) (Adams *et al.*, 2000) as well as when enrichment is lacking
493 (Merighe *et al.*, 2004). Therefore, increased pervasiveness of aggression could be an indicator that
494 something is compromising welfare. However, according to the natural-based welfare approach, a
495 certain level of these behaviours would be classified as natural as they would be performed in the wild.
496 For example, clownfishes (Pomacentridae) reside in social groups where numerous agonistic
497 interactions occur that are important to the maintenance of social hierarchy and dominance
498 establishment (Colleye & Parmentier, 2012). Thus lack of aggressive interactions could also indicate
499 welfare issues.

500 The incidence of aggressive behaviours occurs across different fish species and is diverse in its
501 prevalence. Territorial behaviour, such as being stationed near a shelter, refuge or feeding area, can be
502 an indicator of indirect aggression in some ornamental fish species (such as angelfish, *Pterophyllum*
503 *scalare*) (Brandão *et al.*, 2021), but not all (such as the dwarf cichlid, *Apistogramma agassizi*)
504 (Kochhann & Val, 2017). Consequently, it is imperative to create OWIs that are both species-specific
505 and also based upon the behavioural repertoire of the chosen species (e.g. whether the species is
506 territorial or not). If the behaviour of one fish causes injury or undue stress to another, it is likely to
507 compromise the welfare of that specific animal. Additionally, when aggression levels become excessive
508 it can indicate that the individual exhibiting the behaviour is doing so because its welfare is
509 compromised and it is showing stress-like behaviours. For aggression to be used as an OWI, it not only
510 needs to take into account the welfare and behaviour of individual fish but also (if applicable) the group
511 of fish housed together, in conjunction with a thorough understanding of the behavioural repertoire of
512 the fish species, or group of species, whose OWI will be created.

513 Despite a clear link between acute short-term stress responses and coping strategies (the way in which
514 fish cope with a stressful situation), there is limited information available regarding chronic long-term
515 stress responses and respective coping strategies (Castanheira *et al.*, 2017). Stocking density affected
516 coping strategies in African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*), with higher stocking densities (considered in
517 this study as a chronic stress) resulting in an increased feed conversion ratio and overall feeding activity,
518 alongside lowered agonistic behaviour (van de Nieuwegiessen *et al.*, 2010). Evidently, coping strategies
519 play an essential role in how individuals adapt to their housing environment and thereby their individual
520 welfare (Castanheira *et al.*, 2017). However, as a whole, individual coping strategies should not be used
521 as welfare indicators, but inferences from individual behaviours can potentially be made to identify a
522 welfare problem (Galhardo *et al.*, 2008; Wemelsfelder & Mullan, 2014). Additionally, as different
523 species have different behavioural and social traits, such as territoriality and dominance/size-based
524 hierarchies (Sloman & Armstrong, 2002; Oliveira *et al.*, 2002; Oliveira *et al.*, 2003), it is crucial that
525 the person observing aggressive behaviour as a welfare indicator is familiar with the species and able
526 to distinguish between normal and abnormal levels of aggressive behaviours.

527 1.2.5.3. Swimming behaviour

528 The use of swimming behaviour in the assessment of fish welfare relies on the observer's ability to
529 distinguish normal and abnormal swimming behaviours which can be problematic. Nevertheless, it is
530 still one of the most widely used parameters when attempting to appraise fish welfare (Table 1.1). The
531 most prevalent ways in which swimming behaviour is quantified include speed, absence of swimming,
532 rapid changes in direction, erratic swimming, tank depth variance and utilisation, startle speed,
533 shuttling, shoaling distances and group swimming cohesion. Half of the behaviour papers identified in
534 Table 1.1 ($n=18$) used swimming behaviour as a measurable parameter.

535 The way in which groups of fish swim together (for example in cages and ponds) is the most commonly
536 used OWI to evaluate farmed fish welfare (Martins *et al.*, 2012). However, studies into social dynamics
537 have found that one fish can dictate the behaviour of a whole group (Romey, 1996), highlighting that
538 interpretations of group behaviours can give false indications of welfare as they do not consider the
539 welfare of individuals within the group. This is especially true when fishes are kept at high stocking
540 densities as they can adopt polarised schooling behaviour, purely to reduce the potential for collisions
541 (Føre *et al.*, 2018). However, separating individuals from their conspecifics or social group may prevent
542 the fish from displaying their full behavioural repertoire in an experimental setting, with social
543 separation increasing stress intensity in very social species (Kleinhappel *et al.*, 2019).

544 Swimming behaviours (such as erratic movements, chases, and latency to enter sections of a tank) are
545 routinely used in ethograms when analysing stress in fishes. *D. rerio* alter their swimming behaviour
546 by either adjusting their swimming frequency or type of swimming patterns when exposed to negative
547 conditions (Reilly *et al.*, 2008; White *et al.*, 2017), highlighting how swimming behaviour can be an
548 indirect indicator of poor welfare conditions. Guppies (*Poecilia reticulata*) adapt their shoaling and
549 swimming behaviour to their actual social environment and whether there is a perceived predation threat
550 (Croft *et al.*, 2003). There are stark differences in natural swimming behaviours between different
551 species, such as shoaling fishes (e.g. neon tetras, *Paracheirodon innesi*) and nocturnal burrowing fishes
552 (e.g. Kuhli loaches, *Acanthopthalmus kuhlii*). Thus classification of swimming behaviours as ‘normal’
553 or ‘abnormal’ is both species- and context-dependent.

554 Some ornamental fishes are bred for their elaborate ornamentation through artificial morphological
555 selection, such as colouration, body, tail and eye morphological variants, which are deemed more
556 appealing to consumers (Ota *et al.*, 2016; Rasal *et al.*, 2016). For example, some *D. rerio* have been
557 genetically modified to have aesthetically pleasing exaggerated fins, which are classified as *long fin*
558 (Gumm *et al.*, 2009). However, *long fin D. rerio* have significant swimming deficiencies as a result of
559 their mutant fins compared to their *short fin* (truncated fins) and wild type counterparts (Gumm *et al.*,
560 2009). This is in contrast to male threadfin rainbowfish (*Iriatherina wernerii*) whose lavish
561 ornamentations do not appear to impede swimming performance (Trappett *et al.*, 2013). The effects of
562 morphological variations on swimming behaviour across ornamental fish species make it increasingly
563 difficult to create generalised OWIs for ornamental fishes. While it would be unrealistic and impractical
564 to create species-specific OWIs for individual ornamental fish species, grouping species together
565 dependent on morphological and behavioural traits may facilitate creation of a suite of welfare
566 monitoring tools for use within the trade.

567 1.2.6. Non-behavioural OWIs

568 1.2.6.1. Morphological observations (colouration, fin damage, trauma)

569 Although guidance exists for assessment of fish welfare by eye, there is a focus on direct signs of ill
570 health (e.g. social isolation, lesions, bites) rather than behaviours. Depending on the stressor and
571 species, monitoring welfare by eye can present distinct challenges (Deakin *et al.*, 2019). Stress can
572 induce colour changes in the skin and eyes of some fishes, including ornamental species. Compared to
573 fish reared at low density, sand gobies (*Pomatoschistus minutus*) reared at a higher density had
574 significantly darker eyes (lower luminance values) which was positively correlated with skin darkening
575 (Sköld *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, the eyes of guppies (*P. reticulata*) darken when exposed to a predator,
576 another indicator that colour changes can be used as an indicator of stress and negative welfare
577 (Magurran & Seghers, 1991).

578 Physical injuries, such as dorsal fin injuries and erosion in salmonids and dislodged scales in ornamental
579 fishes, can be suggestive of poor welfare. This is particularly true for ornamental species with long
580 delicate fins, as there is a potential for fraying. Poor handling techniques and inappropriate transport
581 methods can also result in injuries (Belema *et al.*, 2017), and increase susceptibility to bacteria such as
582 the highly pathogenic *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* - a causative agent of tail rot and a common disease in
583 ornamental fishes (Marudhupandi *et al.*, 2017). Consequently, using observations of physical injuries
584 in combination with behaviour could be used to assess the welfare of ornamental fishes.

585 1.2.6.2. Ventilation/respiration

586 Stress results in a high oxygen demand, met by an increased ventilation rate through buccal movements
587 and/or opercular beating. Opercular beat rate (OBR) is, therefore, a good indicator of stress in some
588 situations and can be counted either automatically, for example through biosensor technology, or by
589 eye (Eckroth *et al.*, 2014). Increased OBR may be attributable to stress and also indicative of low
590 dissolved oxygen and gill problems (Noble *et al.*, 2018). However, lethargic behaviour or inactivity
591 combined with a decreased OBR may also indicate low dissolved oxygen levels (Domenici *et al.*, 2007).
592 Through calculating OBR and amplitude of OBR, an index of ventilation activity can be created and
593 from this welfare can be assessed (Brown *et al.*, 2005).

594 1.2.6.3. Infections/ disease

595 Visual observations of infections and diseases and/or symptoms, such as flashing and substrate rubbing,
596 can be used as an effective, non-invasive tool for anti-parasitic aquaculture applications in three ways:
597 (i) being an OWI of infection status; (ii) enhancing resistance to diseases and parasites; and (iii)
598 improving welfare through the use of encouraging behaviours via adaptive learning (Bui *et al.*, 2019).
599 Indirect indicators of compromised health and subsequently welfare, can be observed in individuals (in
600 which case, prophylactic medicinal treatment or feed deprivation interventions can be put in place) or
601 in groups (whereby quarantine or more invasive measures will need to be taken) (Huntingford *et al.*,

602 2006). Behaviour is the primary line of defence for fishes against diseases and parasites with some
603 behaviours limiting exposure to infection and therefore have the potential to be used to develop host
604 resistance (Hart, 2011).

605 1.3. Conclusion: Creating OWIs for ornamental fishes

606 Good animal husbandry conditions and practices can produce fishes that are less stressed, less prone to
607 disease, are in better physiological condition and consequently have better welfare. Although there is
608 an increasing amount of fish welfare research, it has primarily focussed on food-fish species
609 (Braithwaite and Ebbesson, 2014) with limited research into improving welfare within the ornamental
610 fish trade. It is evident that at every stage of the ornamental fish supply chain, fishes are exposed to
611 stressors that have the potential to be detrimental to their welfare. Combining the behavioural
612 parameters identified through systematic review (Table 1.1) and the additional non-invasive measures
613 discussed above, Table 1.2 presents potential OWIs for ornamental fishes. OWIs need to be fully
614 comprehensive and incorporate multiple measurable parameters which the fishes come into contact
615 with, to counteract any effects from avoidable stressors. Existing welfare monitoring tools have the
616 tendency to address four welfare categories: living environment, nutrition, health/injury and behaviour.
617 However, with increased acknowledgement that transport is a significant stressor for ornamental fishes,
618 transport conditions should be included within the welfare categories. Aggregated welfare constructs
619 are often developed using available scientific knowledge and input from expert panels and stakeholders
620 (Botreau *et al.*, 2007a; Botreau *et al.*, 2007b) and the development of successful OWIs for the
621 ornamental trade will depend on collaboration across a range of parties.

622 Table 1.2. Example of operational welfare indicators with correlating worst- and best-case scenarios in relation to ornamental fish welfare. Worst case scenarios are likely to
 623 be indicative of very poor welfare, whereas best case scenarios are likely to be indicative of good welfare. Y/N indicates Yes/No.

Welfare category	Operational Welfare Indicators	Example measures	Worst case	Best case
Behaviour	Aggression	Attack bouts Aggressive displays Chasing Biting	Large numbers of aggressive behaviours which compromise the welfare of tank mates.	Limited numbers of aggressive behaviour bouts; welfare of conspecifics not compromised.
	Species compatibility	Attack bouts Aggressive displays Chasing Biting Territoriality Shoaling	Inappropriate species behavioural compatibility resulting in aggressive behaviours which compromise the welfare of tank mates.	Species chosen to be housed together are compatible and able to express natural behaviours without compromising welfare of conspecifics.
	Swimming behaviour	Erratic movement Freezing Darting Thigmotaxis Stereotypy	High numbers of erratic movements, significant time spent immobile, significant neophobia, pacing (glass surfing), excessive thigmotaxis.	‘Normal/natural’ swimming behaviour
	Feeding	Foraging Feeding	Loss of appetite/ not eating or foraging.	Normal eating and foraging behaviours
Living environment	Physical enrichment (if appropriate for species)	Plants Shelter Substrate	No enrichment.	Presence of physical enrichment in tank.
	Social composition	Y/ N	Inappropriate social composition for species.	Appropriate social composition for species.
	Water quality	pH Dissolved oxygen Ammonia Nitrite/nitrate	Outside of optimum water quality parameters.	Within optimum water quality parameters.
	Photoperiod	Lighting Y/ N	Inappropriate photoperiod regime for the species.	Lighting kept on a strict photoperiod regime.
	Noise	Quiet internal filter Y/ N Physical location of tank	Loud internal filter, with the tank being placed in an area with lots of noise.	Quiet internal filter, with tank kept in a quieter area away from loud noises.
Nutrition	Appropriate nutrition profile	Y/ N	Inappropriate feed for species.	Appropriate feed for species.
	Live feed (if applicable to species)	Y /N	No live feed supplementation.	Live feed supplementation.
	Feed amount	Amount suitable for species and number of fish Y/ N	Too much feed resulting in poor water quality and/or obese fish. Too little feed resulting in emaciated fish.	Appropriate amount of feed for species and number of fish.
	Evidence of injury	Lesions/ wounds	Extensive evidence of injuries.	No evidence of injury.

Overall health		Missing scales Fin damage		
	Evidence of disease	Fin rot White spot Disease-related behaviours	Obvious evidence of disease (e.g. parasites, infections, disease such as white spot, fin rot, appetite loss).	No obvious evidence of disease.
	Evidence of malnutrition	Scoliosis Obesity Lordosis Skin de-pigmentation Rapid ventilation	Obvious evidence of malnutrition/obesity.	No obvious evidence of malnutrition.
Transportation conditions	Water quality	pH Dissolved oxygen Ammonia Nitrite/nitrate	Outside of optimum water quality parameters.	Within optimum water quality parameters.
	Noise	Packaging Y/ N	Excessive amounts of noise.	Limited amounts of noise with adequate packaging to dampen sound.
	Mechanical disturbance	Packaging Y/ N	No packaging to limit mechanical disturbance, potential for bag rupture.	Adequate packaging to reduce potential for excessive mechanical disturbance, fish double-bagged to prevent rupture.

624 Due to the broad range of species being traded, a one-size-fits-all approach is not likely to be suitable.
625 The creation of a suite of non-specialist OWIs with a focus on behaviour may aid in identifying when
626 welfare is becoming compromised. Furthermore, with an increase in popularity in keeping ornamental
627 fishes, creating standardised legislation and husbandry standards for every stage of the ornamental
628 fish supply chain is essential to improve welfare. Moreover, with purchasers becoming increasingly
629 conscious of animal welfare, ensuring that fishes come from ethical sources and are not exposed to
630 poor welfare conditions may make the ornamental fish trade even more profitable. For welfare to be
631 improved, there needs to be a conscious effort made by all involved within the ornamental fish supply
632 chain with a combination of stakeholders contributing towards a solution on how to rectify welfare
633 issues as and when they arise. This starts with improving education of what constitutes poor welfare
634 and how it can be remediated, alongside in-depth research regarding the improvement of ornamental
635 fish welfare and the development of an ornamental fish welfare monitoring tool that utilises non-
636 invasive OWIs.

637 Therefore: the main aim of this thesis was to investigate ways to improve the welfare of ornamental
638 fish during and post-transport. The secondary aim was to identify novel enrichment types for
639 ornamental fishes to actively promote positive welfare. These aims were achieved through the
640 following objectives:

- 641 1. Review current literature regarding the known stressors of ornamental fish and identify
642 potential non-invasive Operational Welfare Indicators (OWIs) to be used within the
643 ornamental fish trade (Chapter 1).
- 644 2. Investigate the effects of a novel and commercially available water conditioners on fish
645 behaviour post-transport (Chapters 2 and 5).
- 646 3. Investigate whether social enrichment can be a viable method of reducing stress and recovery
647 post-transport (Chapter 3).
- 648 4. Examine the effects of a novel natural compound on fish behaviour and physiology post-
649 transport (Chapter 4).

650 The final chapter provides a summary and discussion of the main findings of the thesis and suggests
651 future directions to build upon this research.

652 Chapter 2: The effects of a novel water conditioner on fish behaviour
653 post-transportation

654 This chapter has been submitted as an industrial report to Mars WALTHAM. As it contains confidential
655 information about the development of a new water conditioner it will not be published in the peer-
656 reviewed literature.

657 2.1. Abstract

658 Ornamental fishes are often transported over long distances from their origin to destination country,
659 regardless of whether they are wild-caught or originate from aquaculture, with the process exposing
660 fish to stressors that could be detrimental to their welfare. One of the ways of reducing transport stress
661 is to improve water quality through the addition of water conditioners. The novel water conditioner
662 tested in the present study contains three main components that remove ammonia, de-toxify chlorine
663 and chloramine, and bind trace metals. While commercial water conditioners are tested for their efficacy
664 in improving water quality, it is important to understand whether there are any concomitant effects, for
665 example on fish behaviour. The aim of this research was to identify any effects of this novel water
666 conditioner during regional transport of variatus platy (*Xiphophorus variatus*) through behavioural
667 analyses. The novel water conditioner was added to transport bags (with n=9 bags and without n=9
668 bags) for transport from a UK wholesaler to UK retail stores (< 7 h transport time), with water quality
669 samples taken on arrival in store. Videos of the fish in tanks at the retailer were taken on days 2, 4 and
670 8 after arrival, and behaviours analysed. There were no significant effects of the novel water conditioner
671 found on aggression (direct: biting; indirect: chasing), erratic movements or ventilation rate but fish on
672 day 2 that had been transported with the novel water conditioner spent a significantly longer time
673 immobile. Water quality remained high for the duration of the transport and there was no difference in
674 water quality between the control and bags containing the novel water conditioner. Overall, the addition
675 of the novel water conditioner did not appear to cause any major changes in fish behaviour post-
676 transport.

677 2.2. Introduction

678 The ornamental trade of freshwater and marine organisms has become a proliferative global industry
679 over the past decades, with the current (legal and legitimate) trade globally worth between \$15-20
680 billion *per annum* and £400 million *per annum* for the UK economy (Leal *et al.*, 2015; King, 2019;
681 Pouli *et al.*, 2019). Current estimations suggest that 1.3 billion individual ornamental fishes are
682 harvested, transported and sold annually (King, 2019). Ornamental fishes are often transported over
683 long distances from their origin to destination country, regardless of whether they are wild-caught or
684 originate from aquaculture (Brinn *et al.*, 2012; Metar *et al.*, 2018; Sampaio *et al.*, 2019). The
685 transportation process can expose ornamental fishes to stressors that could be detrimental to their
686 welfare (Stevens *et al.*, 2017; Masud *et al.*, 2019). Some of the most common stressors that fishes can
687 encounter during transportation include variable stocking density, mechanical disturbance, oxygen
688 depletion and poor water quality (Stevens *et al.*, 2017; Chapter 1). Increased stress can have detrimental
689 effects on the overall health and welfare of fishes, therefore, reducing these stressors can be beneficial
690 (Braithwaite & Ebbesson, 2014; Parodi *et al.*, 2014; Sneddon *et al.*, 2016).

691 Ornamental fishes are usually transported in plastic bags without a mechanical filtration system, in some
692 instances for > 12 h (Portz *et al.*, 2006). One of the main problems during the transport of ornamental
693 fishes is that water quality parameters can deviate from optimum ranges; within a closed system oxygen
694 is depleted from the water and metabolic wastes accumulate (Öz *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, optimum
695 ranges and tolerances vary significantly among different species (Portz *et al.*, 2006). Ammonia (NH₃
696 (ammonia gas) and NH₄⁺ (ammonium ion)) is the main nitrogenous waste product of teleosts, primarily
697 arising from catabolism of amino acids (Ip & Chew, 2010). Acute effects of high water ammonia
698 concentrations include interference with sodium transport (Ip & Chew, 2010), and disruption of
699 electrochemical gradients in the central nervous system (Wright & Wood, 2009). Exogenous
700 waterborne chemicals that can cause toxicity to fishes if they are present in the water they are shipped
701 in include chlorine (Cl₂), chloramines (if municipal water is used) (Cooke & Schreer, 2010) and trace
702 metals. Chlorine and associated chloramines can alter gill structure and function, and can have
703 synergistic effects with trace metals (Cooke & Schreer, 2010; Adams & Ham, 2011). Trace metal
704 contaminants are known to cause a broad array of physiological effects including oxidative stress (Javed
705 *et al.*, 2015; Zheng *et al.*, 2017), cell death (Matz & Krone, 2007), impaired neuronal development, (Tu
706 *et al.*, 2017) and cellular dysfunction (Rasinger *et al.*, 2017). At acute levels, changes in these water
707 quality parameters can lead to severe changes in health and subsequent mortality. However, the effects
708 of low levels of these contaminants may be harder to detect, for instance causing subtle changes in
709 behaviour. Ammonia can alter swimming behaviour (Shingles *et al.*, 2001; Tudorache *et al.*, 2008) and
710 agonistic interactions (Tudorache *et al.*, 2008) and chlorine can induce stress-like behaviours (Cooke
711 & Shreer, 2001). Low oxygen levels can limit aerobic swimming capability (Domenici *et al.*, 2012) and

712 trace metal contaminants can alter feeding through a variety of mechanisms (reviewed by Scott &
713 Sloman, 2004).

714 Water quality is, therefore, a key determinant of optimal fish health and welfare and needs to be
715 controlled during transportation (Stevens *et al.*, 2017) aiming for low ammonia levels, low contaminant
716 levels and appropriate dissolved oxygen and pH for the given species (Harmon, 2009; Zink *et al.*, 2011;
717 Stuart *et al.*, 2013). Methods by which metabolic wastes can be reduced during transport in bags include
718 starvation (Kamalam *et al.*, 2017; Waagbø *et al.*, 2017), altering water temperature (Waagbø *et al.*,
719 2017; Lili *et al.*, 2019), transporting appropriate biomass (Gomes *et al.*, 2007; Harmon, 2009) and
720 adding water conditioners (Harmon, 2009; Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2020a, 2020b, 2021; Chapter 5).
721 There are many commercially available water conditioners with formulations that specifically act as
722 ammonia removers, chlorine detoxicants, heavy metal binders, slime layer protectants to ensure skin
723 mucus integrity, anti-foaming agents and pH stabilisers (Swanson *et al.*, 1996; Harmon, 2009; Harnish
724 *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, if compromised welfare arising from poor water quality can be mitigated by
725 the use of water conditioners, they should be considered for use when formulating transportation
726 standards for live fishes. As part of the assessment of a novel water conditioner it is also important to
727 understand any potential effects on fish behaviour that may occur due to the presence of the water
728 conditioner itself.

729 The novel water conditioner tested in the present study contains three main components that remove
730 ammonia, de-toxify chlorine and chloramine, and bind trace metals. The three main components are
731 ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), sodium dithionite ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$) and sodium metabisulfite
732 ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_5$). EDTA is frequently used as an ion-complexing chelating agent in a variety of settings due
733 to its ability to readily act as a ligand with a variety of metal ions in solution (McDougall *et al.*, 2020).
734 EDTA can reduce the bioavailability of heavy metals, consequently mitigating heavy metal toxicity
735 potential for fish (Shalaby, 2007). $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$ is used in industrial applications for its reduction properties,
736 capability to react with oxygen and ability to lower the redox potential of a solution (Mayhew, 1978).
737 The dithionite ion ($\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$) reacts with iron hydroxides, and forms a more soluble substance through
738 reducing the iron oxidation state from +3 to +2 (Selwyn & Tse, 2008). $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_5$ is an inorganic sulphite
739 that is commonly used to reduce the potential for microorganism proliferation (Yoo *et al.*, 2018). The
740 novel water conditioner used is not currently available commercially, which has been tested by the
741 manufacturer in toxicity tests under laboratory conditions. While it has clear potential to improve water
742 quality during ornamental fish transport, any positive or negative effects on other aspects of fish
743 behaviour and welfare during transport are unknown. Therefore, the aim of this research was to identify
744 any behavioural effects of a novel water additive during regional transport of variatus platy
745 (*Xiphophorus variatus*).

746 2.3. Materials and methods

747 2.3.1. The novel water conditioner and study species

748 Nine pairs of transport bags (each pair comprising one control bag and one with the water conditioner;
749 $n=9$) containing 10 mixed sex variatus platy (*Xiphophorus variatus*) were transported from an
750 ornamental fish wholesaler to five retail stores within the Greater Glasgow area (Scotland, UK)
751 (distance range of wholesaler to store: 11.43 – 24.94 km). During the course of the experiment, four
752 retail stores received two pairs of bags, and one store received one pair of bags. Time spent in transport
753 varied depending upon delivery route, traffic and weather conditions (time range: 1 – 7 h). Fish were
754 transported in transparent polyethylene bags (25.4 x 45.72 cm) containing 500 ml of tank water from
755 the ornamental fish wholesaler, with the remaining space filled with pure oxygen. Bags were securely
756 sealed and then placed in another bag. After packing, the bags of fish were placed in light-tight
757 polystyrene boxes (40 x 40 x 40 cm) with a variable number of bags of fish of the same species. Before
758 being sealed, the experimental treatment bags were dosed with 125 μ l of the novel water conditioner as
759 per manufacturer instructions. To allow identification of control and fish exposed to the water
760 conditioner within the same transport run, each bag contained a different colour strain of platy which
761 was randomly allocated at the start of the experiment.

762 On arrival at the retail store, pairs of bags were floated on the surface of an empty tank on a recirculating
763 system in the main fish display and video recorded for 30 min using a Go Pro Hero 5 attached to a
764 flexible camera mount, suction-cupped to the glass at the front of the tank. After 30 min, bags were
765 gradually opened to allow some tank water to mix with the transportation water for another 30 min,
766 after which, fish were released into the tank. Tanks of fish were then video recorded again for the same
767 amount of time on days 2, 4, 8 following arrival, when fish were free swimming in tanks. To ensure
768 that there were no food-anticipatory behaviours during recordings (Lall & Tibbetts, 2009; Martins *et*
769 *al.*, 2012), videos were not recorded within an hour before or after feeding. As tanks were within the
770 main fish display within the stores, videos were recorded at random times throughout the day to account
771 for different customer footfall numbers that could potentially have an effect on fish behaviour.

772 Water quality (pH, dissolved oxygen (DO) and temperature ($^{\circ}$ C); LDO101 probe and HQ30d meter) of
773 the water within the transportation bags was measured as soon as they were opened at the retail store,
774 and a 50 ml water sample was taken from each and placed in a Falcon tube for later analysis of ammonia.
775 Water samples (50 ml) were transported on ice in a light-tight insulated box back to the laboratory
776 where they were stored at -20° C until processing at a later date. Throughout the trial, fish were fed

777 Love Fish Temperate Flakes (Pets at Home Ltd.) twice daily and any diseased or dead fish were
778 removed from the tank and recorded by retail store staff.

779 2.3.2. Un-ionised ammonia (NH₃) analysis

780 Total ammonia nitrogen levels were determined spectrophotometrically (Bower and Holm-Hansen,
781 1980), with standards and samples run in triplicate. Levels of un-ionised ammonia (NH₃) were
782 calculated using total ammonia nitrogen amounts in combination with pH and temperature (°C)
783 (California Water Boards Agency, 2011).

784 2.3.3. Behavioural analysis

785 On arrival at the store, opercular beat rate (OBR) was measured for the fish while they were still in bags
786 (Table 2.1). Three individuals were randomly selected for OBR observation in each bag. This was the
787 only parameter measured while the fish were in the bags due to low light conditions and crowding of
788 the fish. Behavioural Observation Research Interactive Software (Friard & Gamba, 2016) was then used
789 to analyse behaviours exhibited by fish in the video recordings on days 2, 4 and 8 after arrival. An
790 ethogram of stress-related behaviours was developed from existing literature and used to interpret
791 behaviours displayed by fish (Table 2.1). To avoid observer bias, behavioural analysis of the video
792 recordings was conducted blind and it was unknown which treatment the fish came from (i.e. novel
793 water conditioner vs control). Three randomly selected fish were analysed for 10 min each in each 30-
794 min video.

795 Table 2.1. Ethogram of behaviours analysed in videos from days 2, 4 and 8 following arrival at the retail stores.

Behaviour	Description	Interpretation
Opercular beat rate (beats/min)	OBR was measured by counting how many opercular movements occur within a 20 s period and calculating the OBR/min from this.	Increased ventilation rate can be an indirect indicator of stress and consequently poor welfare (Martins <i>et al.</i> , 2012).
Bite	Contact aggression: Focal fish making physical contact by biting or nipping at the fins or other fish.	Although contact aggression is a natural behaviour for some dominant fish, its result can have negative welfare consequences on attacked fish by way of stress or injury (Oldfield, 2011).
Chase	Non-contact aggression: Focal fish exhibits accelerated swimming while pursuing another fish in the tank.	Non-contact aggression is a natural behaviour for dominant fish, but these behaviours can be increased when fish are in stressful environments and be a result of poor welfare for both the pursuer and pursued (Oldfield, 2011).
Erratic movement	Focal fish making sudden and/or rapid alteration in swimming direction and speed.	Used as a welfare indicator due to positive correlation with increase in stress (Egan <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Kleinhappel <i>et al.</i> , 2019).
Time spent immobile	Focal fish is stationary either on the bottom of the tank or in the water column (fins not moving).	A measure of anxiety and stress, whereby increased time immobile is an indicator of stress and/or anxiety and consequently poor welfare (Tran & Gerlai, 2016).

796

797 2.3.4. Statistical analysis

798 Statistical analysis was conducted using R software version 3.5.1 (“Feather Spray”) (R Core Team,
799 2018). Results in plots are given as means \pm SEM, with statistical significance at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$).
800 Differences in the number of bites, chases, erratic movements, percentage of time fish spent immobile
801 and OBR were analysed using generalised linear mixed models in the package ‘*glmmTMB*’. The
802 presence/absence of the novel water conditioner, sampling day and their interaction were considered as
803 fixed effects and bag pair nested within store was included as a random variable to account for any
804 differences experienced in the different retail stores or during transportation. For OBR analysis, only
805 the fixed effect of the water conditioner was included and random effects were as before. To account
806 for over-dispersion in bite, chase and erratic movement numbers, family distributions were altered from
807 Poisson to negative binomial families, and in the case of percentage of time fish spent immobile and
808 opercular beat rate, binomial distribution was used. The model was tested for zero inflation in the
809 ‘*DHARMA*’ package, but there was no statistical indication that data were zero-inflated, therefore, a
810 zero inflation formula was not included in the model. Residuals were analysed using the residual
811 diagnostics and fitted models were visually assessed *via* Q-Q plots of theoretical quantiles and
812 standardised residuals vs model prediction plots. The significance of the main effects and their
813 interaction was investigated using the *anova.glmmTMB* function, with integrated likelihood ratio
814 testing. If significance was found, *post-hoc* analyses were used to conduct pairwise comparisons for
815 interactions and main effect comparisons using the Tukey method from the *emmeans* package (Lenth,
816 2016).

817 2.3.5. Ethical approval

818 This research was approved by the University of the West of Scotland’s Animal Welfare and Ethics
819 Review Board and the WALTHAM Centre for Pet Nutrition’s MRRB (Mars Research Review Board).

820 2.4. Results

821 There was no significant difference in OBR on arrival at retail stores between water conditioner treated
822 fish and control fish ($\chi^2 = 0.890$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.348$). Direct contact aggression (i.e. the number of bites
823 performed) was not affected by exposure to water conditioner ($\chi^2 = 1.881$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.170$) or sample day
824 ($\chi^2 = 0.177$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.915$) and no significant interaction between these two factors was found ($\chi^2 = 3.313$,
825 $df = 2$, $p = 0.191$). Indirect aggression (i.e. chasing) was also not affected by the water conditioner (χ^2
826 $= 2.392$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.122$), although chasing increased over time ($\chi^2 = 8.086$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.018$; Fig. 2.1) with
827 more chases on day 8 than day 2 ($t = 2.663$, $p = 0.028$) but with no significant interaction between the

828 conditioner and time ($\chi^2=3.154$, $df= 2$, $p=0.207$). Levels of erratic movement were not significantly
 829 affected by the novel water conditioner ($\chi^2=0.095$, $df=1$, $p=0.759$) or sample day ($\chi^2=0.596$, $df=2$,
 830 $p=0.743$) with no significant interaction between the factors ($\chi^2=0.114$, $df=2$, $p=0.945$). Exposure to the
 831 novel water conditioner increased the amount of time fish spent immobile ($\chi^2=6.151$, $df=1$, $p=0.013$)
 832 (Fig. 2.2) but there was no significant effect of sampling day ($\chi^2=5.871$, $df=2$, $p=0.053$). While there
 833 was no significant interaction between the two factors ($\chi^2=5.355$, $df=2$, $p=0.069$), post-hoc analyses
 834 found that this behavioural effect of the water conditioner was only seen on day 2 (Fig. 2.2).

835 There was no significant effect of the novel water conditioner on pH ($\chi^2=0.1709$, $df=1$, $p=0.679$),
 836 temperature ($\chi^2=0.285$, $df=1$, $p=0.594$) or ammonia ($\chi^2=0.012$, $df=1$, $p=0.913$) (Table 2.2). DO was
 837 above readable levels for the probe and the water was therefore classified as supersaturated with oxygen.

838 Table 2.2. Mean (\pm SE) water quality of transportation bag water post-transport.

Treatment	pH	Temperature (°C)	Ammonia (mg/l)
Control	6.92 \pm 0.08	19.01 \pm 0.15	<0.001
Novel water conditioner	6.83 \pm 0.06	19.03 \pm 0.17	<0.001

839 |
 840 Figure 2.1. Mean (\pm SE) number of chases per fish (30 min⁻¹) for fish that were transported either with or without
 841 the novel water conditioner, recorded on days 2, 4 and 8 after arrival at the store. Letters indicates significant post-
 842 hoc differences between sampling day within a treatment ($p<0.05$), where bars sharing a letter are not significantly
 843 different.

844

845 Figure 2.2. Mean (\pm SE) amount of time immobile ($s/30 \text{ min}^{-1}$) of fish that were transported either with or without
 846 the novel water conditioner, recorded on days 2, 4 and 8 after arrival at the store. Letters indicates significant post-
 847 hoc differences between treatments within a sample day ($p < 0.05$).

848 2.5. Discussion

849 The aim of this study was to identify any post-transport behavioural effects of a novel water conditioner
 850 on variatus platy (*Xiphophorus variatus*). Water quality was high on arrival at the retail stores and there
 851 were no significant differences in water quality between control and bags containing the novel water
 852 conditioner. As ammonia concentrations remained low in untreated bags following transport, the
 853 duration of regional transport during this study ($< 7 \text{ h}$), may not have been long enough to demonstrate
 854 the ability of the water conditioner to mitigate measurable changes in water quality. Longer
 855 transportation times (e.g. international transport) may yield different results, as greater changes in water
 856 quality would be expected. High standards of welfare and water quality have previously been
 857 documented for the wholesaler used in the present study (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2020a, 2020b) thus
 858 this novel water conditioner may also be beneficial for regulating water quality where wholesalers are
 859 utilising poorer water quality. Identifying the efficacy of this novel water conditioner over longer
 860 periods of transportation may be advantageous, although care should be taken to ensure saturation of
 861 water with oxygen as sodium metabisulfite can scavenge dissolved oxygen in water (Shojaee *et al.*,
 862 2017) with a detrimental effect on water pH, due to the increase in carbon dioxide as a result of increased
 863 respiration due to hypoxic stress. This is unlikely to be an issue within the trade as existing studies have

864 found that transportation water remains super-saturated with oxygen (at 25° C, 100% saturation) after
865 24-48 h of transportation (Teo *et al.*, 1989). In Singapore, the world's foremost ornamental fish
866 exporting country, standard practice for the transportation of ornamental fishes is to supply pure oxygen
867 to transportation bags three to four times that of the volume of water (Lim *et al.*, 2003).

868 The primary aim of the novel water conditioner is to remediate the effects of poor water quality that
869 can arise from water contamination and metabolic processes that occur during transport. Current water
870 conditioners on the market aim to target different aspect of potential stressors that fishes may encounter
871 such as poor water quality, heavy metal contamination, handling, water changes, routine husbandry
872 procedures, injury and disease. Some existing water conditioners such as Ultimate (Aqua Science),
873 Aquaplus (Hagen Nutrafin), Nov Aqua (Kordon, Prime (Seachem)) and Stress Coat® (Mars Fishcare)
874 aim to protect the mucus layer of the fish, dechlorinate the water and bind heavy metals (Harnish *et al.*,
875 2010). Stress Coat® has been developed with the aim of reducing detrimental effects of some of the
876 known stressors that ornamental fishes encounter. Studies have been conducted into the water quality
877 remediation and stress-alleviating effects of Stress Coat® post-international and post-regional
878 transportation (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2020a, 2020b). In these studies, Stress Coat® appeared to reduce
879 the occurrence of direct aggression behaviours (biting) and erratic swimming, which are known
880 behavioural indicators of stress (Kalueff *et al.*, 2013; White *et al.*, 2017).

881 While the primary aim of the novel water conditioner is to improve water quality, it is also important
882 to understand whether it has any concomitant effect on fish welfare, either positive or negative. This
883 was considered here through behavioural analysis. Behaviour can provide an insight into the welfare
884 state of an organism as a whole, in a non-invasive manner. This is especially true in ornamental fishes,
885 whereby physiological measures of welfare, such as blood cortisol or lactate, would require an invasive
886 procedure or terminal sampling (due to them generally being small in size). Nevertheless, using
887 behaviour as a welfare indicator in ornamental fishes can be difficult due to the wide range of species
888 that are traded and the different species-specific behaviours they exhibit. To circumvent this potential
889 problem, the study species used here was chosen specifically as their behaviour post-transport is already
890 well documented (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2020a, 2020b) and therefore, baseline behavioural data were
891 available for comparison. The present study used the same behavioural measures as Vanderzwalmen *et al.*
892 (2020) (i.e. erratic swimming, biting, chasing and opercular beat rate), with the addition of analysing
893 the time that fish spent immobile within the tank.

894 The number of chases performed within this study increased over time (Fig. 2.1), with a significantly
895 higher number of chases on day 2 compared to day 8 of data collection. A similar increase in chasing
896 behaviour over time was seen in Vanderzwalmen *et al.* (2020) where chasing behaviour increased in
897 retail stores over time following regional and international transport. With new fish being added
898 regularly, social interactions and hierarchies in retail stores are constantly altered and therefore, the

899 amount/severity of aggressive behaviours may vary between tanks (Desjardins *et al.*, 2012). Social
900 hierarchies in fish are established *via* physiological and behavioural reactions to both physical and social
901 environments, with behaviour playing an integral role when establishing the dominant and subordinate
902 individuals within a social group (Carbonara *et al.*, 2019). Gómez-Laplaza & Morgan (2002) identified
903 that the housing conditions and social dynamics that fish previously experience can have a significant
904 effect on behavioural responses to a novel social environment. Consequently, the social environment
905 and the social hierarchies therein that fish experience within the wholesaler may affect the time it takes
906 to establish social hierarchies upon introduction to the novel environment (retail store tanks). The
907 increase in indirect aggressive behaviours, rather than direct aggression such as biting, is likely to be
908 the product of social hierarchy establishment within their novel environment.

909 The presence of the novel water conditioner had a significant effect on the time fish spent immobile.
910 This was a new behaviour, not measured by Vanderzwalmen *et al.* (2020) and was chosen as an
911 additional measure because an increased amount of time that a fish is immobile can be indicative of a
912 stress response (Cachat *et al.*, 2010). In this study, the effect of sampling day on time that fish spent
913 immobile approached significance ($p=0.053$) although a clear overall pattern did not really emerge (Fig.
914 2.2). However, there does appear to be a potential for freezing behaviour to be included in subsequent
915 ethograms documenting platy behaviour and could be complemented by identifying the location within
916 the water column that the fish “freezes” (Aponte & Petrunich-Rutherford, 2019). Spatial distribution
917 and location within the tank could indicate how bold or “comfortable” the fish is within their
918 environment and whether they deem that there is any potential threat. It is acknowledged that observer
919 presence/absence is a bias-factor in behavioural studies (Trnski *et al.*, 2020), with fishes responding to
920 the presence of humans in the same manner in which they would react to predators (Frid & Dill, 2002).
921 This study was conducted in retail stores to obtain an accurate representation of the stressors that
922 ornamental fish experience where there is a potential for customers to influence fish behaviour. As this
923 study was conducted in a “real-world” environment for ornamental fishes within retail stores, the results
924 found are a realistic representation of what ornamental fishes experience when being housed in retail
925 stores prior to purchase.

926 The fish used within this study were in good health throughout, with no injuries or diseases observed
927 prior to or during the experiment and therefore, it was not possible to identify whether the novel water
928 conditioner has an effect on wounds or disease prevalence. Existing polymer-based water conditioners
929 have been found to reduce the incidence of handling-related injuries in multiple fish species (see review:
930 Harnish *et al.*, 2010). Although the novel water additive is not polymer-based, the antimicrobial effects
931 of sodium metabisulfite (Frank & Patel, 2007) may reduce the incidence of microbial infections arising
932 from any injuries sustained within the ornamental fish supply chain and potentially aid in healing.
933 Further research into whether the addition of this water conditioner to water pre-transport could reduce
934 the likelihood of severe injuries and mortalities arising from mechanical disturbance and handling due

935 to the chemical composition of the novel water additive could be conducted. It would also be interesting
936 to investigate whether the novel water conditioner tested has a beneficial effect on pathogenic load
937 within transportation water.

938 2.6. Conclusion

939 Overall, the addition of the novel water conditioner in the transport bags of *variatus platy* during
940 regional transport did not affect the measured behavioural parameters used within this study, with the
941 exception of the time fish spent immobile on the second day post-transport to the retailer. Water quality
942 was not different between the control bags and those treated with the water conditioner, with water
943 quality post-transport remaining high. Therefore, for regional transport where wholesalers maintain
944 high husbandry and water quality procedures it is not possible to determine whether the novel water
945 additive causes any measurable benefits in water quality. It may be advantageous to test the effects of
946 the water conditioner on water quality for longer international transport times, or in situations where
947 poor water quality is known to occur. Results from this study suggest that there are no major
948 advantageous or disadvantageous effects of the novel water conditioner on stress-related behaviours,
949 but that measurement of time spent motionless may be a more sensitive behaviour to consider for
950 subsequent ethograms used with *variatus platy*.

951 **Chapter 3: It matters who your tank-mates are: Social composition**
952 **affects behaviour post-transport.**

953 Published as: Jones, M., Alexander, M.E., Lightbody, S., Snellgrove, D., Smith, P., Bramhall, S.,
954 Henriquez, F.L., McLellan, I. and Sloman, K.A. (2023) Influence of social enrichment on transport
955 stress in fish: a behavioural approach. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*. **262**.
956 DOI:10.1016/j.applanim.2023.105920

957 3.1. Abstract

958 Ornamental fishes are one of the most commonly owned companion animals in the world, however, the
959 transportation process during acquisition can result in fishes being exposed to biotic and abiotic
960 conditions which compromise welfare. While many studies have considered methods of improving
961 welfare for food fishes through physical and social enrichment, few have considered how to improve
962 welfare of ornamental fishes post-transport. This Chapter investigated whether (i) being introduced into
963 an empty tank, a tank with resident conspecifics (variatus platys; *Xiphophorus variatus*), or a tank with
964 resident heterospecifics (common mollies; *Poecilia sphenops*) and (ii) being able to see resident fish in
965 an adjacent tank affected stress-associated behaviour post-transport. Videos of variatus platys being
966 introduced to their treatment tanks were taken immediately on release following transport, and at 1, 24,
967 72, 120 and 168 h after release. Behaviours analysed included biting, chasing, erratic movement and
968 time spent immobile which were analysed across all time points. Latency to forage was analysed
969 immediately upon release post-transport only. The social composition of the tanks that the variatus
970 platys were placed in influenced the majority of behaviours analysed, however visual cues only had a
971 significant effect on chasing behaviour at 168 h post release and on biting behaviours of resident fish
972 towards transported fish. Fish placed in tanks with resident conspecifics exhibited significantly more

973 agonistic behaviours than those introduced into empty tanks or with resident heterospecifics. Variatus
974 platys introduced into tanks with resident conspecifics had shorter foraging latencies. It is clear that
975 tank composition post-transport has an effect on behaviour of ornamental fishes and represents a way
976 in which retailers can implement welfare improvements.

977 3.2. Introduction

978 Ornamental fishes are one of the most commonly owned companion animals in the world but although
979 popular, historically ornamental fish welfare has not been a priority for farmers, exporters, importers or
980 retailers (Huntingford & Kadri, 2009). In recent years this has changed (Stevens *et al.*, 2017; King,
981 2019), with increasing legislation and attention from fish welfare advocacy groups, due to the stressors
982 fish can experience within the ornamental fish supply chain and the detrimental effect they have on
983 welfare of ornamental fishes (Huntingford *et al.*, 2006). Ornamental fishes experience a plethora of
984 stressors during transport, for example inappropriate stocking density, poor water quality and
985 mechanical disturbance (Jones *et al.*, 2021; Chapter 1), and with increasing public consciousness
986 regarding animal welfare, it would be beneficial for every stage of the ornamental fish supply chain to
987 be refined to improve fish welfare during transport including in their penultimate destination of a retail
988 store.

989 The ornamental fish supply chain exposes fishes to stressors at every stage, but the transportation stage
990 has been identified as one of the areas where stressors can culminate in poor welfare (Jones *et al.*, 2021).
991 Various studies have considered how to improve welfare during transport (reviewed by Stevens *et al.*,
992 2017; Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2019; Jones *et al.*, 2021), but research into refinement of conditions at
993 retail stores to aid recovery of fishes from the stress associated with transport is lacking. While treatment
994 of fishes post-transport can vary between retailers, in general on arrival at a retail store following long
995 periods of national and/or international transport, fishes are left in their transport bags and floated in
996 their destination tanks for a period of time to allow gradual acclimation to water temperature and water
997 quality (Donaldson *et al.*, 2008). Following this, fishes are released into the tanks which vary
998 considerably in physical (e.g. substrate, enrichment) and social (e.g. conspecifics or heterospecifics)
999 environments between retailers. The conditions that fishes experience during recovery post-transport
1000 such as changes in water quality, temperature and various social environments are likely to have a
1001 critical effect on welfare and concomitant issues. From a social perspective, it is unknown whether
1002 being placed into single or mixed species tanks aids recovery from transport stress, or whether there is
1003 an influence of visual cues of fishes from other tanks.

1004 Surrounding environments can affect an organism's behavioural and physiological state. Both
1005 enrichment and stocking density can influence fish behaviour (Näslund & Johnsson, 2014; Stevens *et al.*
1006 *et al.*, 2017) and through increased structural complexity, enrichment is a well-documented method of
1007 improving fish welfare (Näslund & Johnsson, 2014). However, the benefits of social complexity as a
1008 form of enrichment for fishes have received limited scientific attention. The presence of conspecifics
1009 in a tank can act as social enrichment, facilitating social learning and promoting adaptive social
1010 behaviours, as seen in Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*) (Strand *et al.*, 2010). Unlike many terrestrial and

1011 farmed fish species, which are generally kept in single species groups, ornamental fishes are routinely
1012 kept in mixed species compositions in home aquaria but the use of this as social enrichment and how
1013 this interplays with stocking density has not been studied. Furthermore, little scientific research has
1014 been conducted in terms of identifying optimum tank composition for ornamental fishes (Saxby *et al.*,
1015 2010; Sloman *et al.*, 2011; Desjardins *et al.*, 2012; Palagi *et al.*, 2020), and no studies to my knowledge
1016 have been conducted that look at whether species composition can be used to reduce stress following
1017 transport. Consequently, understanding whether visual or physical presence of other fishes has the
1018 potential to improve or hinder recovery from transport would contribute to refinement of procedures
1019 within the ornamental trade and potentially have a beneficial effect on the welfare of all ornamental
1020 fishes post-transport.

1021 In response to a social interaction, individuals receive a broad range of sensory information which they
1022 use to form appropriate responses (Korzan & Summers, 2007; Chen & Fernald, 2011). Fishes rely on
1023 vision as a source of sensory information, with the majority of fish species having well-developed vision
1024 and defined brain structures (Fernald & Wright, 1985; Guthrie, 1986; Sandström, 1999). The
1025 telencephalon is responsible for non-specific arousal and habituation to novel experiences in fishes (Lal
1026 *et al.*, 2018) and it has been suggested, based on neuroanatomical studies, that the fish dorsal
1027 telencephalon is a homolog of the mammalian pallial amygdala, with functional and neurochemical
1028 similarities (LeDoux, 2000; Maren, 2001; Lal *et al.*, 2018). In support of this, a glutamatergic
1029 subpopulation of neurons within the fish dorsal telencephalon (120A-Dm neurons) was found to be
1030 essential for active avoidance and fear conditioning behaviours (Lal *et al.*, 2018). This processing of
1031 sensory information highlights the importance of vision in how fishes interact with one another.

1032 Social structure, composition and interactions have the potential to influence a broad range of factors
1033 during development, for example, mate choice (Royle *et al.*, 2008), anti-predation tactics (Herbert-Read
1034 *et al.*, 2017) and group membership decisions (Jordan *et al.*, 2009). Fishes have been found to learn
1035 socially through observing others and reacting accordingly, which is referred to as ‘eavesdropping’/
1036 ‘observing’ in signal-receiver and social-learning literature (McGregor, 1993; Heyes & Galef, 1996;
1037 Brown & Laland, 2003). The term ‘social facilitation’ has also been coined, which is when the
1038 behaviour of one individual induces the same response in the observer, from which the observer learns
1039 through expressing this behaviour and experiencing the consequences in a particular context (Brown &
1040 Laland, 2003; Ward, 2012).

1041 Emotional states can be increased or decreased dependent upon the presence of companion individuals
1042 (Kujur & Parganiha, 2013). The phenomenon of emotional contagion, the process of emotional states
1043 being influenced and matched between an observer and demonstrator (Nakahashi & Ohtsuki, 2018;
1044 Lombana *et al.*, 2021), has been recently studied in mammals (Du *et al.*, 2020), birds (Morelli *et al.*,
1045 2019) and fishes (Faustino *et al.*, 2017; Silva *et al.*, 2019). It is important to note that although emotional

1046 contagion is similar to social facilitation, emotional contagion focusses on the emotional states of the
1047 organism. Specifically, in fishes, individuals not exposed to a stressor can become ‘fearful’ and exhibit
1048 a behavioural stress response when they are able to see other fish undergoing stressful situations (Silva
1049 *et al.*, 2019). Consequently, it has been proposed that fear contagion has developed as a precursor for
1050 empathy (Preston & de Waal, 2002). However, the extent to which emotional contagion occurs can be
1051 modulated by circumstantial aspects such as familiarity or kinship (Silva *et al.*, 2019). Social buffering,
1052 the ability for an affiliative individual to mitigate both the physiological and behavioural stress response
1053 of a conspecific when exposed to a stressor (Kiyokawa *et al.*, 2018), has been observed in fishes, with
1054 fishes having the ability to recover better from aversive stimuli when conspecifics are visually present
1055 (Faustino *et al.*, 2017). Originally, social buffering was only assumed to be found in mammals
1056 (Takahashi *et al.*, 2013; Kiyokawa *et al.*, 2014; Fuzzo *et al.*, 2015), however, more recent studies into
1057 social buffering in fishes highlight that social buffering is evolutionarily conserved amongst social
1058 organisms (Oliveira & Faustino, 2017) and that the social repertoire of fishes is more sensitive than
1059 originally assumed.

1060 This study builds on and expands existing studies that have looked at the effect of mixed species
1061 assemblages on ornamental fish behaviour (Saxby *et al.*, 2010; Sloman *et al.*, 2011) and aims to identify
1062 the effects of social environment on post-transport behaviour of ornamental fishes. Whether (i) being
1063 introduced into an empty tank, a tank with resident conspecifics, or a tank with resident heterospecifics
1064 and (ii) being able to see resident fish in an adjacent tank affected stress-associated behaviour post-
1065 transport was investigated.

1066 3.3. Materials and methods

1067 Ornamental fishes used in the present study were acquired from a local wholesaler. Mixed sex variatus
1068 platys (*Xiphophorus variatus*) (~3cm in total length; n=240) were used as the study species as it is one
1069 of the most popular ornamental freshwater fish species (Teletchea, 2015) and for mixed-species housing
1070 treatments another live-bearing fish species, the common molly (*Poecilia sphenops*), was used to
1071 replicate housing conditions in local retail stores. The resident fishes were initially held in stock tanks
1072 and then placed into 18 litre tanks for 1 week to acclimate prior to the addition of transported fish (40
1073 of each species). Tanks were located on a recirculation system with stock tanks and experimental tanks
1074 held at: DO₂ 94 ± 3 %; pH 6.9 ± 0.2; temperature 25 ± 1 °C (mean ± S.E.M.) and the light:dark period
1075 was 12:12 h. All tanks contained two identical artificial plants as enrichment (50 x 100 x 70 mm; taking
1076 up ~20% of the tank) which mimicked tank conditions in local retail stores; substrate was not provided
1077 in line with the conditions fish would experience in retail stores. Water quality was checked three times
1078 per week, and ammonia, nitrate and nitrite remained low throughout (<0.25 mg/l, <5 mg/l and 0 mg/l,

1079 respectively) using API[®] colourimetric water testing kits. Resident fishes were fed Mars API Tropical
 1080 flakes twice daily (08.00 ± 1 h and 16.00 ± 1 h) and the same feeding regime was conducted after the
 1081 addition of transported fish. Tanks were siphoned daily to remove solid waste and the recirculating
 1082 system water was topped-up with charcoal-filtered tap water. There were a few natural mortalities
 1083 within the resident fish species, but no tank lost more than one resident fish during the course of the
 1084 experiment.

1085 3.3.1. Experimental design

1086 The experiment investigated the behaviour of *variatus* platys immediately post-transport when added to
 1087 tanks with differing species and visual cues. Visual cues were removed by covering the sides of the
 1088 tanks with opaque plastic; if visual cues were present this plastic screening was removed. Six different
 1089 treatments were used (Table 3.1) which manipulated the two factors of interest: (i) whether transported
 1090 fish were introduced into tanks that were empty, contained resident conspecifics (*X. variatus*) or resident
 1091 heterospecifics (*Poecilia sphenops*) and (ii) whether fish were able to see a tank of mixed species
 1092 resident fish in adjacent tanks (visual cues) or not (no visual cues). The behaviours of the transported
 1093 fish and also the agonistic behaviours (Table 3.2) of the resident fishes were analysed to identify
 1094 whether any of the six treatments had an effect on transport-stress recovery or social interactions within
 1095 the tank. Due to the number of tanks available, data collection occurred over five replicate time periods
 1096 (five separate weeks) where the same resident fishes were used throughout but returned to stock tanks,
 1097 redistributed and allowed 1 week acclimation prior to each experimental period. Where transported fish
 1098 were placed into tanks with visual cues they were able to see a mixed species assemblage (five *X.*
 1099 *variatus* and five *P. sphenops*) in an adjacent tank.

1100 Table 3.1. The six treatments used in the present study (n=8 tanks per treatment). Tank stocking density was kept
 1101 the same across all treatments to reduce the potential for stocking density effects influencing any behaviours
 1102 observed.

Treatment	Visual cues	Resident fish present in tank	No. of transported fish added
1	No	None	10
2	Yes	None	10
3	No	Five <i>X. variatus</i>	5
4	Yes	Five <i>X. variatus</i>	5
5	No	Five <i>P. sphenops</i>	5
6	Yes	Five <i>P. sphenops</i>	5

1103 Once the resident fishes had acclimated to the tanks, bags containing five mixed sex *X. variatus* were
 1104 transported from the ornamental fish wholesaler to the University of the West of Scotland (7 miles; 30-
 1105 35 min depending on traffic and weather conditions). Fish were packed and transported as if they were
 1106 being shipped from the wholesaler to local stores, and were held at the wholesaler in single species
 1107 tanks. They were placed in transparent polyethylene bags (25.4 x 45.72 cm) with ~400 ml of water; the

1108 remaining space was filled with pure oxygen. Bags were securely sealed, placed in another bag, and
1109 then in a light-tight polystyrene box with heat pads and insulation/packaging to reduce any potential for
1110 mechanical disturbance and to maintain an appropriate temperature. To allow for identification, the
1111 transported *X. variatus* observed for behaviour following transport were a different colour to resident
1112 *X. variatus*.

1113 On arrival, bags were floated on the surface of their allocated tank for 30 min. Water from the tank was
1114 then gradually introduced to the bags over a 30 min period. Fish were then released into the tanks and
1115 the tanks videoed for 15 min using a Go Pro Hero 5 camera. The tanks were then videoed for 15 min
1116 again 1 h later and then 24, 72, 120 and 168 h after arrival. A technical malfunction meant that videos
1117 for one tank replicate were lost for the release and 1 h time points.

1118 3.3.2. Behavioural analysis

1119 Behavioural Observation Research Interactive Software (BORIS) (Friard & Gamba, 2016) was used to
1120 analyse behaviours exhibited by the transported and resident fishes. An ethogram of stress-related
1121 behaviours was developed using a range of existing literature (Table 3.2). Although no feed was added
1122 during the observation period, transported fishes exhibited foraging behaviours when they were first
1123 added to the tank, therefore latency to forage was included in the behavioural analysis for this time point
1124 only. For this measure, three randomly selected transported fish were followed and timed to identify
1125 how long it took for them to begin foraging.

1126 For the transported fish, all other behaviours (Table 3.2) were measured at every time point, where three
1127 randomly selected fish were followed across a 15 min period for 5 min each (i.e. three transported fish
1128 were followed per 15 min video). For the behavioural analysis of the resident fishes, the same method
1129 of randomly selecting three resident fish and following one for 5 min each and repeating this three times
1130 was conducted (i.e. three resident fish were followed per 15 min video). Only aggressive behaviours
1131 were considered for the resident fishes. When transported fish were added to empty tanks, clearly any
1132 biting or chasing behaviour recorded was a transported fish biting or chasing another transported fish.
1133 However, aggression in tanks where transported fish were added to resident fishes had the potential to
1134 be more complex. Therefore, aggressive behaviours were explored further by identifying the targets of
1135 agonistic interactions initiated by transported fish where they were added to tanks containing either
1136 resident conspecifics or heterospecifics (i.e. were they targeting other transported fish or the resident
1137 fish?). Specifically the incidence of aggression by (i) transported fish towards other transported fish,
1138 (ii) transported fish towards the resident fish species, (iii) resident fishes towards transported fish and
1139 (iv) resident fishes towards other resident fishes was determined.

1140 Videos were all recorded at the same time each day (12.00 ± 1 h) to reduce the likelihood of food-
 1141 anticipation related behaviours (Lall & Tibbetts, 2009; Martins *et al.*, 2012). Due to the nature of the
 1142 experiment, it was not possible to analyse the videos while remaining blind to treatment. Therefore, to
 1143 reduce the potential for observer bias, two independent researchers (MJ and SL) analysed all videos
 1144 using BORIS and an inter-reliability score was calculated for each behaviour. SL was blind to the study
 1145 aims to further reduce the potential for observer bias. Concordance was high for all behaviours (erratic
 1146 movement: $r(27)=0.859$, $p<0.001$; biting: $r(27)=0.930$, $p<0.001$; chasing: $r(27)=0.924$, $p<0.001$ and
 1147 time spent immobile: $r(27)=0.899$, $p<0.001$).

1148 Table 3.2. Ethogram of behaviours analysed. Focal fish in this instance refers to the fish being followed at a
 1149 particular moment in the video, for all analyses three fish were followed in total per video (15 min).

Behaviour	Description	Interpretation
Bite	Direct contact aggression: Focal fish making direct physical contact with another fish (either a transported fish or resident fish) by biting or nipping of fins or body. The total number of individual acts of biting and nipping was recorded.	Contact aggression is a natural behaviour for dominant fish, but at elevated levels can also be an indicator of stress. The act of biting can also induce stress and injury to the attacked fish (Oldfield, 2011).
Chase	Indirect non-contact aggression: Focal fish exhibits chasing behaviour through quickly pursuing another fish (either a transported fish or resident fish) within the tank. The total number of individual acts of chasing was recorded.	Non-contact aggression is a natural behaviour for dominant fish and exhibited during social hierarchy establishment (Oldfield, 2011). However, as with biting, at elevated levels it can be an indicator for stress and in itself cause stress to resident con- and/or heterospecifics (Oldfield, 2011).
Erratic movement	Focal fish exhibiting non-stereotypical swimming behaviour through rapid alterations in direction and/or speed of swimming. The total number of individual acts of erratic movement was recorded.	An indicator of aversion to their current physical or social environment. Erratic movement has been used as a welfare indicator due to a positive correlation with stress (Egan <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Kleinhappel <i>et al.</i> , 2019).
Time spent immobile	Focal fish stationary within the water column or bottom of tank with no obvious fin movement. Fish were timed to identify how long they spent immobile within each data collection time period.	The time a fish spends immobile either within the water column or on the substrate can be an indicator of stress and/or anxiety and a proxy for boldness; a shorter amount of time immobile could indicate a reduction in stress (Tran & Gerlai, 2016). However, a shorter amount of time immobile combined with an increase in erratic movements is likely to be indicative of increased stress.
Foraging latency	The time it takes for the focal fish to exhibit foraging behaviour, such as nipping at the artificial vegetation, walls or bottom of tank usually at a 45° angle. Foraging	Foraging behaviours can be influenced by social environments and latency to exhibit foraging behaviours can be an indicator of how bold a fish is (Martins <i>et al.</i> , 2012). A longer latency to feed

latency was only recorded immediately after the focal fish were introduced into the tanks. Fish were timed from initial introduction until they exhibited foraging behaviours.

time could indicate increased levels of stress if fish are either not motivated to feed due to physiological state, or perceive a risk to approaching food.

1150 3.3.3. Statistical methods

1151 Statistical analyses were conducted using R statistical analysis software version 3.6.2 ("Dark and
1152 Stormy Night") (R Core Team, 2018). Data in figures are shown as means \pm SEM, with significance at
1153 the 5% level ($p < 0.05$). Data were square-root transformed to account for over-dispersion and family
1154 distributions changed from Poisson to negative binomial distribution, apart from the aggression data
1155 relating to the incidence of biting and chasing behaviours of resident and transported fishes, where data
1156 were not transformed. The aggressive behaviours of the transported and resident fishes were analysed
1157 to identify the incidence of aggression by (i) transported fish towards other transported fish, (ii)
1158 transported fish towards the resident fish species, (iii) resident fishes towards transported fish and (iv)
1159 resident fishes towards other resident fishes. Variances in biting, chasing and erratic movement
1160 occurrence as well as time spent immobile and foraging latency were analysed using generalised linear
1161 models with template model builders using the ‘*glmmTMB*’ package. The presence/ absence of visual
1162 cues, tank composition and sampling time were considered as fixed effects, with data collection round
1163 nested within tank number included as a random variable to account for any differences in conditions
1164 during the five different data collection rounds. Interactions between fixed effects (visual cues presence/
1165 absence and tank composition) were also analysed. Each model was tested for zero-inflation and
1166 residuals visually assessed *via* Q-Q plots of theoretical quantiles and standardised residuals vs model
1167 prediction plots, both using the ‘*DHARMA*’ package. Significance of main effects and their interaction
1168 were investigated using the *anova.glmmTMB* function; if interactions and/or random effects were found
1169 to be non-significant they were removed for model simplification. If significance was identified, *post-*
1170 *hoc* analyses using the *emmeans* package were used to conduct pairwise comparisons for main effects
1171 and any potential interactions using the Tukey method (Lenth, 2016). Between- and within- group
1172 variations were also analysed for main effects and post hoc analyses conducted using the *TukeyHSD*
1173 function.

1174 3.3.4. Ethical approval

1175 This research was approved by the Animal Welfare and Ethics Review Boards for the University of the
1176 West of Scotland (Submission Number 14836) and WALTHAM Petcare Science Institute.

1177 3.4. Results

1178 3.4.1. Biting

1179 The number of bites performed by the transported fish was affected by tank composition but not by
1180 visual cue presence/ absence, with biting also increasing over time (Table 3.3; Fig. 3.1). No significant
1181 interactions between the tank composition and visual cues were found. Fish placed into empty tanks
1182 post-transport, and those placed into tanks containing heterospecifics, performed significantly fewer
1183 bites than those placed into tanks containing resident conspecifics (Fig. 1). This was particularly evident
1184 immediately after introduction, 1 h and 24 h after addition to the tanks where levels of biting were much
1185 higher in the tanks where fish were added to resident conspecific groups (Fig. 3.1). However, 1 h after
1186 introduction, fish placed in an empty tank also exhibited more biting behaviour than fish that were
1187 added to resident heterospecifics.

1188 Table 3.3. Summary of main statistical findings, with significant results ($p < 0.05$) highlighted in bold.

Behaviour	Tank Composition	Visual Cue Presence/Absence	Time	Tank Composition* Visual Cue
Total bites performed by transported fish	$\chi^2=14.0$, df=2, $p < 0.001$	$\chi^2=0.04$, df=1, $p=0.85$	$\chi^2=46.99$, df=5, $p < 0.001$	$\chi^2=0.79$, df=2, $p=0.67$
Bites among transported fish	$\chi^2=0.04$, df=1, $p=0.85$	$\chi^2=1.95$, df=1, $p=0.16$	$\chi^2=8.72$, df=5, $p=0.12$	$\chi^2=0.34$, df=1, $p=0.53$
Bites by transported fish towards resident fish	$\chi^2=4.05$, df=1, $p=0.04$	$\chi^2=0.02$, df=1, $p=0.89$	$\chi^2=10.34$, df=5, $p=0.07$	$\chi^2=0.07$, df=1, $p=0.8$
Bites among resident fish	$\chi^2=9.97$, df=1, $p=0.002$	$\chi^2=0.81$, df=1, $p=0.38$	$\chi^2=1.77$, df=5, $p=0.88$	$\chi^2=0.48$, df=1, $p=0.49$
Bites by residents to transported fish	$\chi^2=5.28$, df=1, $p=0.02$	$\chi^2=5.25$, df=1, $p=0.02$	$\chi^2=11.94$, df=5, $p=0.04$	$\chi^2=0.89$, df=1, $p=0.35$
Total chases performed by transported fish	$\chi^2=7.04$, df=2, $p=0.03$	$\chi^2=1.43$, df=1, $p=0.23$	$\chi^2=82.26$, df=5, $p < 0.001$	$\chi^2=0.61$, df=2, $p=0.77$
Chasing among transported fish	$\chi^2=0.42$, df=1, $p=0.52$	$\chi^2=0.74$, df=1, $p=0.39$	$\chi^2=68.96$, df=5, $p < 0.001$	$\chi^2=0.03$, df=1, $p=0.86$
Chases by transported fish towards resident fish	$\chi^2=0$, df=1, $p=0.99$	$\chi^2=0.53$, df=1, $p=0.47$	$\chi^2=14.19$, df=5, $p=0.01$	$\chi^2=0$, df=1, $p=0.99$
Chases among resident fish	$\chi^2=0.46$, df=1, $p=0.5$	$\chi^2=0.48$, df=1, $p=0.49$	$\chi^2=2.71$, df=5, $p=0.74$	$\chi^2=3.41$, df=1, $p=0.06$
Chases by residents to transported fish	$\chi^2=0.66$, df=1, $p=0.42$	$\chi^2=1.33$, df=1, $p=0.25$	$\chi^2=4.92$, df=5, $p=0.43$	$\chi^2=0.33$, df=1, $p=0.56$
Erratic Movements	$\chi^2=8.17$, df=2, $p=0.02$	$\chi^2=0.89$, df=1, $p=0.35$	$\chi^2=31.08$, df=5, $p < 0.001$	$\chi^2=3.25$, df=2, $p=0.2$
Foraging Latency	$\chi^2=14.62$, df=2, $p < 0.001$	$\chi^2=0.02$, df=1, $p=0.9$	n/a	$\chi^2=2.97$, df=2, $p=0.23$
Time Immobile	$\chi^2=1.64$, df=2, $p=0.44$	$\chi^2=0.94$, df=1, $p=0.33$	$\chi^2=10.5$, df=5, $p=0.06$	$\chi^2=0.60$, df=2, $p=0.74$

1189

1190 Figure 3.1. Number of bites (mean \pm SE) performed by the focal transported fish that were either introduced into empty tanks, with resident conspecifics or with resident
 1191 heterospecifics, recorded upon arrival, 1, 24, 72, 120 and 168 h after arrival. Lower case letters indicate significant post-hoc differences between treatments within the same
 1192 time point (Tukey; $p < 0.05$) and capital letters indicate significant post-hoc differences between time points within treatment (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing the same letter
 1193 are not significantly different. Absence of letters on a set of bars indicates that there are no significant differences.

1194 There was no significant difference in the number of bites performed among the transported fish
1195 regardless of tank composition ($\chi^2=0.038$, $df=1$, $p=0.845$), visual cue presence/absence ($\chi^2=1.928$,
1196 $df=1$, $p=0.165$) or sampling time (Table 3) ($\chi^2=8.545$, $df=5$, $p=0.129$). However, more bites were
1197 performed by the transported fish towards resident fish of the same species (*X. variatus*) than towards
1198 resident heterospecifics (*P. sphenops*) ($\chi^2=4.186$, $df=1$, $p=0.041$; Fig. 3.2A); sampling time and visual
1199 cue presence/absence had no significant effect on the number of bites performed by the transported fish
1200 towards the resident fish ($\chi^2=10.866$, $df=5$, $p=0.054$ and $\chi^2=0.021$, $df=1$, $p=0.885$, respectively).
1201 Resident *X. variatus* were also more aggressive towards each other than resident *P. sphenops* ($\chi^2=9.884$,
1202 $df=1$, $p=0.002$; Fig. 3.2B); sampling time and visual cue presence/absence had no significant effect on
1203 the number of bites performed within resident fish groups ($\chi^2=10.866$, $df=5$, $p=0.054$ and $\chi^2=0.021$,
1204 $df=1$, $p=0.885$, respectively).

1205 When analysing the number of bites performed by the resident fish (either resident *X. variatus* or *P.*
1206 *sphenops*) towards the transported fish added to their tank it was found that tank composition, visual
1207 cue presence/absence and sampling time all had a significant effect on the number of bites performed
1208 by the resident fish (Table 3, Fig. 3.2C). Resident *X. variatus* performed significantly more bites
1209 towards the transported fish than the resident *P. sphenops* did ($\chi^2=5.168$, $df=1$, $p=0.023$) and resident
1210 fish with the ability to see fish in adjacent tanks performed significantly fewer bites towards the
1211 transported fish than those without visual access to fish in adjacent tanks ($\chi^2=5.119$, $df=1$, $p=0.024$).
1212 Sampling time also had a significant effect, with a greater number of bites performed overall towards
1213 the transported fish 1 h after release compared to 120 h after release ($\chi^2=12.166$, $df=5$, $p=0.033$).

1214

1215 Figure 3.2. **A:** Number of bites (mean \pm SE) performed by the focal transported fish towards resident fish (conspecifics or heterospecifics). Asterisk indicates a significant post
 1216 hoc difference (Tukey; $p < 0.05$). **B:** Number of bites (mean \pm SE) performed by focal resident fish towards other resident fish (conspecifics or heterospecifics). Asterisk indicates
 1217 a significant post hoc difference (Tukey; $p < 0.05$). **C:** Number of bites (mean \pm SE) conducted by focal residents (conspecifics or heterospecifics) towards transported fish.
 1218 Capital letters at the top of each panel indicate a significant post-hoc difference between tank composition (conspecifics and heterospecifics) (Tukey; $p < 0.05$). An overall effect
 1219 of time and visual cue presence/absence was also identified (see text for further analyses). As significant effects of time and visual cues were found, data are shown for each
 1220 time point (upon arrival, 1, 24, 72, 120 and 168 h after arrival) and with visual cues present or absent

1221 3.4.2. Chasing

1222 Chasing frequency was affected by tank composition, with time also having a significant effect (Table
1223 3.3, Fig. 3.3). Visual cue presence/ absence had no effect on chasing frequency overall and there was
1224 no significant interaction between tank composition and visual cues. Transported fish placed in tanks
1225 with resident conspecifics performed significantly more chases than fish placed in empty tanks or tanks
1226 with heterospecifics; post-hoc analyses showed a significant difference 24 h after arrival (Fig. 3.3).
1227 Chasing frequency significantly increased over time, which was evident when fish were added to tanks
1228 containing resident conspecifics with significantly more chases performed at sampling times 72, 120
1229 and 168 h after arrival, than immediately after release (Fig. 3.3).

1230 Figure 3.3. Number of chases (mean \pm SE) performed by the focal transported fish that were either introduced into empty tanks, with resident conspecifics or with resident
 1231 heterospecifics, recorded upon arrival, 1, 24, 72, 120 and 168 h after arrival. Lower case letters indicate significant post-hoc differences between treatments within the same
 1232 time point (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing a lower case letter are not significantly different (Tukey; $p > 0.05$). Capital letters indicate significant post-hoc differences within
 1233 each treatment across time points (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing the same capital letter are not significantly different (Tukey; $p > 0.05$). Absence of letters on a set of bars
 1234 indicates that there are no significant differences.

1235 Within the treatments where transported fish were added to tanks containing either resident conspecifics
1236 or heterospecifics, time had a significant effect on the incidence of transported fish chasing other
1237 transported fish ($\chi^2=68.960$, $df=5$, $p<0.001$), with the number of chases increasing with time (Table
1238 3.3, Fig. 3.4). Tank composition and visual cue presence/ absence had no significant effect on the
1239 incidence of transported fish chasing other transported fish ($\chi^2=0.417$, $df=1$, $p=0.518$ and $\chi^2=0.739$,
1240 $df=1$, $p=0.390$, respectively). There was no significant difference in the number of chases performed by
1241 transported fish towards either resident conspecifics or heterospecifics ($\chi^2=0$, $df=1$, $p=0.999$) with
1242 visual cue presence/absence also having no effect ($\chi^2=0.525$, $df=1$, $p=0.469$). Sampling time was found
1243 to have an effect ($\chi^2=14.185$, $df=5$, $p=0.014$) but post-hoc analyses found no significant differences
1244 between time points.

1245 No significant difference in the number of chases performed by the resident fish species towards other
1246 resident fish was found, regardless of tank composition, visual cue presence/absence or sampling time.
1247 There was no significant difference in the number of chases performed by either of the resident fish
1248 species towards the transported fish ($\chi^2=0.659$, $df=1$, $p=0.417$) with visual cue presence/absence and
1249 sampling time also having no significant effect ($\chi^2=1.329$, $df=1$, $p=0.249$ and $\chi^2=4.923$, $df=5$, $p=0.425$,
1250 respectively).

1251 Figure 3.4. Number of chases (mean \pm SE) performed by the focal transported fish towards other transported *X.*
 1252 *variatus*. As there were no significant effects of tank composition, data for these treatments have been combined.
 1253 Lower case letters indicate a significant post hoc difference (Tukey; $p < 0.05$) between sampling points.

1254 3.4.3. Erratic movement

1255 The remaining behaviours were considered for transported fish only. Erratic movement of transported
1256 fish was affected by tank composition ($\chi^2=8.171$, $df=2$, $p=0.017$), with time also having a significant
1257 effect ($\chi^2=31.077$, $df=5$, $p<0.001$) (Table 3.3, Fig. 3.5). Visual cue presence/ absence had no significant
1258 effect on erratic movement frequency overall ($\chi^2=0.888$, $df=1$, $p=0.346$). No significant interaction
1259 between tank composition and visual cues was found ($\chi^2=3.252$, $df=2$, $p=0.197$). Fish placed into empty
1260 tanks post-transport exhibited significantly fewer erratic movements than those placed into tanks with
1261 resident conspecifics at 24 h post transport (Fig. 3.5). The number of erratic movements increased over
1262 time in both the empty tanks and those housing mixed compositions, with a significant increase
1263 appearing between 0 and 72 h post-transport. Higher levels of erratic movement in the tanks housing
1264 resident conspecifics immediately post-transport meant that no significant effects of time were seen for
1265 this treatment.

1266 Figure 3.5. Erratic movement frequency (mean \pm SE) performed by the focal transported fish that were either
 1267 introduced into empty tanks, with resident conspecifics or with resident heterospecifics, recorded upon arrival, 1,
 1268 24, 72, 120 and 168 h after arrival. Lower case letters indicate significant post-hoc differences between the
 1269 different tank composition groups within the same time point (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing a lower case
 1270 letter are not significantly different (Tukey; $p > 0.05$). Absence of letters on a set of bars indicates that there are no
 1271 significant differences. Capital letters indicate significant post-hoc differences within each tank composition
 1272 group across sampling points (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing the same capital letter are not significantly
 1273 different (Tukey; $p > 0.05$).

1274 3.4.4. Foraging latency

1275 Tank composition had a significant effect on foraging latency ($\chi^2=14.622$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$), with
1276 transported fish introduced into empty tanks exhibiting foraging behaviours significantly faster than
1277 fish introduced into tanks with resident conspecifics or heterospecifics (Table 3.3, Fig. 3.6). Visual cue
1278 presence/ absence had no significant effect on foraging latency ($\chi^2=0.017$, $df=1$, $p=0.897$). No
1279 significant interaction between tank composition and visual cues was found ($\chi^2=2.973$, $df=2$, $p=0.226$).
1280 Foraging latency was recorded immediately after introduction into the tanks only, hence there are no
1281 repeated time points.

1282 Figure 3.6. Latency to exhibit foraging behaviours (mean \pm SE) by focal transported fish immediately after
 1283 introduction into tanks that were either empty, with resident conspecifics or with resident heterospecifics.
 1284 Foraging latency was recorded upon arrival immediately after introduction into the tank. Lower case letters
 1285 indicate a significant post hoc difference (Tukey; $p < 0.05$) between treatments where bars sharing a letter are not
 1286 significantly different.

1287 3.4.5. Time immobile

1288 There was no significant effect of tank composition ($\chi^2=1.636$, $df=2$, $p=0.441$), visual cue
 1289 presence/absence ($\chi^2=0.938$, $df=1$, $p=0.333$) or time ($\chi^2=10.496$, $df=5$, $p=0.062$) on the time that
 1290 transported fish spent immobile, and no significant interaction between tank composition and visual
 1291 cues was found (Table 3) ($\chi^2=0.597$, $df=2$, $p=0.742$).

1292 3.5. Discussion

1293 The aim of this Chapter was to identify whether tank composition or the presence/absence of visual
1294 cues had an effect on stress-related behaviours (i.e. biting, chasing, erratic movements, foraging latency
1295 and time immobile) induced by short-term transportation. Although it was hypothesised that having
1296 visual or physical access to conspecifics would reduce the amount of time transported fish took to
1297 recover from transport stress, the contrary was found. While the presence of visual cues had minimal
1298 effects on fish behaviour, tank composition had a significant effect on all behaviours, with the exception
1299 of time spent immobile. Fish introduced into tanks containing resident conspecifics exhibited
1300 significantly more stress-related behaviours compared with fish placed into empty tanks or into tanks
1301 containing resident heterospecifics post-transport. In particular, increased aggression was seen which
1302 may have occurred through disruption of existing resident social hierarchies when transported fish were
1303 introduced and subsequent hierarchy re-establishment. Although biting behaviours were significantly
1304 higher in tanks containing conspecifics, the overall number of bites was quite low, so it is possible that
1305 this difference in biting did not have major effects on the levels of stress in each treatment. However,
1306 chasing behaviours within the tanks containing conspecifics were around double that of the other
1307 treatment groups, which coupled with the increased biting would likely result in elevated stress
1308 Aggression appeared to stabilise over time, with a notable reduction in aggression from resident
1309 conspecifics towards transported fish. Identifying optimum tank compositions and understanding their
1310 effects on subsequent behaviours may facilitate a faster recovery from transport, with economic benefits
1311 for the ornamental trade, as increased welfare can help reduce disease, injury and potential mortalities
1312 (Jones *et al.*, 2021). Compared with fish added to tanks containing residents, transported fish introduced
1313 into empty tanks exhibited foraging behaviours much quicker. A return to foraging is potentially an
1314 indication of lower stress levels and the lack of additional stress generated by resident fish may explain
1315 why foraging behaviours were exhibited faster (Ward *et al.*, 2008; Martins *et al.*, 2012).

1316 Across all tank compositions, both biting and chasing behaviours increased over the first 72 h post-
1317 transport. It is likely that initial low frequencies of aggressive behaviours were due to the stress
1318 associated with transport and from being introduced into a novel environment (Lucon-Xiccato *et al.*,
1319 2022). Once this behavioural inhibition ceased, time and energy were then invested into exploring the
1320 novel environment, establishing social hierarchies and the agonistic behaviours associated with their
1321 formation (Carbonara *et al.*, 2019). Social instability occurs during the initial stages of hierarchy
1322 establishment but once established, dominance ranks are likely to persist provided fish remain in a static
1323 social environment (Earley & Dugatkin, 2006). The process of combining two social groups of equal
1324 size into one larger group is known as group fusion (Couzin, 2006), which can result in social instability
1325 causing increased aggression until a new hierarchy is formed. Within ornamental wholesalers, fish are
1326 selected at random from holding tanks for bagging and transport. As a result of the standard “picking”

1327 procedure, fish within the same transport bag are unlikely to originate from the same hierarchy and the
1328 inherent stress associated with transport is likely to preclude any short-term aggression within bags. In
1329 the present study, the transportation process from wholesalers to retailers was replicated. Transportation
1330 density for the transported fish was five fish *per* bag, added to a tank containing an established hierarchy
1331 of five resident fish. Where there were no resident fish, two bags of transported fish were added to the
1332 empty tanks. Therefore all transported fish were added to a separate group of fish, necessitating the
1333 formation of new social hierarchies.

1334 The number of erratic movements significantly increased with time, and was seen most prominently
1335 between 0 – 72 h in tanks containing only transported fish or where transported fish were added to
1336 resident heterospecifics. The highest level of erratic movements was observed by transported fish placed
1337 into tanks containing conspecifics at 72 h. Increased levels of erratic movements may be an indication
1338 that an environment is unfavourable (Brandão *et al.*, 2021). In the present study, water quality levels
1339 remained within acceptable levels so the increased erratic movements may be related to unfavourable
1340 social conditions. In all tanks, a new social hierarchy needed to establish which can take time and
1341 requires energetic investment. Consequently, the increased erratic movements are likely to be related
1342 to coping with the initial stress of transport combined with hierarchy establishment.

1343 Individuals that have prior knowledge of an environment (residents) are more likely to invest time and
1344 energy into agonistic behaviours when new individuals (intruders) arrive, as residents already have
1345 knowledge of available resources (Harwood *et al.*, 2003). This is known as the prior-residency effect
1346 and stems from the pay-off asymmetry between the two parties; the intruder is unaware of what the
1347 available resources are, therefore the resident has more to lose. Although often referred to in the context
1348 of territoriality (value asymmetry hypothesis: Nijman & Heuts, 2011), prior residency can also result in
1349 a dominance advantage when forming social hierarchies (Braddock, 1949; Figler & Einhorn, 1983).
1350 This effect is seen both intraspecifically and interspecifically (Skoglund *et al.*, 2012). In juvenile
1351 salmonids (Atlantic salmon, *Salmo salar* and brown trout, *Salmo trutta*), fish of both species that
1352 emerged from gravel nests (redds) the fastest were able to acquire prior residency benefits through
1353 habitat utilisation and identification of optimum feeding resources (Skoglund *et al.*, 2012). This meant
1354 that when other individuals emerged at a later stage (regardless of species) the original fishes were
1355 significantly larger in size and were able to out-compete the newly emerged individuals (Skoglund *et*
1356 *al.*, 2012). In the present study, the high levels of agonistic behaviours (biting, chasing) seen in tanks
1357 where transported fish were placed with resident conspecifics is likely to be related to prior residency
1358 with resident conspecifics defending existing territories. Resident conspecifics conducted a high level
1359 of biting towards transported fish immediately after they were introduced into the tank, likely due to
1360 the transported fish being perceived as intruders. Although the prior residency effect has been seen
1361 between heterospecifics (Skoglund *et al.*, 2012), in the present study, increased levels of agonistic

1362 behaviours by residents towards transported fish were only seen with conspecifics and not with
1363 heterospecifics.

1364 Competition within intraspecific and interspecific groups may be associated with different resources.
1365 Intraspecific interactions are likely to relate to hierarchy establishment where position in a hierarchy
1366 will determine long-term access to available resources (Ward *et al.*, 2006). Interspecific competition
1367 may still occur for available resources where the resource requirement of the two species is the same
1368 (Ward *et al.*, 2006; Eurich *et al.*, 2018) but impacts on hierarchy formation may differ. Although less
1369 biting occurred between transported fish and resident heterospecifics compared with resident
1370 conspecifics, similar amounts of chasing behaviours occurred in both treatments. Any existing
1371 hierarchies among resident conspecifics were likely disrupted through group fusion when new
1372 conspecifics were added (Flood & Wong, 2017). However, when transported fish were added to
1373 heterospecific residents, it is possible that although there was increased competition, the existing
1374 hierarchy was not disrupted to the same extent. Avoiding the escalation of aggressive acts from chasing
1375 to physically damaging behaviours such as biting (Oldfield, 2011) appears possible where competition
1376 occurs between heterospecifics, but resident conspecifics have more to defend in terms of hierarchy
1377 formation. Differences in aggression by residents towards transported fish could also relate to species
1378 differences as aggression between residents was higher for *X. variatus* than for *P. sphenops*. *Poecilia*
1379 *sphenops* are a schooling fish so should routinely be kept in groups (Rogers *et al.*, 2013) and although
1380 they are not technically classified as a schooling fish, *X. variatus* are a social species and fare better
1381 both physically and behaviourally when kept in groups (Beaugrand *et al.*, 1984).

1382 The ability of fish to express natural behaviours may be considered indicative of good welfare (Jones
1383 *et al.*, 2021). As agonistic behaviours are a natural component of a fish's behavioural repertoire, some
1384 level of aggression should be expected and this is likely to increase when new fish are added to existing
1385 social groups. However, for the welfare of fishes in the ornamental trade, it is important that aggression
1386 is kept below levels which would compromise welfare. Following a stressor such as transport, fishes
1387 may engage in displaced aggressive behaviours as a way of coping with their own stress (Sneddon *et*
1388 *al.*, 2016) and this continued aggression once hierarchies are established can cause chronic stress
1389 (Sloman and Armstrong, 2002) with an increased likelihood of physical damage. While displays of non-
1390 contact aggression will have a lesser effect on fish health, continued chasing can still increase the
1391 possibility of disease through stress-induced immunosuppression (Guo & Dixon, 2021). Environmental
1392 enrichment was present in each tank and is often added as a form of shelter to allow fish to escape
1393 aggressive individuals (Kochhann & Val, 2016). Indeed, the presence of environmental enrichment
1394 (plastic loops) during transportation has been found to lessen the effects of transport-induced stress in
1395 *X. variatus* (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2020). However, the presence of physical enrichment may also
1396 represent a defensible resource resulting in increased rather than decreased aggression (Woodward *et*
1397 *al.*, 2019). To our knowledge, no studies have considered the effects of environmental enrichment on

1398 recovery post-transport; interactions between social and environmental enrichment is an avenue for
1399 further research.

1400 Contrary to existing studies (Oliveira *et al.*, 2017; Silva *et al.*, 2019), the presence of fish in adjacent
1401 tanks (i.e. with visual cues) had a minimal effect on behaviours measured. When resident fish were able
1402 to see fish in adjacent tanks they reduced bites towards transported fish, compared to those that did not
1403 have visual cues. Fish can infer social rank purely by observation (Grosenick *et al.*, 2007), therefore, in
1404 the treatments that had visual cues it may have provided the fish with additional information that was
1405 then used to consider where they were placed in the hierarchy of both the tank they were in but also the
1406 adjacent tank. Another potential explanation is that the resident fish with visual cues were exposed to
1407 other “novel” fish (i.e. other resident fish) in adjacent tanks (although not able to interact with them),
1408 thus resulting in a more diluted response when the transported fish were added into the tank. Why this
1409 was seen with heterospecific residents but not conspecific residents remains unclear.

1410 Currently, the main focus on reducing stress of ornamental fish post-transport is on abiotic factors such
1411 as water temperature, water quality, and lighting. We have shown that additional consideration of social
1412 factors in the housing of fishes within wholesalers and retailers could be used to refine fish welfare.
1413 Stress-associated behaviours including contact aggression were reduced when fish were placed into
1414 either empty tanks or tanks with resident heterospecifics post-transport. Ornamental fishes are often
1415 housed in mixed-species compositions where species that share similar water quality requirements and
1416 life-histories, such as the variatus platy and the common molly (both poeciliid live-bearers) are housed
1417 together. Poeciliid live-bearers represent a large proportion of freshwater tropical fishes sold in the UK
1418 (OATA, 2020); refining and standardising procedures concerning the welfare of this group will
1419 therefore have significant benefits for the trade. Although a large number of different species are sold
1420 within the ornamental trade, based on UK data, over 75% of fish sold are freshwater and within tropical
1421 freshwater fish sales, 70% of species sold fall within five main groups (OATA, 2020). Use of simple,
1422 easily quantifiable, behavioural measures such as those in the present study could effectively refine
1423 welfare post-transport for a large number of fish sold. This could be complemented by further research
1424 into the tank composition that fish choose post-transport; for example, through visual choice tests or
1425 social preference tests where transported fish can choose between empty tanks or different social
1426 compositions (Nagel *et al.*, 2018; Ward *et al.*, 2020). Further understanding of the behaviour of
1427 ornamental fishes would also contribute to the potential development of operational welfare indicators
1428 (OWIs) for the trade (Jones *et al.*, 2021) as discussed in Chapter 1.

1429 3.6. Conclusion

1430 Overall, this study highlights the importance of understanding species-specific social dynamics when
1431 attempting to alleviate the effects of stress post-transport. Introducing fish post-transport into empty
1432 tanks without other resident fishes aids behavioural recovery, evidenced by decreased foraging latency
1433 and decreased levels of aggression. Ideally within retail stores it is recommended that fishes are
1434 introduced into empty tanks post-transport at an appropriate density for the species; densities that are
1435 too high or too low can exacerbate aggression (Sloman & Armstrong, 2002). However, the feasibility
1436 of placing new arrivals into empty tanks may be limited by space, or be impractical if insufficient
1437 numbers of fishes are being transported. In such instances, the most suitable tank composition for
1438 *variatus platys* would be to place them with resident (compatible) heterospecifics, such as the common
1439 molly, rather than into a tank with resident conspecifics. Through relatively minor refinements to
1440 current procedures, the welfare of one of the most popular ornamental fishes, the *variatus platy*, can be
1441 improved and this is likely to hold true for similar species which form strong intraspecific hierarchies.
1442 Continued research into the benefits of optimum social compositions for transported ornamental fishes
1443 is necessary to improve fish welfare following transport.

1444 Chapter 4: The benefits of adding CBD to the transport water of
1445 ornamental fishes

1446 4.1. Abstract

1447 The ornamental fish supply chain has multiple transportation phases which have the potential to expose
1448 fishes to conditions that can result in physiological and behavioural stress. Some existing studies have
1449 considered methods of improving welfare through the use of water conditioners containing natural
1450 compounds known to have anxiolytic effects. Cannabidiol (CBD) has recently emerged as a compound
1451 of interest due to it having a beneficial immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, and anxiolytic effects
1452 in mammals. The ability of natural compounds to have an anxiolytic effect and reduce stress-like
1453 behaviours post-transport for fishes opens up potential avenues of research into alternative compounds
1454 that can reduce or alleviate transport-induced stress. In this Chapter, a range finding study was initially
1455 conducted to identify whether CBD exposure (low, medium, high) during transport had an effect on
1456 group behaviour post-transport. The lowest concentration which was found to affect a range of
1457 behaviours was 7.748 mg/l (medium concentration); based on these findings, this concentration was
1458 used in a follow-on study to identify whether CBD exposure during transport had an effect on individual
1459 behaviour and physiology post-transport. In the initial range-finding stage, variatus platys were
1460 transported for 30 min in bags containing one of five treatment groups (control, solvent control, low,
1461 medium or high CBD) and then videoed (15 min) immediately after introduction post-transport into a
1462 tank with further videoing performed 30 min and 2 h after release. Behaviours analysed included biting,
1463 chasing, erratic movements and time spent immobile. In the second stage, the medium CBD
1464 concentration was added to transport water, fish were transported for 30 min and then individuals placed
1465 into open field tanks immediately after transport and videoed for 15 min. Behaviours analysed in the
1466 open field tanks included distance travelled, mean speed, time spent immobile and time spent in the
1467 central zone. Water cortisol and skin mucus quantity were also analysed. CBD was found to have a
1468 significant effect on behaviour post-transport, with those fish exposed to CBD exhibiting significantly
1469 less stress-related behaviours than those in the control and solvent control groups at both the group and
1470 individual level. These findings highlight the potential for using CBD within commercial water
1471 conditioners to reduce the effects of transport stress for ornamental fishes.

1472 4.2. Introduction

1473 The hobby of keeping fish purely for aesthetic reasons was first documented in ancient China (goldfish
1474 (*Carassius auratus*)) (Komiyama *et al.*, 2009), and is still an extremely popular hobby today. The wide
1475 range of ornamental fish species that are currently available in retailers often originate from countries
1476 far from where they will be sold. The ornamental fish supply chain has multiple transportation phases
1477 which have the potential to expose fishes to conditions that can result in physiological and behavioural
1478 stress (Jones *et al.*, 2021) including mechanical disturbances, poor water qualities and temperatures,
1479 and inappropriate stocking densities (Jones *et al.*, 2021; Chapter 1). There are a variety of interventions
1480 to mitigate these stressors, for example appropriate packaging to reduce mechanical disturbance and
1481 maintain optimum water temperatures, understanding the species requirements for stocking densities
1482 and adding water conditioners to water during transport to ameliorate poor water quality. One
1483 commercially available water conditioner often used by retail stores prior to customers transporting
1484 fishes to their home aquaria is Stress Coat[®], where one of the main constituents is Aloe vera (*Aloe*
1485 *barbadensis*) (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2020a; Chapter 5). *Aloe barbadensis* has a number of
1486 neuroprotective properties, including the potential to be anxiolytic (Tabatabaei *et al.*, 2017; Rath *et al.*,
1487 2020), and more specifically aid in reducing stress like behaviours post-transport when Stress Coat[®] is
1488 added to transportation water pre-transport (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2020a). A variety of natural
1489 compounds have been tested as water additives in relation to improving welfare in the ornamental fish
1490 trade (see review by Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2019). The ability of natural compounds to have an
1491 anxiolytic effect and reduce stress-like behaviours post-transport for fishes opens up potential avenues
1492 of research into alternative compounds that can reduce or alleviate transport-induced stress.

1493 Maladaptive stress arising from transportation can compromise homeostasis and result in deleterious
1494 effects to fish health (Harmon, 2009). Physiologically, when fishes encounter stress, a stress response
1495 occurs that is controlled by three main hormones: adrenaline, noradrenaline and cortisol (Braithwaite
1496 & Ebbesson, 2014; Balasch & Tort, 2019). These three endogenous hormones are then released by the
1497 sympathetic nervous system, and the resulting ‘fight or flight’ response halts many internal processes
1498 such as suppression of the immune system (Braithwaite & Ebbesson, 2014). If fishes are exposed to
1499 chronic stress, for example during international transport, then they can become vulnerable to disease
1500 as a result of the suppressed immune system (Winton, 2001). Disease, as an indirect result of transport-
1501 induced stress, means that fishes cannot be sold until they have been quarantined and treated (which
1502 can take a number of weeks) potentially leading to a loss in profit for the wholesaler and/or retailer.
1503 Transport-induced stress can also negatively impact fish behaviour (Jones *et al.*, 2021) and result in
1504 increased aggression such as biting and chasing, which can further exacerbate the levels of stress for
1505 the fish on the receiving end of the aggression. Transport stress can also induce periods of erratic
1506 swimming, whereby fish exhibit atypical swimming patterns (velocity and direction), which is a known

1507 indicator of elevated stress levels. Therefore, by attempting to mitigate transport-induced stress, such
1508 negative effects could potentially be reduced or completely eliminated.

1509 Cannabidiol (CBD; Fig. 4.1) is one of over 100 phytocannabinoid constituents derived from the
1510 *Cannabis sativa* plant, with studies indicating that CBD can exert multiple benefits including acting as
1511 an immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, and anxiolytic agent in mammals (Murkar *et al.*, 2019;
1512 Atalay *et al.*, 2020). Unlike Δ^9 -tetrahydrocannabinol (Δ^9 -THC) (another cannabinoid compound),
1513 CBD is non-psychoactive and has no psycho-active effects (Moltke & Hindocha, 2021). The anxiolytic
1514 effects of CBD have been attributed to numerous mechanisms, including the activation or modification
1515 of multiple receptors within the central nervous system including CB₁, CB₂ and 5-HT_{1A} receptors (see
1516 review by Campos *et al.*, 2012) as well as the ability to indirectly activate cannabinoid receptors *via* the
1517 inhibition of endocannabinoid ligands (*N*-arachidonylethanolamine and 2-arachidonoylglycerol) (van
1518 der Stelt & Di Marzo, 2003; Lam *et al.*, 2006; Norris *et al.*, 2016). Consequently, the use of CBD has
1519 been accruing significant interest as a potential alternative to conventional anxiety therapies (Scotter *et*
1520 *al.*, 2010).

1521

1522 Figure 4.1. Chemical structure of cannabidiol (CBD). Created using BioRender.

1523 In mammals and fishes (e.g. zebrafish, *Danio rerio* and *C. auratus*), cannabinoid CB₁ receptors are G-
1524 protein-coupled receptors that are abundant within the mammalian central nervous system, including
1525 the amygdala, and are responsible for fear regulation and anxiety-related behaviour (nociception
1526 processing) (Elphick, 2012; Cottone *et al.*, 2014). It has been proposed that the teleost fish dorsomedial
1527 telencephalon (Dm) is functionally homologous to the amygdala in mammals (Portavella *et al.*, 2004;
1528 Broglio *et al.*, 2005; Wolkers *et al.*, 2017). Within the periventricular medial zone, diencephalon,
1529 mesencephalon and especially the central zone of the Dm, the CB₁ receptor genes are highly expressed.
1530 In the Dm, expression increases when stimulated by a noxious stimuli, highlighting the potential that
1531 the Dm cannabinoid system modulates nociception processing (Wolkers *et al.*, 2017).

1532 Numerous studies have been conducted examining potential anxiolytic effects using human and
1533 mammalian models, however, the potential for the anxiolytic effects of CBD to reduce stress in
1534 ornamental fishes during transport has yet to be studied. Consequently, this study investigated whether
1535 the presence of CBD in transport water affects group and individual behaviour of variatus platy
1536 (*Xiphophorus variatus*), following transport, as well as identifying any physiological effects through
1537 measurement of water cortisol and mucus secretion.

1538 4.3. Materials and methods

1539 4.3.1. Study species

1540 Ornamental variatus platy fish (*Xiphophorus variatus*, n=200) were acquired from a local wholesaler,
1541 quarantined for 2 weeks upon arrival at the university and prophylactically treated with Protozin (active
1542 ingredient: Malachite Green Copper Sulphate) (given immediately upon arrival and on days 2, 3 and 6
1543 after arrival as *per* manufacturer's instructions). Fish were housed in 18 litre tanks (50 x 100 x 70 mm;
1544 20 fish per tank) across two recirculating systems and held at: DO₂ 95 ± 3%; pH 6.9 ± 0.2; temperature
1545 25 ± 2 °C (mean ± S.E.M.), with a photoperiod of 12:12 h. All tanks contained identical enrichment
1546 (two artificial plants in each tank; taking up ~20% of the tank). Water quality was checked four times
1547 per week, with all measured variables (ammonia, nitrates and nitrites) staying within acceptable ranges
1548 for the study species. Fish were fed API Tropical flakes twice daily (08.00 ± 1 h and 16.00 ± 1 h) and
1549 any solid wastes were siphoned daily. No mortalities were recorded during the study.

1550 4.3.2. Stage 1: Range-finding study

1551 To determine whether CBD in transport water affects fish behaviour post-transport, and how this is
1552 affected by concentration, groups of five fish were randomly selected from the two recirculating systems
1553 and placed in transparent polyethylene bags (4.55 l) containing 1 l water consisting of a 50:50 ratio of
1554 water from both recirculating systems (n=40 bags). Five bags were then allocated to each of five
1555 experimental treatments. For three of these treatments, a CBD stock solution (7.748 g/l; i.e. 2 g CBD
1556 crystal isolate (99% CBD)(Love Hemp Ltd, UK) in 200 g HPLC-grade EtOH (254.74 ml) (Sigma
1557 Aldrich, Germany)) was added to the bags to create nominally low (3.925 mg/l; 500 µl stock + 1.5 ml
1558 EtOH), medium (7.784 mg/l; 1 ml stock + 1 ml EtOH) and high (15.748 mg/l; 2 ml stock + 0 ml EtOH)
1559 CBD treatments where each treatment received the same amount of EtOH (2 ml) (i.e. 0.785 % w/v).
1560 Two remaining treatments consisted of a solvent control (2 ml EtOH), and a control with nothing added
1561 to the transport water.

1562 Bags were securely sealed, double-bagged and placed in a light-tight polystyrene box with
1563 insulation/packaging to reduce the likelihood of mechanical disturbance, as is the procedure in
1564 wholesalers when transporting fishes. The fish were then transported around the laboratory on a trolley

1565 for 30 min to simulate short-term transport. After simulated transport, bags were opened and 50 ml
 1566 water samples were taken from each bag and frozen at -20 °C for later analysis of CBD. Each bag of
 1567 fish was then floated on top of an empty, static, bare tank for 15 min to give the fish time to acclimate
 1568 to any temperature differences. Water from the tanks were then introduced into the bags and then fish
 1569 were released into the tank (44.5 cm x 25.5 cm x 25.5 cm) which contained a 50:50 mix of water from
 1570 both recirculating systems as fish were randomly selected prior to transport from both systems. This
 1571 ensured a minimal amount of the transport water entered the novel tank. Fish in the tanks were videoed
 1572 from the side for 15 min using a Go Pro Hero 5 camera immediately upon release into the tanks, 30 min
 1573 after release and 2 h after release. To avoid observer bias, behavioural analysis of the video recordings
 1574 was conducted blind using the behavioural software BORIS, and it was unknown which treatment the
 1575 fish came from. To further reduce the potential for observer bias, a subsample of the videos (10 %) from
 1576 the range-finding study were analysed by another researcher (DF) also using BORIS to calculate an
 1577 inter-reliability score for each defined behaviour. Concordance was high for all behaviours (biting: $\rho =$
 1578 0.997, $p < 0.001$; chasing: $\rho = 1$, $p < 0.001$, erratic movements: $\rho = 0.956$, $p < 0.001$ and time spent
 1579 immobile: $\rho = 0.847$, $p < 0.001$).

1580 Table 4.1. Ethogram of behaviours observed during group behaviour analysis.

Behaviour	Description	Interpretation
Biting	Contact aggression: Focal fish making direct physical contact with another fish within the tank, by biting or nipping the fins or body.	Making direct physical contact through biting is a natural behaviour for dominant fish when asserting dominance. It can also be an indicator of stress due to the act of biting from the aggressor causing stress and potentially an injury to the attacked fish (Oldfield, 2011).
Chasing	Non-contact aggression: Focal fish exhibiting chasing behaviour through pursuing another fish at speed within the tank.	Non-contact aggression in the form of chasing is a natural behaviour for dominant fish when asserting dominance and/or when establishing a social hierarchy (Oldfield, 2011). Non-contact aggression such as chasing is more commonly observed during social hierarchy establishment and this process and behaviour can directly and indirectly result in stress to both the fish being chased and the fish that is chasing (Oldfield, 2011).
Erratic movements	Focal fish exhibit atypical behaviour contrary to normal swimming behaviour through rapid alterations in speed and/or direction of swimming.	Erratic movement has been found to be positively correlated with stress and can be an indicator of aversion to their abiotic or biotic environment (Egan <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Kleinhappel <i>et al.</i> , 2019).
Time spent immobile	Total amount of time the focal fish spent stationary (except from gills and eyes) either on	The amount of time that a fish spends immobile can be an indicator of stress and/or anxiety (Tran & Gerlai, 2016). However, potentially could be

the bottom of the tank or within the water column.	considered as time that a fish takes to process information and risk-assess their surrounding environment if other observed behaviours do not indicate that the individual is stressed (Stewart <i>et al.</i> , 2012).
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1581 4.3.3. Stage 2: The effect of CBD on individual behaviour and physiology post-transport

1582 Based on the results of the range-finding experiment, the medium CBD concentration was identified as
1583 the lowest concentration to reduce stress-related behaviours across all behavioural metrics. Therefore,
1584 further behavioural and physiological trials were carried out following transport of fish in 7.748 mg/l
1585 CBD. As before, fish were transported in bags containing five fish and were allocated to one of three
1586 experimental treatments: control, solvent control or 7.748 mg/l CBD ($n=8$ bags per experimental
1587 treatment). Due to potential, although non-significant, behavioural effects of the solvent in the range-
1588 finding study, the amount of EtOH was reduced to 1 ml in the solvent control and CBD treatment. In
1589 addition, to identify whether CBD was lost from the water through fish metabolism, a set of bags were
1590 transported with 7.748 mg/l CBD and no fish ($n=8$). To determine whether CBD adhered to the plastic
1591 bag, the same volume of tank water as used in the transport bags was placed into glass bottles ($n=8$),
1592 spiked with 7.748 mg/l CBD and left for the same period of time.

1593 As in the range-finding study, a 30 min simulated transport was used after which fish were individually
1594 placed in the centre of an open field test tank (48 x 31 x 17 cm) containing 10.416 l of water taken from
1595 the two recirculating systems (50:50) and videoed for 15 min after a 2 min acclimation period using Go
1596 Pro Hero 5 cameras from above. Again, to avoid observer bias, behavioural analysis of the video
1597 recordings was conducted blind. Inter-rater reliability indices were not applicable in this study as
1598 automated tracking software was used. Following the open field test, two fish from each bag were
1599 sampled for mucus (see below) and two fish for water cortisol (see below). The remainder of the fish
1600 were returned to their recirculating system into an empty tank designated for fish already exposed to
1601 CBD to ensure that the same fish were not used in other runs of the experiment. All fish were rehomed
1602 at the end of the experiment.

1603 Table 4.2. Ethogram of behaviours determined using the automated tracking software during individual behaviour
 1604 analysis.

Behaviour	Description	Interpretation
Distance travelled (cm)	Total distance travelled by the fish.	The further a fish travels during the trial can be an indication of a reduction in anxiety and stress (Cachat <i>et al.</i> , 2010).
Mean speed (cm/s)	The mean speed of the focal fish for the duration of the observation.	Hyperlocomotion can be an indication of increased stress and be a proxy for erratic movements during an open field behavioural assay. Hypolocomotion could potentially indicate abnormal or altered motor/neurological functioning (Cachat <i>et al.</i> , 2010).
Time spent immobile (s)	Total amount of time the focal fish spent stationary (except from gills and eyes) either on the bottom of the tank or within the water column.	The amount of time that a fish spends immobile can be an indicator of stress and/or anxiety (Tran & Gerlai, 2016). However, potentially could be considered as time that a fish takes to process information and risk-assess their surrounding environment if other observed behaviours do not indicate that the individual is stressed (Stewart <i>et al.</i> , 2012).
Time spent in central zone (s)	The total amount of time that fish spent in the central zone of the open field tank.	An increased amount of time spent within the central zone of the open field tank suggests increased boldness and/or exploratory behaviour and consequently a reduction in anxiety (Lucon-Xiccato <i>et al.</i> , 2020).

1605 4.3.4. Mucus quantity analysis

1606 After the open field test, sixteen randomly selected fish from each treatment group (48 fish in total; two
 1607 fish from each bag) were lightly anaesthetised (0.08 g/l MS-222 buffered with NaHCO₃), blotted gently
 1608 with absorbent paper to remove excess water and then swabbed for mucus from the both sides of the
 1609 epaxial musculature using a sterile sponge. Sponges were then placed into an Eppendorf tube and
 1610 weighed for an indication of any variation in the amount of mucus present. Mucus quantity was
 1611 established by subtracting the mass of the sponge and Eppendorf (weighed prior to experiment) from
 1612 the total mass. Body mass was recorded to calculate the amount of mucus per gram of fish. Fish were
 1613 then placed into a recovery tank containing clean water from both recirculating systems to recover from
 1614 the anaesthesia. Once recovered, fish were placed back into their housing tanks.

1615 4.3.5. Water cortisol analysis

1616 Following the open field test, sixteen fish were randomly selected from each treatment group (48 fish
1617 in total; two from each bag) and placed into individual glass beakers with 100 ml of clean water from
1618 the recirculating system (50:50 mix from both systems) and placed in a dark, quiet area of the laboratory
1619 for 30 min. Fish were then returned back into their housing tanks and the water was taken from
1620 the beakers and immediately frozen (-20 °C) for cortisol analysis at a later date. Frozen samples were
1621 transported on ice packs to WALTHAM Petcare Science Institute (Waltham-on-the-Wolds, UK) and
1622 stored at -20°C on arrival. Water-borne cortisol concentrations were determined by WALTHAM
1623 Petcare Science Institute (MT) *via* liquid chromatography – mass spectrometry (LC-MS) using the
1624 following method:

1625 4.3.5.1. Solid Phase Extraction (SPE)

1626 Water samples (75 ml) were loaded onto Sep-Pak® Light C18 SPE cartridges (Waters Corporation,
1627 Wilmslow, UK) at 1 ml/min following priming with methanol (5 ml) and two ultra high quality (UHQ)
1628 water washes (5 ml each). Cartridges were washed with UHQ water (5 ml) prior to either immediate
1629 elution with HPLC grade methanol (5 ml) or freezing (-20°C) and elution at a later date. Samples were
1630 evaporated to dryness using a SpeedVac SP2010 centrifugal evaporator (ThermoFisher, Loughborough,
1631 UK) and reconstituted in 70:30 UHQ water:acetonitrile (0.5 ml). Samples were taken to the next step
1632 immediately or frozen (-20°C) for future analysis. Reconstituted samples (20 µl) were diluted with
1633 cortisol-D4 internal standard solution (60 µl, 50 ng/ml), vortex mixed (10 s) and centrifuged (12000
1634 rpm, 5 min). The supernatant (65 µl) was diluted with formic acid in UHQ water (0.1%, 130 µl) and
1635 vortexed (10 s) to mix. Extracted samples were analysed the same day.

1636 4.3.5.2. Liquid Chromatography – Tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)

1637 Separation of Cortisol and Cortisol-d4 was achieved using a Kinetex 2.6u C18 100A 100 x 4.6 mm
1638 column fitted with a KrudKatcher ULTRA HPLC in-line filter (both Phenomenex, Macclesfield, UK)
1639 with gradient elution (30 to 95% 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile: 0.1% formic acid in UHQ water).
1640 Instrumentation consisted of a Triple Quadrupole (QQQ) LC-MS/MS system incorporating a 1290
1641 Infinity UPLC system and a 6460 QQQ Mass Spectrometer fitted with a Jet Stream Electro-spray source
1642 (ESI) (Agilent Technologies, Winnersh, Berkshire, UK). Data acquisition and chromatogram analysis
1643 was carried out using Masshunter Qualitative and Acquisition software version 10.0*, (Agilent
1644 Technologies, Winnersh, Berkshire, UK). Peak and spectral data were acquired using Multiple Reaction
1645 Monitoring (MRM) in Positive Ionisation mode for the transitions m/z 363.2 → m/z 120.9 and m/z
1646 367.2 → m/z 120.0 for cortisol and cortisol-D4 respectively. The linear range was found to be 0.5-125

1647 ng/ml as injected, equivalent to 6.0-1500 ng/ml in the sample. The Lower Level of Quantification was
1648 defined as the lowest linear response level of 6.0 ng/ml.

1649 4.3.6. CBD analysis *via* HPLC-UV

1650 Water samples were taken from each bag during both the range finding study and the follow up study.
1651 They were shipped along with a stock solution frozen on ice packs to Fera Science Ltd. (York, UK) and
1652 on arrival kept in the dark at 4 °C for < 24 h. Prior to analysis, samples were homogenised *via* shaking
1653 before extracting into solvent and dilution. Actual CBD concentrations were determined *via* high-
1654 performance liquid chromatography with ultra-violet absorption detection (HPLC-UV).

1655 4.3.7. Ethical approval

1656 This research was approved by the University of the West of Scotland's Animal Welfare and Ethics
1657 Review Board and the WALTHAM Centre for Pet Nutrition's MRRB (Mars Research Review Board).
1658 The work for this Chapter was carried out under UK Home Office project licence (KS).

1659 4.3.8. Statistical analyses

1660 Statistical analyses were conducted using R statistical analysis software version 4.1.2 ("Bird Hippie")
1661 (R Core Team, 2021). Results are means \pm SEM, with significance at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$). Family
1662 distributions were changed from Poisson to negative binomial distributions to account for over-
1663 dispersion. All behaviours were analysed using generalised linear models with template model builders
1664 using the '*glmmTMB*' function from the '*glmmTMB*' package. The treatments used within the studies
1665 (Range-finding experiment: control, solvent control, low CBD, medium CBD, high CBD; Individual
1666 behaviour and physiology experiment: control, solvent control, medium CBD) and sampling point (in
1667 the range-finding study) were considered as fixed effects, with replicate included as a random effect to
1668 account for any differences in conditions within the replicates. Interactions between the fixed effects
1669 (treatments and sampling points) were analysed but no significant interactions were identified and
1670 therefore, were removed from the model for simplification. Each model was assessed for zero-inflation;
1671 if zero-inflation was identified then the zero-inflation formula was included in the model. Model
1672 residuals were visually assessed *via* Q-Q plots of theoretical quantiles and standardised residuals vs
1673 model prediction plots, both using the '*simulateResiduals*' function in the '*DHARMA*' package.
1674 Significance of main effects were identified using the '*anova.glmmTMB*' function from the '*glmmTMB*'
1675 package and if any significant results were identified, *post-hoc* analyses using the '*emmeans*' function
1676 from the '*emmeans*' package, were used to conduct pairwise comparisons for main effects using the

1677 Tukey method. Between- and within- treatment group and sampling point variations were also analysed
1678 for main effects and *post-hoc* analyses were conducted using the *TukeyHSD* function.

1679 4.4. Results

1680 4.4.1. CBD analysis *via* HPLC-UV

1681 Actual CBD concentrations measured in the range-finding experiment were consistently lower than
1682 nominal concentrations, suggesting approximately 55-60% degradation of CBD when added to the
1683 transport water (Table 3). There was no significant difference in amount of CBD degradation between
1684 the low, medium and high treatments ($\chi^2=3.898$, $df=2$, $p=0.142$), however, as intended, there was a
1685 significant difference in actual concentration between treatments ($\chi^2=27.149$, $df=2$, $p<0.005$). The low
1686 and medium concentrations were significantly different to the high concentration of CBD ($p<0.005$ and
1687 $p=0.019$, respectively). The difference in concentration between the low and medium treatment tended
1688 towards significance ($p=0.058$).

1689 In the individual behaviour and physiology experiment, a similar amount of CBD degradation was seen
1690 in the bags containing CBD and fish, the CBD treated bags without fish, and also in the CBD treated
1691 glass bottles ($\chi^2=1.447$, $df=2$, $p=0.485$; Table 4). There was no significant difference in actual CBD
1692 concentration between the CBD water in bags with and without fish, and in the glass bottles ($\chi^2=0.156$,
1693 $df=2$, $p=0.924$), indicating that CBD is not being metabolised by the fish or absorbing specifically to
1694 the plastic bags. The CBD stock solution was also analysed *via* HPLC-UV to determine cannabidiol
1695 concentration (Fera Science Ltd, York; Test Report No.: FR002212_S22-009729; analysed from 21st
1696 January to 24th January 2022). The nominal CBD stock solution concentration was 7.748 g/l, with the
1697 actual concentration measured at 8.9 g/l. The actual concentration increase is likely due to a combination
1698 of factors such as the evaporation of ethanol during opening and closing the stock solution vial during
1699 experimentation, duration of storage and temperature variations during experimentation, with the stock
1700 solution being taken in and out of the fridge, consequently resulting in the stock solution becoming
1701 more concentrated over time.

1702 Table 4.3. Cannabidiol concentrations of water from transport bags taken post-transport ($n=8$) during the range-
 1703 finding experiment analysed by HPLC-UV at Fera Science Ltd, York (Test Report No.:
 1704 FR002212_Mars_151021). Samples were received on 6th October 2021 and analysed from 7th to 11th October
 1705 2021.

Treatment	Nominal CBD conc. (mg/l)	Actual CBD conc. (mg/l; mean \pm SE)	Degradation (%; mean \pm SE)
Control	0	0 \pm 0	0 \pm 0
Solvent control	0	0 \pm 0	0 \pm 0
Low CBD	3.925	1.539 \pm 0.08	60.796 \pm 2.03
Medium CBD	7.748	3.57 \pm 0.06	54.137 \pm 0.76
High CBD	15.748	7.101 \pm 0.15	54.907 \pm 0.98

1706 Table 4.4. Cannabidiol concentrations of water samples taken from transport bags post-transport ($n=8$) during
 1707 the individual behaviour and physiology experiment analysed *via* HPLC-UV at Fera Science Ltd, York (Test
 1708 Report No.: FR002212_Mars_151021). Samples were received on 6th October 2021 and analysed from 7th to
 1709 11th October 2021.

Treatment	Nominal CBD conc. (mg/l)	Actual CBD conc. (mg/l; mean \pm SE)	Degradation (%; mean \pm SE)
Control	0	0	0
Solvent control	0	0	0
CBD	7.748	3.025 \pm 0.09	60.917 \pm 1.17
CBD metabolism	7.748	3.033 \pm 0.27	60.854 \pm 3.52
CBD absorption	7.748	3.566 \pm 0.54	53.975 \pm 6.92

1710 4.4.2. Stage 1: Range-finding study

1711 4.4.2.1. Behavioural analysis

1712 Biting frequency was affected by treatment ($\chi^2=13.452$, $df=4$, $p=0.009$), with fish in the control group
 1713 exhibiting significantly more bites than those in both the medium and high CBD treatments. Biting
 1714 increased with time post-transport ($\chi^2=11.105$, $df=2$, $p=0.004$); more bites were performed overall 2 h
 1715 post-transport than when fish were released into the tanks and 30 min after release (Fig. 4.2). However,
 1716 within individual treatments, there were no post-hoc effects of time.

1717

1718 Figure 4.2. Number of bites (mean \pm SE) per fish (15 min⁻¹) for fish that were either transported in clean water
 1719 (control), with ethanol (solvent control), or with a low, medium or high CBD concentration (see Table 3 for
 1720 concentration). Lower case letters indicate significant post-hoc differences between treatments within the same
 1721 time point (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing a lower case letter are not significantly different (Tukey; $p > 0.05$).
 1722 Absence of letters on a set of bars indicates that there are no significant differences.

1723 Chasing frequency was affected by treatment ($\chi^2=13.789$, $df=4$, $p=0.008$) with significantly more chases
 1724 performed in the control groups than in the CBD treatments (low, medium, high) (Fig. 4.3). Although
 1725 a main effect of time on chasing was found ($\chi^2=6.028$, $df=2$, $p=0.049$), post-hoc analyses did not find a
 1726 significant difference between time points ($p=0.051$), potentially as no chases were performed by fish
 1727 in the high CBD treatment.

1728
 1729 Figure 4.3. Number of chases (mean \pm SE) per fish (15 min^{-1}) for fish that were either transported in clean water
 1730 (control), with ethanol (solvent control), or with a low, medium or high CBD concentration (see Table 3 for
 1731 concentration). Lower case letters indicate significant post-hoc differences between treatments within the same
 1732 time point (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing a lower case letter are not significantly different (Tukey; $p > 0.05$).
 1733 Absence of letters on a set of bars indicates that there are no significant differences.

1734 Erratic movement frequency was affected by treatment ($\chi^2=96.077$, $df=4$, $p<0.001$). Overall, fish
 1735 both the control and solvent control treatments exhibited significantly more erratic movements than fish
 1736 transported in all concentrations of CBD (low, medium, high), although post-hoc analyses revealed that
 1737 this was not necessarily the case at all time points (Fig. 4.4). Immediately after release those exposed
 1738 to all three CBD concentrations had lower levels of erratic movements compared to the control
 1739 treatment, but at 30 min after introduction to the tank only fish from the medium and high concentrations
 1740 had significantly lower levels of erratic movement compared to the control. Post-hoc analyses revealed
 1741 no significant effect of treatment 2 h after release into the tank (Fig. 4.4). Erratic movements were
 1742 affected by time post-transport ($\chi^2=8.859$, $df=2$, $p=0.012$) but post-hoc analysis revealed this was driven
 1743 by the control treatment where there were significantly more erratic movements seen immediately after
 1744 release than at the other two time points (Fig. 4.4).

1745 Figure 4.4. Number of erratic movements (mean \pm SE) per fish (15 min⁻¹) for fish that were either transported in
 1746 clean water (control), with ethanol (solvent control), or with a low, medium or high CBD concentration (see Table
 1747 3 for concentration). Lower case letters indicate significant post-hoc differences between treatments within the
 1748 same time point (Tukey; $p<0.05$), where bars sharing a lower-case letter are not significantly different (Tukey;
 1749 $p>0.05$). Capital letters indicate significant post-hoc differences within treatment between time points (Tukey;
 1750 $p<0.05$), where bars sharing the same capital letter are not significantly different (Tukey; $p>0.05$). Absence of
 1751 letters on a set of bars indicates that there are no significant differences.
 1752

1753 The amount of time that fish spent immobile was affected by treatment ($\chi^2=261.178$, $df=4$, $p<0.001$).
 1754 Overall, fish in the control, solvent and low CBD concentration groups spent significantly less time
 1755 immobile compared to fish in the medium and high CBD concentration groups at all time points. There
 1756 was a significant effect of time ($\chi^2=34.113$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$) on time spent immobile (Fig. 4.5) where
 1757 post-hoc analyses revealed that in both the medium and high CBD concentrations, fish spent more time
 1758 immobile 2 h after release than immediately after and 30 min after release.

1759

1760 Figure 4.5. Amount of time (s) fish spent immobile (mean \pm SE) per fish (15 min^{-1}) for fish that were either
 1761 transported in clean water (control), with ethanol (solvent control), or with a low, medium or high CBD
 1762 concentration (see Table 3 for concentration). Lower case letters indicate significant post-hoc differences between
 1763 treatments within the same time point (Tukey; $p<0.05$), where bars sharing a lower-case letter are not significantly
 1764 different (Tukey; $p>0.05$). Capital letters indicate significant post-hoc differences within treatment between time
 1765 points (Tukey; $p<0.05$), where bars sharing the same capital letter are not significantly different (Tukey; $p>0.05$).
 1766 Absence of letters on a set of bars indicates that there are no significant differences.

1767 4.4.3. Stage 2: The effect of CBD on individual behaviour and physiology post-transport

1768 4.4.3.1. Physiological analysis

1769 The amount of mucus present on the sampled fish was not affected by treatment ($\chi^2=1.950$, $df=2$,
1770 $p<0.377$) and the concentrations of water-borne cortisol in the water samples were below detectable
1771 levels (<6.0 ng/ml).

1772 4.4.3.2. Behavioural analysis

1773 The mean speed ($\chi^2=7.075$, $df=2$, $p=0.029$), total distance that fish travelled ($\chi^2=38.083$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$),
1774 amount of time spent immobile ($\chi^2=31.516$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$) and amount of time spent in the central
1775 zone ($\chi^2=8.651$, $df=2$, $p=0.013$) were all affected by treatment (Fig. 4.6). However, there was no
1776 significant difference between treatments in relation to maximum speed of fish ($\chi^2=3.280$, $df=2$,
1777 $p=0.194$). Post-hoc analyses revealed that fish transported in water containing CBD had a significantly
1778 lower mean speed than those in the control group but not the solvent control group (Fig. 4.6a). Fish in
1779 the control and solvent control treatments travelled significantly further and spent less time immobile
1780 than fish exposed to CBD (Fig. 4.6b,c). CBD exposed fish spent a significantly longer time in the central
1781 zone of the open field tank than fish in the solvent control group, but not the fish in the control group
1782 (Fig. 4.6d).

1783

1784 Figure 4.6. (A) Mean speed (cm/s), (B) total distance travelled (cm), (C) time spent immobile (s) and (D) time spent in central zone (s) (mean \pm SE) per fish (14 min^{-1}) within
 1785 an open field tank for fish that were either transported in clean water (control), with ethanol (solvent control), or with CBD (see Table 4 for concentration). Lower case letters
 1786 indicate significant post-hoc differences between treatments (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing a lower-case letter are not significantly different (Tukey; $p > 0.05$).

1787 4.5. Discussion

1788 The aim of this Chapter was to identify whether adding CBD to the water that fish are transported in
1789 had an effect on stress- and anxiety-related behaviours induced by short-term simulated transportation.
1790 In the range-finding study, it was identified that the presence of CBD had a significant effect on all
1791 analysed behaviours, particularly when exposed to the medium and high concentrations of CBD.
1792 Overall, fish that were exposed to the medium and high concentration of CBD exhibited a reduction in
1793 stress-related behaviours compared to the control and solvent control treatment. As a result of this initial
1794 range-finding study, it was decided to use the medium CBD concentration for further behavioural
1795 analysis. Development of a commercial product using CBD would need to include the lowest possible
1796 concentration to minimise cost, but also require a concentration that clearly reduced stress-related
1797 behaviours across a range of behavioural metrics. Overall, the presence of the medium dose of CBD in
1798 the transport water reduced anxiety-like behaviours evidenced by a reduction in aggressive behaviours
1799 (biting/chasing) and erratic movements in the range finding study which considered group-level
1800 behaviour. This was supported by the same dose resulting in a reduction in mean speed and thigmotaxis
1801 levels when fish were observed individually in Stage 2 of the study, coupled with an increase in the
1802 amount of time fish spent in the central zone of the open field assay.

1803 When group behaviours were observed in Stage 1, exposure to CBD had a dose-dependent effect on
1804 biting behaviours, but not chasing behaviours. No significant difference in the number of bites between
1805 the control, solvent control and low CBD concentration groups was observed. However, these groups
1806 did exhibit significantly more biting behaviours than fish in the medium and high CBD concentration
1807 groups. Fish exposed to CBD concentrations (low, medium and high) had a reduction in the number of
1808 chases performed compared to the control group. Furthermore, CBD also has an effect on anxiety-
1809 related behaviours (i.e. time immobile and erratic movements), whereby fish exposed to at least medium
1810 and high concentrations of CBD spent significantly more time immobile and exhibited significantly less
1811 erratic movements. While an increase in time spent immobile could be an indicator of increased stress
1812 and/or anxiety, these results when used in combination with the other findings (reduction in aggressive
1813 behaviours and reduction in erratic movements) could potentially indicate that it is not stress-related
1814 but due to the attenuation of locomotion, an effect observed in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) when exposed
1815 to low doses of CBD (Hasumi *et al.*, 2020). This could be due to the potential release of serotonin (a
1816 neurotransmitter known for its connection with anxiety when suppressed (Albert *et al.*, 2014) as a result
1817 of the cannabinoid receptors being activated alongside noradrenergic and dopaminergic regulation
1818 (Hasumi *et al.*, 2020). The results from the range-finding study highlight that CBD exposure reduces
1819 stress- and anxiety-related behaviours.

1820 Biting and chasing behaviours are routinely performed during social hierarchy establishment
1821 (Carbonara *et al.*, 2019) and are a part of a fish's natural behavioural repertoire. Once a group of fish is
1822 displaced from their known environment and placed into a novel one, the established social hierarchy
1823 can be disrupted and needs to be reformed (Gonçalves-de-Freitas *et al.*, 2019; Jones *et al.*, 2023; Chapter
1824 2). Establishing a social hierarchy, although necessary for group cohesion, can result in an increase in
1825 stress due to the increased aggressive interactions necessary to identify the more dominant and
1826 subordinate individuals within the group (Oldfield, 2011). Fishes have been found to learn socially
1827 through observing others and reacting accordingly, which is referred to as 'eavesdropping'/'observing'
1828 in the signal-receiver and social-learning literature (McGregor, 1993; Heyes & Galef, 1996; Brown &
1829 Laland, 2003). If fish that are introduced into a novel environment are "calm", they are less likely to be
1830 secreting stress-related hormones such as cortisol into the water which could in turn increase the stress
1831 of the resident fish. In Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), exposure to CBD for 5 weeks reduced their
1832 baseline levels of cortisol when encountering a stressor (Camarago-dos-Santos *et al.*, 2022). High levels
1833 of cortisol can result in immunodysfunctioning therefore, it could be suggested that CBD could be a
1834 promising immunomodulator for ornamental fishes during and post-transport where cumulative
1835 stressors could have a negative impact on immunofunctioning.

1836 CBD has been found to exert a number of anti-inflammatory effects *via* CB₁/CB₂ agonist
1837 antagonization, the result of which may inhibit immune cell migration and inflammatory responses. In
1838 zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), exposure to CBD triggered gene activation of two pro-inflammatory cytokines
1839 (*il1b* and *il17a/f2*; the latter being a homolog of *IL-17a* and *IL-7F* in humans) but down regulated other
1840 immune related genes (*ighm*, *cd4-1*, *tgfb* and *s100a10b*) (Jensen *et al.*, 2018). The primary form of
1841 immune response in fishes involves the secretion of immune cell rich mucus. Therefore, it could be
1842 speculated that through the addition of CBD in transport water, the negative knock-on effects of
1843 immunosuppression from transport stress could mitigate the potential for fishes to contract diseases and
1844 illnesses. Further studies into the effect of CBD immunomodulation with regard to fish transport need
1845 to be conducted to identify whether CBD could be used as an immuno-protectant during transport stress.
1846 *In-vitro* studies have found that CBD can degrade into the psychoactive Δ 9-THC and Δ 8-THC
1847 cannabinoids when exposed to simulated gastric fluid (Merrick *et al.*, 2016), however the stock solution
1848 concentration used in that study was ~40 mg/ml, which is 80.63% higher than the concentration used
1849 in the present study. It could be speculated that some of the CBD that the fish were exposed to in this
1850 study was consumed and consequently degraded into Δ 9-THC and Δ 8-THC. However, the relatively
1851 low levels of CBD used in this study makes the likelihood of observing an effect low.

1852 The amount of time that fish spend immobile during an open field behavioural assay can be a reflection
1853 of increased anxiety as a result of the novel environment however, in a novel stress-inducing
1854 environment, spending time immobile may also be involved in decision making, risk assessment and
1855 information processing (Kindermann *et al.*, 2009). Existing studies have observed similar behaviours

1856 to those observed in the CBD-exposed fish in this Chapter, in that exposure to CBD affects locomotory
1857 behaviour, with potential parallels drawn with the effects of sedation. In humans, orally ingested high
1858 doses of CBD (300– 600 mg) can have mentally sedating effects, therefore, potentially the hypo-
1859 locomotion in this study could be the result of CBD exposure (Shannon *et al.*, 2019), although, studies
1860 into non-mammalian animals have not been conducted to prove this to my knowledge. Sedatives are
1861 used routinely during the transport of ornamental fishes in an attempt to reduce the detrimental levels
1862 of stress that fishes experience (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2019). Sedation can have direct and indirect
1863 knock-on effects improving welfare for ornamental fish being transported, for example, by reducing the
1864 likelihood of fishes injuring themselves during mechanical disturbance (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2019).
1865 However, these chemical and natural compound-based sedatives can also have detrimental effects that
1866 are both dose- and species-dependent and therefore, potentially not suitable for facilities that export a
1867 large variety of ornamental fish species. Further research into many of these compounds is required.
1868 Non-sedative natural compounds may also be used to reduce transport-associated stress in ornamental
1869 fishes (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2020a). Stress Coat[®], a water conditioner containing *A. barbadensis*, was
1870 found to lower cortisol levels after being exposed to handling stress (netting) (Snellgrove *et al.*, 2007)
1871 and reduced aggression amongst conspecifics post-transport (Edmonds, 2016). In mammals, it has been
1872 suggested that exposure to CBD has the potential to attenuate acute autonomic stress responses (Resstel
1873 *et al.*, 2008), which may explain the lower aggression in fish exposed to the higher concentration of
1874 CBD in this Chapter. CBD exposure has been found to abnormally upregulate *bdnf* expression in *D.*
1875 *rerio* at low doses (Carty *et al.*, 2019), which has been related to cognitive impairment, which was
1876 linked with an increase in time spent immobile. This could potentially be a reason why an increase in
1877 time that CBD exposed fish spent immobile was observed in this study, however, it cannot be said for
1878 certain as *bdnf* expression was not measured.

1879 Time in the central zone of an open field behavioural assay is a routinely used indicator of boldness and
1880 exploration (Burns, 2008). Measuring exploratory behaviour can be used to elucidate the extent of a
1881 fish's stress response (Baker *et al.*, 2018), and in the case of the present study, identify the magnitude
1882 of efficiency of a potential anxiolytic. CBD exposed fish spent significantly longer in the central zone
1883 of the tank which could potentially equate to a reduced stress response consequently indicating that
1884 CBD mitigates an acute stress response upon exposure to novel environment stress. This increase in
1885 time in the central zone could also be due CBD having an effect on locomotion, as found previously in
1886 *D. rerio* (Jensen *et al.*, 2018). In the current Chapter, fish were placed in the centre of the open field test
1887 tank, which could mean that the CBD exposed fish did not travel far from this central point. This
1888 hypolocomotory effect may present another potential benefit of using CBD in transport waters of
1889 ornamental fish as it may reduce the likelihood for injury during transport as well as decrease metabolic
1890 wastes potentially compromising the water quality.

1891 Ethanol has been found to be a mild irritant in fishes, disrupting the secretion of epidermal mucus
1892 (Brugman *et al.*, 2009). After data from the range-finding study (ethanol concentration 0.02%) were
1893 analysed, it was decided to reduce the amount of ethanol as although there was a significant difference
1894 in the number of chases between the control and CBD treatments, there was no difference between the
1895 solvent control and the CBD treatments. In the individual behaviour study (ethanol concentration
1896 0.01%), there was a significant difference in the time that fish spent in the central zone between the
1897 solvent control and the CBD group but no significant difference between the control and the CBD
1898 treatment. However, it seems unlikely that this is an ethanol effect given the direction of the effect (Fig.
1899 6D) but more likely associated with biological variation in the control data. According to the European
1900 Chemical Agency, the generalised no observable effect concentration (NOEC) of ethanol in a range of
1901 freshwater fish species is 250 mg/l (2.5%) (based on a range of existing toxicity studies) (EC number:
1902 200-578-6; CAS number: 64-17-5; www.echa.europa.eu). Consequently, the ethanol concentrations
1903 used in this study are well below the official NOEC.

1904 The water samples in this study were immediately frozen (-20° C) after collection, however, degradation
1905 could have occurred during the 30 min of simulated transport through exposure to bacteria in the water,
1906 metabolism *via* fish up-take, air exposure or during the time refrigerated before processing. It is standard
1907 practice to ensure that there is ample air in transport bags during transport, however, it has been found
1908 previously that air exposure can lead to CBD degradation (Fraguas-Sánchez *et al.*, 2020). A study by
1909 Pacifici *et al.* (2017), identified that at ambient temperature, aqueous solution CBD degraded to 50%
1910 or less (72% maximum degradation) to that of the initial concentration. Further, when refrigerated at
1911 4°C (as is the case in this study upon the sample arrival at Fera Science), similar decreasing CBD
1912 profiles were observed. Although these studies do identify degradation, in the present study, degradation
1913 rate could have potentially also increased due to bacterial metabolism or enzymatic degradation. To my
1914 knowledge, studies into this have not been conducted. Therefore, the observed degradation of CBD in
1915 this study is most likely to be due to a combination of unavoidable factors and is to be expected,
1916 especially as the observed loss of CBD is uniform throughout the groups. Breakdown of CBD and the
1917 effects of its breakdown products need to be considered if this it to be taken forward for
1918 commercialisation.

1919 4.6. Conclusion

1920 This study highlights the potential for CBD to be used as an ingredient within a commercial water
1921 treatment to mitigate the effects of stress that ornamental fishes may encounter during transportation
1922 through a reduction in locomotion and potential indirect increase in immune functioning. Transporting
1923 ornamental fish in bags of water containing 7.748 mg/l CBD significantly alters behaviour post-

1924 transport, with anxiolytic effects observed both within group and individual environments. The solvent
1925 concentration used to dissolve the CBD into the water was a nominal amount based on existing studies
1926 and could be used to produce a commercial product for future use. It is worth noting, however, that
1927 before this could occur, further studies into the effects of CBD on cognitive functioning and fish
1928 physiology should be conducted, including the effects of its metabolites.

1929 Chapter 5: Investigating the effects of Stress Coat[®] or salt on
1930 behaviour of ornamental fish post-transport.

1931 5.1. Abstract

1932 Millions of ornamental fishes pass through multiple stages of transport in the global ornamental fish
1933 supply chain. Existing research has identified multiple stressors that can occur during transport and
1934 culminate in poor welfare. However, there are ways in which welfare for ornamental fishes can be
1935 improved, with water conditioners such as Stress Coat[®] and salt being trialled previously by other
1936 researchers yielding promising results. Existing studies have investigated the efficacy of the
1937 commercially available water conditioner, Stress Coat[®] in relation to improving welfare during the
1938 international transportation process. However, use of Stress Coat[®] prior to international transport can
1939 be difficult for wholesalers to ensure, as packing procedures occur out-with their control. Alternatively,
1940 these treatments may have benefits if used on arrival at the wholesaler and so the present study explored
1941 the potential benefits of exposing fish to compounds post-transport. In the current Chapter, firstly it was
1942 investigated whether being exposed to either Stress Coat[®] or salt on arrival at a wholesaler affected
1943 behaviour and recovery following a long-term (~48 h) international transport of variatus platys
1944 (*Xiphophorus variatus*). Secondly, it was considered whether the exposure to either treatment at the
1945 wholesaler immediately following international transport had lasting behavioural effects when the fish
1946 were subsequently transported nationally (~19 h) to a simulated “retailer”. Behaviour has been
1947 identified as a reliable and important non-invasive welfare indicator and therefore, used as a welfare
1948 metric in this study. At the wholesaler, videos of variatus platys were taken 1, 24 and 144 h after
1949 exposure to the treatments. At the “retailer”, videos were taken immediately upon release into tanks
1950 following national transport and then at 24 and 144 h after release. Overall, there were no notable
1951 differences in behaviour across both stages of the experiment in relation to the treatments they were
1952 exposed to, with time after either introduction of the treatment, or introduction to a novel tank having a
1953 greater behavioural effect. While these two treatments appeared to have no negative or positive effects
1954 on behaviour, they do have other potential benefits in terms of immunoprotection. Consequently, the
1955 prophylactic use of Stress Coat[®] or salt into waters that fish will be introduced into, whether it is in a
1956 wholesaler, retailer or hobbyist aquaria, when used at the correct dose for the species, could potentially
1957 benefit the welfare of ornamental fishes and is something that warrants further investigation.

1958 5.2. Introduction

1959 The transport of ornamental fishes can expose them to multiple stressors, which can have negative
1960 effects on their welfare and health including an increased susceptibility to infectious disease and
1961 mortality. Acquisition of fishes for the ornamental trade involves multiple transportation stages (Jones
1962 *et al.*, 2021; Chapter 1) with each stage variable in length. The majority of ornamental fishes are
1963 transported in plastic bags but whether they are packaged together at high density or individually is
1964 dependent upon species characteristics. One of the most popular ornamental fish, the variatus platy
1965 (*Xiphophorus variatus*), is routinely transported in high density groups, as this corresponds to lower
1966 transportation costs for the exporter, importer, wholesaler, retailer and hobbyist. Indeed, the freight cost
1967 of consignments from Asia to the USA can potentially cost more than the fish within the consignment
1968 (wholesalers, pers. comm). However, high fish density can lead to deterioration of water quality through
1969 accumulation of waste products, which can compromise fish health and cause mortality (Lim *et al.*,
1970 2003). Suppliers within the trade are only paid for live fishes, therefore it is important for them to find
1971 a balance between economic cost and transportation density in order to receive payment. The effects of
1972 water quality deterioration can either be seen immediately upon arrival in the destination country at the
1973 wholesaler (mortality) or in the coming days after arrival where the fish exhibit signs of ill health (e.g.
1974 lesions or fin damage) and/or atypical behaviours indicating there is something wrong (e.g. parasites or
1975 disease).

1976 Teleost fishes invest energy in osmoregulation, controlling electrolyte homeostasis which is influenced
1977 by their extracellular medium. Plasma osmolality varies between freshwater and marine teleost fish
1978 (230 - 280 mOsm per kg H₂O and 300 – 350 mOsm per kg H₂O, respectively) (Kirschner, 1991). Stress,
1979 including transport stress, can alter a fish's ability to osmoregulate, resulting in osmoregulatory
1980 dysfunction. Studies into transport-related osmoregulatory dysfunction (in freshwater fishes) have
1981 identified that the addition of salt in transport water can significantly reduce the degree to which
1982 osmoregulation and stress-related physiological responses are affected, resulting in an overall reduction
1983 in mortality (Tomasso *et al.*, 1980; Johnson & Metcalfe, 1982). In addition, the use of salt in the
1984 transportation water of freshwater fish species may benefit the integrity of the skin as a barrier to
1985 infection. Fishes exposed to stress have increased disease susceptibility, potentially through the
1986 disruption of the epidermal barrier (Tacchi *et al.*, 2015), as evidenced by increased skin and gill mucus
1987 excretion (Vatsos *et al.*, 2010). Just like mammals, in fishes the skin is a key barrier against pathogens
1988 and parasites and if compromised can result in disease and concomitant issues. The addition of salt can
1989 stimulate a skin mucosal response and increased ability to inhibit *Vibrio anguillarum* (causative agent
1990 of haemorrhagic septicaemia; Frans *et al.*, 2011) in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) (Tacchi *et al.*,
1991 2015). A salinity of 5 ppt in transport water has also been found to positively affect recovery rates and

1992 survivability after transport stress in adult Argentinian silverside/ pejerrey (*Odontesthes bonariensis*)
1993 (Tsuzuki *et al.*, 2001).

1994 Salt is one of many additives that are routinely used in the transport of ornamental fishes
1995 (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2019) with the aim of improving health and welfare. For example, within major
1996 ornamental retailers the commercially available conditioner, Stress Coat[®], is often added to the
1997 transportation water of fishes for their journey to the final home aquarium destination (Jones, pers.
1998 obs.). For longer transports, sedatives may be used in an attempt to reduce stress and potential for injury
1999 (Harmon, 2009; Cupp *et al.*, 2017; Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2019), with the active ingredient often
2000 essential oil-based such as eugenol (active ingredient in clove oil) or *Aloe vera*. However, the efficacy
2001 of these conditioners, additives and sedatives can be species- and/or size-dependent. The mechanism of
2002 action for Stress Coat[®] is facilitated through two main ingredients, polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP-I) and
2003 *Aloe vera*. PVP-I is a widely used disinfectant in aquaculture, with the compound proven to aid in the
2004 acceleration of wound healing and disinfection when combined with iodine in koi carp (*Cyprinus*
2005 *carpio*) (Zhang *et al.*, 2023) as well as preventing pathogen transmission in a food-fish aquaculture
2006 setting (Scarfe *et al.*, 2006). *Aloe vera* is a natural compound that, in fishes, can help prevent electrolyte
2007 loss, guard compromised tissues from infection (Shivappa *et al.*, 2017) and improve physical/humoral
2008 protection (Zanuzzo *et al.*, 2015). Stress Coat[®] also contains *Nitrosomonas europaea* and *Nitrobacter*
2009 *winogradskyi* which as oxidising chemolithotrophic bacteria, can remove nitrates from the water (Chain
2010 *et al.*, 2003; Mellbye *et al.*, 2015).

2011 There is ample scientific evidence supporting the beneficial use of salt and the active compounds present
2012 within Stress Coat[®] (PVP-I and *Aloe vera*) when it comes to transporting fishes, specifically food fishes
2013 in aquaculture. Due to the majority of ornamental fishes originating from a variety of countries, it is not
2014 always possible to ensure that the correct dosages are used. Therefore, understanding whether these
2015 treatments have the additional potential to reduce stress-like behaviours post-transport and improve
2016 recovery from transport may aid welfare refinement within the ornamental trade. Two studies are
2017 presented here, the first study aimed to identify whether adding Stress Coat[®] or salt (NaCl) to wholesaler
2018 recirculating systems affected behaviour and recovery of ornamental fish post international transport,
2019 and the second then followed the same fish through onward national transport a week later, to identify
2020 any lasting benefits of these treatments.

2021 5.3. Materials and methods

2022 5.3.1. Experiment 1: Salt and Stress Coat[®] treatment post-international transport

2023 Ornamental variatus platy (*Xiphophorus variatus*) (10,800) were transported by air from Vietnam (~ 48
2024 h) to a UK-based ornamental fish importer and wholesaler at a stocking density of 100 fish per bag (25

2025 fish/ l). Three separate consignments of fish were used, with one consignment arriving in the UK each
 2026 week for a three-week period (Fig. 5.1). Each consignment consisted of 3600 fish. On arrival, fish
 2027 underwent an ‘in-house’ acclimation protocol, whereby boxes containing eight bags of fish were
 2028 unpacked under red light, and then floated on the surface of destination tanks (123 x 33 x 33 cm; ~150
 2029 l) within one of three 650 l recirculating systems (three tanks per system; 400 fish per tank; 8 fish/l) for
 2030 30 min of temperature acclimation. Bags of fish were then allowed to acclimate to the water quality by
 2031 water gradually being added to the bags over the following 30 min period. Fish were then released into
 2032 the tanks and maintained under red light overnight to allow for further acclimation and undisturbed
 2033 recovery. Therefore, each week, the consignment of 3600 fish was divided between three recirculating
 2034 systems, with three different systems used each week for the three-week period.

2035 The next morning the fish were exposed to either NaCl (1.95 kg; 3 g/l) in one recirculating system or
 2036 Stress Coat[®] (260 µl/l) in another with one recirculating system not dosed (Table 5.1). To avoid the
 2037 potential for NaCl particulates to cause irritation to gill structures if added in one dose, in the NaCl
 2038 treatment, three equal doses of NaCl diluted in system water were gradually added. After final dosage,
 2039 the system dosed with NaCl had a salinity of 3.3 ppt (KoiMedic; accuracy ± 0.3 ppt). This dropped
 2040 slightly during the experiment to an average of 3.08 ± 0.22 ppt. Standard practice at the wholesaler is
 2041 to prophylactically treat all fishes with Formalin Malachite Green (FMG) (2 days after arrival) and
 2042 Acriflavin (5 days after arrival), both at a dose of 20 ml/650 l system. Due to the mechanism of FMG
 2043 action, systems containing NaCl were only prophylactically treated with Acriflavin, whereas the control
 2044 and Stress Coat[®] systems were treated with both FMG and Acriflavin as per wholesaler protocol.

2045 Table 5.1. Time over which the treatments were added to the separate recirculating systems.

Time (min)	Treatment		
	Control	Stress Coat [®] (ml)	NaCl (g); resulting salinity (ppt)
0	-	-	650; 1.2
45	-	-	650; 2.1
90	-	169	650; 3.3

2046 All recirculating systems were maintained at: pH 8.0 ± 0.0; temperature 22 ± 1 °C (mean ± SEM), on a
 2047 12:12 h light:dark photoperiod. Water quality was checked five times per week using API liquid testing
 2048 kits, with all measured variables (ammonia and nitrites) remaining within acceptable ranges for the
 2049 species (0 mg/l and <0.03 mg/l, respectively). Neither substrate nor environmental enrichment were
 2050 provided, in line with the wholesaler’s normal procedures, which facilitates easier cleaning of tanks and
 2051 fish observation. Fish were fed API Goldfish and Tropical mix flakes three times daily (10:00, 13:00

2052 and 16:00). Tanks were siphoned three times per week to remove solid waste, with the tanks
2053 automatically topped up with filtered water to maintain a constant volume within the tanks.

2054 Fish were videoed for 16 min, 1 h after treatments had been added to the recirculating systems using
2055 Exprotrek 4K action cameras stationed on the outside of the tank on tripods, and then again 24 h and
2056 144 h after exposure. The tank area was cordoned off to minimise any disturbances from people walking
2057 past the tank. Videos were recorded at the same time each day for consistency. Mortalities were
2058 recorded daily by the wholesaler.

2059 5.3.2. Experiment 2: Subsequent national transport of fish from Experiment 1 from
2060 wholesaler to simulated retailer

2061 *Variatus platy* (720; $n = 240$ per treatment) from Experiment 1 (that had been maintained at the
2062 wholesalers for 1 week) were randomly selected from their respective tanks and placed in bags with
2063 fish from the same treatment at a stocking density of 20 fish per bag (7.5 fish/l) (Fig. 5.1). This was
2064 done the evening before they were due to be transported, as per the standard protocol of the wholesaler.
2065 Fish were placed into polyethylene bags that contained water from each recirculating system (~40% of
2066 bag volume) and therefore any remaining treatment (salt or Stress Coat[®]) from Experiment 1. The air
2067 space at the top of the bag was filled with oxygen (~60% of bag volume). Bags were then sealed, double-
2068 bagged and placed into insulated polystyrene boxes in preparation for transport the following day (four
2069 bags/box). Fish were then transported by road to Waltham Petcare Science Institute (~120 miles) which
2070 was included as an additional destination on the usual wholesaler delivery route. The average time that
2071 fish spent in the bags was ~19 h. Due to the space required, it was not possible to use retailer premises
2072 for this experiment, however, receiving systems at the Waltham Petcare Science Institute replicated
2073 retailer conditions as far as possible (i.e. no environmental enrichment or substrate, 12:12 h light:dark,
2074 temperature 22 °C, fed twice daily API Goldfish and Tropical mix).

2075 On arrival, water quality of the bags was analysed for pH and ammonia, using API liquid test kits. Fish
2076 then underwent a known retailer acclimation protocol, where bags were floated on the receiving tanks
2077 for 30 min, following which system water was gradually introduced into the bags over a 30 min period,
2078 ensuring that no water from the transportation bags entered the new system. When the fish were
2079 released, they were netted from the bag and placed into the tanks to avoid contamination with any
2080 residual treatments. Transported fish were placed into six identical static tanks (61 x 30.5 x 30.5 cm;
2081 0.714 fish/l) divided in half to make twelve tanks (30.5 x 30.5 x 30.5 cm; 28 l), so there were four tanks
2082 *per* treatment. Fish from the same treatment were always placed into the same tank either side of the
2083 divide to avoid the potential for any treatment residue coming into contact with fish from another
2084 treatment group. Due to some fish showing signs of fin rot, all fish were treated with eSHa EXIT white
2085 spot treatment (active ingredients: ethacridine lactate 6.3 mg, malachite green oxalate 0.13 mg and

2086 methylene blue 3.98 mg) and eSHa 2000 (a fungus, fin rot and bacteria treatment; active ingredients:
2087 ethacridine lactate 6.3 mg, copper sulphate 8.0 mg and proflavine hemisulphate 1 mg) 24, 48 and 72 h
2088 after arrival. The standard practice in retail stores is, once disease is identified, to quarantine and treat
2089 based on the symptoms being observed. Treatments that retail stores vary considerably but the
2090 treatments mentioned above are the standard treatments used by WALTHAM Petcare Science Institute.
2091 Tanks were siphoned daily in line with standard procedure in retail stores.

2092 Fish were videoed for 16 min upon release (0 h), and at 24 h and 144 h after release using GoPro Hero
2093 9 action cameras stationed outside of the tanks on tripods. Videos were recorded at the same time each
2094 day for consistency. Any mortalities were recorded daily.

2095

2096 Figure 5.1. Schematic of the procedures for the ornamental fish used within the study on arrival at the wholesaler. This process was conducted three times, where fish were
 2097 placed into three different recirculating systems in the wholesaler, treated with Stress Coat®, salt or nothing (control), maintained for a week then transported to the simulated
 2098 "retailer". Schematic made using BioRender.

2099 5.3.3. Behavioural analysis

2100 Behavioural Observation Research Interactive Software (BORIS) (Friard and Gamba, 2016) was used
 2101 to analyse behaviours exhibited by the fish in both Experiments 1 and 2. An ethogram of stress-related
 2102 behaviours was developed using a range of literature, combined with personal observations of variatus
 2103 platy behaviour (Table 5.2). Due to high fish densities, particularly at the wholesaler, rather than
 2104 tracking individual focal fish for set periods of time, every occurrence of a target behaviour within the
 2105 tank was noted in BORIS each time it was observed. For continuity, the same method of recording all
 2106 target behaviours exhibited per tank within a set period was used in both experiments. The first minute
 2107 of each video footage was discounted to allow fish to settle after the disturbance of the researcher being
 2108 present in front of the tank to start the camera. Therefore, all behaviours are recorded as number of
 2109 times the behaviour was noted per tank in a 15 min period.

2110 Videos were recorded at the same time each day (11.00 ± 1 h) to reduce the potential for food-
 2111 anticipation behaviours (Martins *et al.*, 2012). Due to the nature of the experiment, it was impossible
 2112 for MJ to analyse the behaviours while completely blind to the treatments. Therefore, to reduce the
 2113 potential for observer bias, another observer (AM) analysed 10% of the videos from both stages of the
 2114 experiment using BORIS and an inter-rater reliability score (IRR) was calculated for each behaviour.
 2115 AM was blind to both the treatments and study aims and experimental design. Concordance was high
 2116 for all of the behaviours observed (Table 5.2).

2117 Table 5.2. Ethogram of behaviours analysed.

Behaviour	IRR (Pearson correlation coefficient)	Description	Interpretation
Biting	$\rho=0.896, p<0.001$	Direct contact aggression: Focal fish making direct physical contact using their mouth either nipping or biting the fins or body of another fish. The total number of individual acts of biting behaviours was recorded in both experiments 1 and 2.	A natural behaviour in dominant individuals that can also be an indicator of stress when observed at higher levels. Excessive amounts of direct contact aggression can lead to injury of the individual being attacked by dominant fish (Oldfield, 2011).
Chasing	$\rho=0.647, p=0.022$	Indirect non-contact aggression: Focal fish exhibits chasing behaviours by directed accelerated swimming towards another fish within the tank. The total number of individual acts of chasing behaviours was recorded in both experiments 1 and 2.	A natural behaviour in dominant individuals and exhibited during the establishment of social hierarchies. As with biting, higher levels of non-contact aggression can be an indicator of stress and also result in increased stress of the individual being chased (Oldfield, 2011).

Erratic movements	$\rho=0.935; p<0.001$	Focal fish exhibiting atypical swimming behaviours through quick changes in direction and/or speed of swimming. The total number of erratic movements was recorded in both experiments 1 and 2.	Atypical swimming patterns can be used as an indicator of aversion and used as a welfare indicator due to higher levels being positively correlated with stress (Egan <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Kleinhappel <i>et al.</i> , 2019).
Freezing bouts	$\rho=0.955, p<0.001$	Focal fish immobile either within the water column or on the bottom of the tank with no obvious movement of fins. The number of individual freezing bouts by all individuals were recorded. The total number of freezing bouts was recorded in both experiments 1 and 2.	The number of freezing bouts, either within the water column or on the substrate, can be an indicator of stress (Tran & Gerlai, 2016). However, low levels of freezing in combination with high levels of erratic movement is also likely to be indicative of stress (Jones <i>et al.</i> , 2022).
Fin Flaring	$\rho=0.757, p=0.004$	A pair of focal fish exhibiting fin flaring behaviour; a stereotypical dominance display where two individuals extend fins and encircle each other, usually followed by a display of direct physical aggression. The total number of fin flares was recorded in both experiments 1 and 2; each fin flaring bout involved two individuals but only the display of the behaviour was recorded, not the number of individuals performing the behaviour.	A previously unused behavioural metric when it comes to analysing stress in <i>variatu platys</i> . Fin flaring in other species is a natural behaviour exhibited during dominance displays. Higher levels of fin flaring could be correlated with lower levels of stress due to the energy investment it takes to perform these behaviours as stress and associated recovery can promote behavioural inhibition.

2118 5.3.4. Ethical approval

2119 This research was approved by the University of the West of Scotland’s Animal Welfare and Ethics
2120 Review Board and the WALTHAM Centre for Pet Nutrition’s MRRB (Mars Research Review Board).

2121 5.3.5. Statistical analyses

2122 Statistical analyses were performed using R statistical analysis software version 4.2.3 “Shortstop
2123 Beagle” (R Core Team, 2018). Data in figures are displayed as means \pm SEM, with significance at the
2124 5% level ($p<0.05$). Some of the data were found to be overdispersed (using the *check_overdispersion*
2125 function from the ‘glmmTMB’ package), so distributions were changed from Poisson to negative

2126 binomial. The response variables of behaviours and mortalities were analysed using generalised linear
2127 mixed effect models with template model builders using the *glmmTMB* function from the ‘glmmTMB’
2128 package. The treatment groups used within both experiments (control, salt, Stress Coat[®]) and sampling
2129 points were considered fixed effects, with data collection run included as a random effect to account for
2130 any differences in the conditions the fish experienced either during time at the wholesaler, during
2131 transport to the “retail store” or at the “retail store”. However, no significant effect of collection run
2132 was found, so it was removed from the model for simplification. Interactions between the fixed effects
2133 were also analysed. Each model was tested for zero-inflation using the *check_zeroinflation* function in
2134 the ‘glmmTMB’ package; no zero inflation was identified. Model residuals were visually assessed *via*
2135 Q-Q plots of theoretical quantiles and standardised residuals vs model prediction plots, using the
2136 *simulateResiduals* function in the DHARMA package. Significance of main effects were identified using
2137 the ‘anova.glmmTMB’ function from the ‘glmmTMB’ package and where significant results were
2138 identified, post-hoc analyses were carried out using the *emmeans* function from the ‘emmeans’ package,
2139 to conduct pairwise comparisons for main effects using the Tukey method. Between- and within-
2140 treatment group and sampling point variations were also analysed for main effects and post-hoc analyses
2141 were conducted using the TukeyHSD function. Inter-rater reliability scores were calculated using the
2142 *cor.test* function to identify the Pearson’s correlation coefficient and associated *p*-values. Data were
2143 visualised using *ggplot* function in the *ggplot2* package.

2144 5.4. Results

2145 5.4.1. Experiment 1: Salt and Stress Coat[®] treatment post-international transport

2146 There were no significant differences in mortality between treatments ($\chi^2=0.227$, $df=2$, $p=0.893$). The
2147 number of bites and chases was not significantly affected by treatment (bites: $\chi^2=0.322$, $df=2$, $p=0.851$;
2148 chases: $\chi^2=2.446$, $df=2$, $p=0.294$) or time (bites: $\chi^2=1.862$, $df=2$, $p=0.394$; chases: $\chi^2=1.626$, $df=2$,
2149 $p=0.444$) and no significant interaction between treatment and time was found for either behaviour
2150 (bites: $\chi^2=8.565$, $df=4$, $p=0.073$; chases: $\chi^2=8.248$, $df=4$, $p=0.083$; Table 5.3).

2151 Similarly, the number of erratic movements performed was not affected by treatment ($\chi^2=3.765$, $df=2$,
2152 $p=0.152$) or time ($\chi^2=5.279$, $df=2$, $p=0.071$) although there was a significant interaction between these
2153 factors ($\chi^2=21.088$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$; Fig. 5.2) so the data were further explored. Fish exposed to Stress
2154 Coat[®] exhibited significantly more erratic behaviours immediately after exposure compared with the
2155 later time points within the same treatment (post hoc analysis: 24 h, $p=0.024$; 144 h, $p=0.033$; Fig. 5.2).

2156 Table 5.3. Aggressive behaviour (i.e. biting and chasing) measured in Experiment 1 (means \pm SE) per tank 15
 2157 min^{-1} (n=12). The number of individuals in each of the wholesaler tanks was 400, the number of individuals in
 2158 each of the “retailer” tanks was 20.

	Biting			Chasing		
	1 h	24 h	144 h	1 h	24 h	144 h
Control	9.7 \pm 2.0	16.0 \pm 2.0	17.0 \pm 3.5	6.1 \pm 1.1	9.6 \pm 1.6	13.4 \pm 3.2
Stress Coat [®]	15.9 \pm 4.4	12.9 \pm 3.7	12.3 \pm 2.1	7.3 \pm 2.0	8.8 \pm 3.3	7.9 \pm 1.2
Salt	12.7 \pm 2.0	10.1 \pm 1.7	14.7 \pm 2.5	11.1 \pm 4.4	6.3 \pm 1.0	6.8 \pm 0.8

2159 Figure 5.2. Number of erratic movements (per tank 15 min^{-1}) (mean \pm SE) performed by fish held in tanks with
 2160 no added treatments (control), with Stress Coat[®] or with salt, recorded at 1, 24 and 144 h after exposure. There
 2161 were no overall effects between treatments; lower case letters indicate significant post-hoc differences within
 2162 treatments between different sampling times (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing a letter are not significantly
 2163 different.
 2164

2165 The number of freezing bouts was not affected by treatment ($\chi^2=0.002$, $df=2$, $p=0.999$), but was affected
2166 by time ($\chi^2=36.605$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$; Fig. 5.3A) with no significant interaction between the factors
2167 ($\chi^2=8.659$, $df=4$, $p=0.07$). Freezing bouts decreased over time in all treatments, with more freezing 1 h
2168 and 24 h after exposure compared with 144 h after exposure. Similarly, time had a significant effect on
2169 the number of fin flaring behaviours ($\chi^2=30.002$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$; Fig. 5.3B) but treatment did not
2170 ($\chi^2=1.021$, $df=2$, $p=0.6$). For fin flaring behaviour there was no significant interaction between treatment
2171 and time ($\chi^2=3.421$, $df=4$, $p=0.49$). Overall, the number of fin flares increased over time, with
2172 significantly fewer fin flaring behaviours 1 h after exposure compared to 24 h and 144 h after exposure.

2173

2174 Figure 5.3. Number of freezing bouts (A) and fin flares (B) (per tank 15 min⁻¹) (mean ± SE) performed by fish held in tanks with no added treatments (control), with Stress
 2175 Coat® or with salt, recorded at 1, 24 and 144 h after exposure. Letters indicate significant post-hoc differences between sampling times (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing a
 2176 letter are not significantly different.

2177 5.4.2. Experiment 2: Subsequent national transport of fish from Experiment 1 from
 2178 wholesaler to simulated retailer.
 2179 No significant differences in mortality were found between treatments ($\chi^2=0.346$, $df=2$, $p=0.751$). The
 2180 pH and ammonia levels of the transport water were within safe levels throughout the three runs of the
 2181 experiment, with the salinity remaining stable throughout (Table 5.4).

2182 Table 5.4. Water quality in transport water on arrival at “retailer” (mean \pm SE).

	Treatment		
	Control	Stress Coat [®]	Salt
pH	7.03 \pm 0.06	7.04 \pm 0.05	7.36 \pm 0.05
Ammonia (mg/ l)	0.67 \pm 0.07	0.67 \pm 0.07	0.42 \pm 0.04
Salinity (ppt)	-	-	3.17 \pm 0.06

2183 Prior treatment at the wholesaler did not affect the performance of biting ($\chi^2=0.244$, $df=2$, $p=0.885$) or
 2184 chasing behaviours ($\chi^2=1.316$, $df=2$, $p=0.518$) following national transport, but there was a significant
 2185 effect of time on both behaviours (bites: $\chi^2=21.194$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$; chases: $\chi^2=62.866$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$).
 2186 Biting and chasing increased following introduction to the tanks, with significantly fewer bites
 2187 performed immediately on introduction (Fig. 5.4). There was no significant interaction between the
 2188 factors for either behaviour (bites: $\chi^2=1.627$, $df=4$, $p=0.07$; chases: $\chi^2=4.01$, $df=4$, $p=0.405$).

2189

2190 Figure 5.4. Number of bites (A) and chases (B) (per tank 15 min⁻¹) (mean ± SE) performed by fish from Experiment 1 following transport from the wholesaler. Behaviours
 2191 were recorded upon arrival when the fish were introduced to the tanks (0 h), 24 h and 144 h post-transport. Letters indicate significant post-hoc differences between sampling
 2192 points (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing a lower-case letter are not significantly different.

2193 Erratic movement of transported fish was affected by time ($\chi^2=12.347$, $df=2$, $p=0.002$), but not by prior
 2194 treatment exposure ($\chi^2=1.96$, $df=2$, $p=0.375$), although there was a significant interaction between the
 2195 factors ($\chi^2=11.153$, $df=4$, $p=0.02$). Overall, fish exhibited significantly more erratic movements 144 h
 2196 after transport, than immediately following transport. Within the control group, there was a significant
 2197 increase in the number of erratic movements 144 h after transport (Fig. 5.5).

2198

2199 Figure 5.5. Number of erratic movements (per tank 15 min⁻¹) (mean \pm SE) performed by transported fish from
 2200 Experiment 1 following transport from the wholesaler. Behaviours were recorded upon arrival (0 h) when the fish
 2201 were introduced to the tanks, 24 h and 144 h after arrival. Letters indicate significant post-hoc differences between
 2202 sampling times within a treatment (Tukey; $p<0.05$), where bars sharing a letter are not significantly different.

2203 The number of freezing bouts was affected by time ($\chi^2=22.72$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$), but not prior treatment
2204 ($\chi^2=0.436$, $df=2$, $p=0.804$), with no significant interaction between time and exposure ($\chi^2=8.092$ $df=4$,
2205 $p=0.088$). The incidence of fish exhibiting freezing behaviour was significantly higher immediately
2206 after transport than 24 h and 144 h after transport (Fig. 5.6A). Similarly, the number of fin flaring
2207 behaviours was affected by time ($\chi^2=19.469$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$), but not prior treatment exposure
2208 ($\chi^2=5.145$, $df=2$, $p=0.076$) and no significant interaction between time and previous treatment exposure
2209 was found ($\chi^2=6.095$, $df=4$, $p=0.192$). The number of fin flaring behaviours increased over time, with
2210 more fin flaring behaviours observed 24 h and 144 h post-transport than immediately after transport
2211 (Fig. 5.6B).

2212

2213 Figure 5.6. Number of freezing bouts (A) and fin flares (B) (per tank 15 min⁻¹) (mean ± SE) performed by transported fish from Experiment 1 following transport from the
 2214 wholesaler. Behaviours were recorded upon arrival (0 h) when the fish were introduced to the tanks, 24 h and 144 h post-transport. Letters indicate significant post-hoc
 2215 differences between sampling points (Tukey; $p < 0.05$), where bars sharing a letter are not significantly different.

2216 5.5. Discussion

2217 The aim of this study was to identify whether treatment with Stress Coat[®] or salt post-international
2218 transport had an effect on stress-related behaviours (i.e. biting, chasing, erratic movements, freezing
2219 bouts and fin flaring) in variatus platy (*Xiphophorus variatus*) on arrival at a UK wholesaler. Whether
2220 or not exposure to these treatments at the wholesaler had any longer-term benefits following national
2221 transport to the “retail store” was also investigated. The “retail store” in this experiment was a laboratory
2222 setting manipulated to simulate a retailer; the number of tanks required and standardisation of conditions
2223 meant that it was not feasible to carry out in a store. In the first part of the current study (Experiment
2224 1), where fish were transported from Vietnam to a UK-based wholesaler and then exposed to either
2225 Stress Coat[®] or salt, neither treatment had a significant effect on any behaviours measured apart from
2226 in the Stress Coat[®] treatment group where a significant decrease in erratic movements over the first 24
2227 h after exposure was observed. Similarly in the second part of the current study (Experiment 2),
2228 following national transport of the same fish from the wholesaler to the “retail store”, wholesaler
2229 treatments had no significant effect on behaviours apart from in the control group where erratic
2230 movements increased significantly over time.

2231 While treatment did not have many effects on behaviour, time following either addition of treatment to
2232 the system (Experiment 1), or fish to the tank (Experiment 2), had an effect on a greater number of
2233 behaviours. Although the initial experiment was looking at behaviours after the addition of the
2234 treatments, in both experiments the fish had been recently introduced into a novel environment and
2235 therefore represents changes in behaviour as fish acclimate to a novel environment post-transport. An
2236 increase in agonistic behaviours (i.e. biting and chasing) over time was seen only in the “retailer”
2237 environment and is likely linked to the establishment of social hierarchies as fish acclimate to their new
2238 tank. At the wholesalers, fish were held in tanks much larger than those at the “retailer” and at much
2239 higher densities (8 fish/l and 0.714 fish/l respectively), which may explain why no increases in agonistic
2240 behaviours over time were seen. For example, neon tetras (*Paracheirodon innesi*), white cloud
2241 mountain minnows (*Tanichthys albonubes*) and tiger barbs (*Barbus tetrazona*), all popular ornamental
2242 fish within the trade, maintained at higher group sizes (10, 10 and eight, respectively) exhibited higher
2243 levels of shoaling compared to those held in smaller groups (two, two and five, respectively) (Saxby *et*
2244 *al.*, 2010). Additionally, at higher densities, neon tetra aggression levels were lower in larger group
2245 sizes than smaller groups (Saxby *et al.*, 2010). There was a more than 10-fold change in stocking density
2246 between the wholesaler and “retailer” in the present study.

2247 Overall counts of aggressive behaviours (per 15 min) were higher at the wholesaler compared with the
2248 “retailer” with a mean of ~ 13 bites and ~ 9 chases per 15 min observed at the wholesaler under control

2249 conditions (Table 3) compared with ~ 4 bites and ~ 3 chases per 15 min at the “retailer”. As the number
2250 of fish in tanks necessitated the counting of all occurrences of the behaviour, and the stocking density at
2251 the wholesaler was 10 times higher, it could therefore be speculated that overall aggression levels were
2252 lower at the wholesaler than at the “retailer”. The initial low incidences of agonistic behaviours (i.e.
2253 biting, chasing and fin flaring) at time 0 h in experiment 2 are likely due to them recovering from the
2254 stress of transport combined with being introduced into a novel environment (Lucon-Xiccato *et al.*,
2255 2022; Jones *et al.*, 2023). After stress recovery and associated behavioural inhibition, time and energy
2256 can be invested into establishing the social hierarchy and displaying the agonistic behaviours associated
2257 with their formation (Carbonara *et al.*, 2019).

2258 To my knowledge, fin flaring has not previously been used as a behavioural indicator for *variatum* platy.
2259 However, in other ornamental species, displays where males flare their fins to each other are indicative
2260 of dominance, e.g. in Burton’s mouthbreeders (*Astatotilapia burtoni*) (Alcazar *et al.*, 2016) and bluefin
2261 killifish (*Lucania goodei*) (McGhee *et al.*, 2007). In the present study, only a significant effect of time
2262 was observed in relation to fin flaring, with a significant increase occurring within the first 24 h after
2263 introduction of the treatments at the wholesaler and within 24 h of introduction to their novel tank at
2264 the “retailer”. One possible explanation as to why the number of fin flares increased over time also
2265 relates to the reasoning behind the biting and chasing behaviours increasing over time, in that it is
2266 associated with social hierarchy establishment and associated agonistic behaviours.

2267 In Experiment 1, an interaction between Stress Coat[®] and time in relation to the number of erratic
2268 movements was found, with erratic movements decreasing over time only when the fish were exposed
2269 to Stress Coat[®]. Whereas in Experiment 2, the treatments had no effect but erratic movements increased
2270 over time in general. Interestingly, although there was no significant overall main effect of treatment in
2271 Experiment 1, the number of erratic movements 1 h after treatment exposure seemed to be higher in the
2272 fish exposed to Stress Coat[®] than the other treatments (Fig. 2). An increase in erratic movements can
2273 be indicative of stress and adverse environmental conditions (Brandão *et al.*, 2021; Jones *et al.*, 2023;
2274 Chapter 1; Chapter 2) but could also occur in response to the fish detecting something (pleasurable or
2275 aversive) in the water. Therefore in the current study, the fish may be able to smell a compound in the
2276 Stress Coat[®] complex, resulting in a higher rate of erratic movements which decrease over time as the
2277 fish either acclimate to the smell, or the Stress Coat[®] depletes from the water. Fish process odour signals
2278 through an olfactory system consisting of defined structures, i.e., olfactory epithelium, olfactory bulb
2279 and olfactory diencephalic and telencephalic centres (Kermen *et al.*, 2013). The ability to effectively
2280 process olfactory cues and form an appropriate response can elicit behaviours fundamental for survival
2281 such as feeding, social interactions and evading predation (Kermen *et al.*, 2013). After being transported
2282 in high densities for an extended period of time (~48 h; Experiment 1), this exposure to a novel

2283 environment followed by exposure to the compounds present within Stress Coat[®] (and the associated
2284 potential pleasurable or aversive olfactory stimulants) may have resulted in allostatic overload.
2285 Therefore, it could be suggested that the treatments should be added prior to transport to ensure that the
2286 fish are acclimated to the potential stimulants. However, as previously mentioned, there may be issues
2287 with dosing if introducing the treatments prior to international transport (i.e. exporters/ farmers adding
2288 inaccurate treatment doses due to inexperience and/or time constraints), and post-transport provides
2289 more control to the wholesaler. Staggering the addition of the Stress Coat[®] to recirculating systems as
2290 was done with salt, may help with acclimation. Contrary to what was found in the present Chapter,
2291 existing studies investigating the efficacy of Stress Coat[®] in reducing transportation stress when exposed
2292 to short- and long-term transport suggests that Stress Coat[®] can persist in system water due to their
2293 being behavioural effects (i.e. reduction in biting and erratic movements) observed in a retail store after
2294 previous exposure during transport (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2020a). The combination of the findings in
2295 this Chapter and the existing study potentially open up a further avenue of research that could
2296 investigate the optimum time to add water conditioners/ treatments to reduce stress either before-,
2297 during- or after-transport.

2298 At both the wholesaler and “retailer”, the number of observations of freezing bouts decreased over time,
2299 with no effect of treatment. The decrease in freezing bouts reached significance at the wholesalers 144
2300 h after the treatments had been added to the systems, whereas, at the “retailer” the number of freezing
2301 bouts decreased significantly within the first 24 h after introduction into a novel environment. Freezing
2302 bouts have been used in a number of behavioural studies as an indicator of stress and/or anxiety, with
2303 high levels being associated with higher levels of anxiety and stress and with lower numbers of freezing
2304 bouts with lower levels of stress (Egan *et al.*, 2009) and recovery (Jones *et al.*, 2022). The apparent
2305 longer recovery time in Experiment 1 could potentially be down to the longer period of time that fish
2306 were transported for compared to Experiment 2, i.e. recovery could be relative to the amount of time
2307 transported.

2308 In the majority of fish transported to the “retailer”, some evidence of fin rot was found on arrival. Fin
2309 rot is a common disease in ornamental fishes caused by *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* (Marudhupandi *et al.*,
2310 2017), with fishes more susceptible to infection when immunocompromised through a stress load which
2311 surpasses the allostatic load tolerance (Tort, 2011). When fishes are exposed to high conspecific
2312 densities with high levels of aggression or mechanical disturbance either during transport or through
2313 repeated netting, their fins can become injured, exposing them to opportunistic pathogens. Physical fin
2314 damage can result in behavioural alterations, reduced welfare and locomotor performance, and can
2315 potentially further compromise a fish’s ability to recover if the injury becomes infected (Audira *et al.*,
2316 2022). Reduced locomotor performance through damaged fins can result in a reduction in feed intake,

2317 if the injured fish is outcompeted by unaffected individuals present within the tank. This reduction in
2318 energy intake in combination with the metabolic energy it takes to recover from fin damage could
2319 potentially lead to further implications such as physical damage from not being able to escape dominant
2320 individuals during agonistic dominance displays. Although fin rot was found in some fish across all
2321 treatments, the healing properties of both Stress Coat[®] and salt could prove efficient at aiding recovery
2322 from infection if the fish are exposed to these compounds for an extended period of time (not just
2323 initially at the wholesaler). Therefore, further research into the efficacy of these treatments as a counter-
2324 infection method over an extended period would be advantageous.

2325 Although there were no significant behavioural benefits of the Stress Coat[®] or salt found compared to
2326 the control treatment throughout the study, neither were any negative effects on behaviour found. The
2327 known anti-parasitic, anti-bacterial, and osmoregulatory-promoting effects of salt (Tavares-Dias, 2021),
2328 and the known wound-healing, disinfecting, and humoral protection-improving properties of Stress
2329 Coat[®] (Shivappa *et al.*, 2017) suggest that these treatments should be considered for fish post-transport.
2330 Numerous studies have shown a reduction in mortality rates through adding salt to transport water,
2331 including in xenocara (*Ancistrus triradiatus*) (Ramírez-Duarte *et al.*, 2013), freshwater drum
2332 (*Aplodinotus grunniens*) (Johnson & Metcalfe, 1982) and striped bass (*Morone saxatilis*) (Mazik *et al.*,
2333 1991). Another benefit of using Stress Coat[®] post-transport is that it removes chlorine and chloramines
2334 (nitrate/ nitrite), and neutralises heavy metals (Shivappa *et al.*, 2017). High concentrations of nitrates
2335 and/ or nitrites in water are detrimental to fish health and welfare and can easily lead to mortality. These
2336 beneficial effects of adding Stress Coat[®] and/or salt to the water fish are introduced into lend themselves
2337 to reducing the effects of stress and the effects of poor welfare conditions post-transport.

2338 5.6. Conclusions

2339

2340 This study highlights the potential for the prophylactic use of Stress Coat[®] or salt into waters that fish
2341 will be introduced into, whether it is at the wholesaler, retailer or in hobbyist aquaria, when used at the
2342 correct dose for the species, could potentially benefit the welfare of ornamental fishes. However, further
2343 research into identifying the best time and frequency to add these treatments to get their optimum benefit
2344 as well as investigating the potential effects of longer-term exposure to the treatments during transport
2345 should be investigated before these treatments are offered as standard.

2346 Chapter 6: Conclusion

2347 The primary aims of the studies conducted within this thesis were to investigate ways to improve the
2348 welfare of ornamental fishes during and post-transport, identify novel enrichment types to actively
2349 promote positive welfare, and to use behaviour as an indicator of stress for ornamental fishes. Chemical
2350 interventions that were trialled during, or after, short- or long-term (~2-48 h) transport included novel (
2351 Chapter 2) and commercially available water conditioners (Stress Coat[®] and NaCl, Chapter 5), and a
2352 potential new water conditioner ingredient (cannabidiol (CBD), Chapter 4). Social intervention
2353 involved manipulating the social composition that fish were introduced into post-transport (Chapter 3).
2354 For all studies, fish behaviour was used as the metric to identify any welfare benefits, quantified either
2355 through manual observation (Chapters 2, 3, 4 and 5) or through automated tracking software (Chapter
2356 4). In addition, water cortisol was measured as an additional non-invasive measure of welfare in Chapter
2357 4. None of the interventions trialled had any negative effects. Social composition (Chapter 3) and CBD
2358 (Chapter 4) manipulations were the most promising in terms of beneficial effects and revealed
2359 themselves as potential methods for improving ornamental fish welfare. The novel and commercially
2360 available water conditioners (F1, Stress Coat[®] and salt; Chapters 2 and 5, respectively) studied had no
2361 direct significant beneficial effects but also had no negative effects.

2362 6.1. Understanding the ornamental fish trade and associated welfare concerns

2363 The ornamental fish trade is an industry that has been consistently growing over the past few decades,
2364 with the current trade estimated to be worth around \$15-20 billion *per annum* (Jones *et al.*, 2021;
2365 Chapter 1). However, it is only in recent years that there has been an interest in improving welfare
2366 within the ornamental trade (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2019, 2020a, 2020b, 2021; Jones *et al.*, 2021, 2023).
2367 While there is European legislation in place regarding fish welfare in aquaculture and research (EU,
2368 1998 and 2010, respectively), currently, there are no specific legal requirements or legislations for
2369 ensuring good welfare for ornamental fishes. In recent years, Operational Welfare Indicators (OWIs),
2370 which are behavioural and physical indicators of welfare, have been developed for fish within
2371 commercial aquaculture (for example Precision Fish Farming for salmonids; Føre *et al.*, 2018) and
2372 laboratories (for example FishEthoBase; Saraiva *et al.*, 2019). However, to date there are no OWIs for
2373 ornamental fishes, potentially because it may be difficult to create OWIs for all species within the
2374 ornamental fish trade due to the diversity and small physical size of the majority of species being traded
2375 (Jones *et al.*, 2021). Further, the species that are traded are incredibly varied in their requirements and
2376 sensitivities (i.e. water quality, feed, space) and consequently, was highlighted in Chapter 1 as one of

2377 the main concerns when attempting to implement welfare standards within the trade. Therefore, a better
2378 understanding of both the requirements (i.e. physical and social) and the conditions that these fish are
2379 exposed to will be useful for improving welfare within the ornamental fish trade.

2380 While there has been a limited amount of research into improving the welfare of ornamental fishes,
2381 there has been an increase in interest, specifically looking at non-invasive measures and indicators of
2382 fish welfare (Martins *et al.*, 2011; Barreto *et al.*, 2021; Jones *et al.*, 2021). Behavioural research has
2383 been used extensively for food fish aquaculture to improve welfare and quality of the fish (see review
2384 by Martins *et al.*, 2011). The research in this thesis used behaviour as the main metric to identify whether
2385 any interventions trialled made a significant difference to fish welfare. Initially, existing research into
2386 welfare concerns within the trade (i.e. transportation, water quality, density) as well as studies
2387 researching ornamental fish welfare through behavioural analysis were reviewed (Chapter 1). In total,
2388 through using a systematic search method, 36 relevant papers were identified. The behaviours most
2389 commonly measured in the identified studies were related to feeding/ foraging (i.e. latency to exhibit
2390 foraging behaviour), aggression (i.e. biting and chasing) and swimming behaviour (i.e. freezing time/
2391 bouts and time immobile), which were highlighted as behaviours that could be useful for this thesis.
2392 From this literature search, five categories where welfare may be compromised were considered based
2393 on particular themes that were repeated across the studies that were analysed: behaviour, living
2394 environment, nutrition, overall health and transportation conditions. Each of these categories had
2395 suggestions pertaining to potential non-specialist (due to the broad range of species being traded), non-
2396 invasive (due to the need for terminal sampling and potential for increased stress) biotic and abiotic
2397 OWIs that could be included when measuring the welfare of ornamental fishes. For ornamental fish
2398 welfare to be improved, there needs to be a conscious effort by all stakeholders within the ornamental
2399 fish supply chain to both understand where welfare concerns may arise and also contribute towards a
2400 solution as and when a welfare issue may arise, potentially through the development of a suite of non-
2401 specialist OWIs.

2402 6.2. Non-invasive measures for welfare research

2403 In this thesis, no invasive measures of welfare were used as these can coincide with negative welfare
2404 outcomes (pain and/or mortality) and although physiological measures of stress are important in some
2405 instances, for the purpose of this thesis behavioural measures of stress were focussed on. Stakeholders
2406 within the ornamental fish trade are generally averse to terminal sampling, which would be unavoidable
2407 if taking physiological measurements such as blood cortisol due to the small size of the fish being traded

2408 (Ellis *et al.*, 2004; Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2021). In Chapter 4, behavioural analyses were complemented
2409 with water cortisol measurements post-transport as a non-invasive physiological measurement of stress.
2410 Although cortisol levels were below detection, water cortisol remains a way of obtaining a physiological
2411 measurement non-invasively. However, water cortisol analysis does have disadvantages, as it is difficult
2412 to quantify at an individual level as evidenced in Chapter 4. Additionally, while fish need to remain in
2413 the holding water for cortisol to be excreted and accumulate, it also potentially could lead to re-uptake
2414 by the fish as well as degradation and/or adsorption by the surface of the container the fish are being
2415 held in (Sadoul & Geffroy, 2019). These results potentially indicate that, for small ornamental fish
2416 species such as the variatus platy, water cortisol analyses may not be the optimum measure of stress
2417 and in fact behaviour may be a more sensitive indicator. Although no invasive measures were used, it
2418 is impossible to expose ornamental fish to transport without also exposing them to potential stress.
2419 Therefore, it is likely that there was cortisol present within the sample but due to the physical size of
2420 the fish in Chapter 4, it is likely that there was not enough present within the volume of water used.
2421 However, due to the likelihood for fish being exposed to further stress if placed in a smaller volume of
2422 water it may have skewed the results if cortisol had been detected. Existing studies have used the same
2423 volume of water as the one used in Chapter 4 (100 ml), but left the fish in the beakers for 1 h (Midttun
2424 *et al.*, 2022) instead of the 30 min in Chapter 4. If Chapter 4 was to be repeated, it may be beneficial to
2425 have more than one fish present within the water cortisol collection tank to increase the amount of
2426 cortisol present (hopefully to within detectable levels). Alternatively, increasing the amount of time the
2427 fish spend in the beaker may be an option as this has been used in previous studies with another
2428 ornamental fish species, zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) (Midttun *et al.*, 2022).

2429 Using behaviour as a monitoring tool has been especially useful within this thesis when considering
2430 stress-related agonistic behaviours to understand the formation of social hierarchies in variatus platies.
2431 All studies included biting, chasing, erratic movements and time immobile/freezing bout behaviours
2432 due to these being well documented stress-related behaviours. These behaviours therefore have the
2433 potential to be used more ubiquitously in future research as a non-invasive measure of welfare for
2434 ornamental fishes. In Chapter 5, fin flaring was included as a novel behavioural indicator due to personal
2435 observations during earlier chapters of this behaviour coinciding with social hierarchy formations and
2436 associated agonistic behaviours observed in previous studies. This behaviour was added in as the
2437 ethogram became more refined throughout the thesis. Automated behavioural tracking software
2438 (ZebTrack in MATLAB) was also used (Chapter 4) when looking at behaviour on an individual level
2439 post-transport as the software could accurately measure how far an individual had travelled and also it
2440 is a method that is unbiased. Whilst tracking software is unlikely to be useful under commercial
2441 conditions due to space constraints it can be useful under laboratory conditions when testing novel

2442 compounds. The research in this thesis has improved our understanding of social hierarchy formation
2443 in *variatus platys*, and the time it takes for hierarchies to form. In all experimental chapters, the overall
2444 trend was for agonistic behaviours to increase over time and then level out, whereas stress-related
2445 behaviours such as freezing and erratic movements decreased over time. These trends in behaviours are
2446 conducive to the formation of social hierarchies. Normal behaviours and group dynamics of fishes
2447 include exhibiting agonistic behaviours to facilitate the formation of a social hierarchy (Oldfield, 2011).
2448 According to the five freedoms/domains (Webster, 2016, Mellor *et al.*, 2020), for the welfare of fishes
2449 to be positive, they should be able to exhibit their natural behavioural repertoire, including exhibiting
2450 agonistic behaviours to identify where they are within a social hierarchy.

2451 *Variatus platys* (*Xiphophorus variatus*) were used in this thesis due to their popularity with hobbyists
2452 (Dey, 2016), their varied colouration, activeness and their relative ease of maintenance. Furthermore,
2453 apart from being viviparous, the anatomy and life history of *variatus platies* are relatively similar to a
2454 wide range of popular ornamental species (for example guppies, zebrafish, tetras). As well as their
2455 popularity with hobbyists, they are also well researched with 1499 studies being conducted on fish in
2456 the *Xiphophorus* family since 1970 (acquired from Web of Science search; 29.07.2023). All
2457 experiments used behaviour as a measure of welfare and using existing literature to solidify the
2458 interpretation of the behaviours, individual ethograms for each chapter were created. *Variatus platies*
2459 were used in each study in the thesis due to their well documented behaviours and facilitated the
2460 development of additional behaviours to be included as the studies progressed. This species was also
2461 used due to their ability to be housed with a range of heterospecific tank-mates. Although the above
2462 reasons do highlight the benefits of using a species such as the *variatus platy* in ornamental fish welfare
2463 research, not all fish will necessarily have the same behavioural repertoire and therefore, more species
2464 need to be studied to identify a broad range of behavioural markers to create ornamental fish OWIs.
2465 However, *variatus platy* behaviours are similar to a large range of other ornamental species, highlighting
2466 the potential for the ethograms used in this thesis to be used to develop OWIs for a range of ornamental
2467 fish species.

2468 Although there was an ample amount of evidence to justify the use of the behaviours used in the
2469 ethograms in this thesis, it was difficult to use all behaviours in all laboratory and wholesaler settings.
2470 In laboratory settings, densities can be controlled to ensure that individual fish behaviours can be easily
2471 observable whereas in a wholesaler setting, the densities are much higher meaning it was more difficult
2472 to differentiate between individuals and behaviours and therefore, all observed behaviours were
2473 recorded. This highlights that if OWIs were to be created they would need to be tailored to different
2474 situations but could be related to ensure all welfare indicators were documented.

2475 6.3. The effect of water conditioners during- and post-transport

2476 Water quality is a key area that can potentially be detrimental to ornamental fish welfare within the
2477 varying stages of the ornamental fish supply chain if not maintained correctly (Chapter 1; King *et al.*,
2478 2019; Jones *et al.*, 2021; Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2021). The effect of a commercially available water
2479 conditioner (Stress Coat[®]) on behaviour during both short- and long-term transport has been studied
2480 previously (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2020a), with Stress Coat[®] proving beneficial in reducing the amount
2481 of direct contact aggression (biting) and erratic movement amongst variatus platies. It may not always
2482 be possible for international suppliers to add water conditioners prior to shipping (e.g. they may not be
2483 available in their country), therefore, to extend this study, I investigated the effects of both Stress Coat[®]
2484 on behaviour of fish when they were exposed immediately after international transport. I also
2485 investigated whether this exposure on arrival at the wholesaler had any behavioural effects after the fish
2486 were exposed to a subsequent short-term transport 1 week later (Chapter 5). Limited behavioural effects
2487 were observed with neither treatment having a significant effect on behaviour, but time did have a
2488 significant effect (Chapter 5). It is worth noting, however, that the active ingredients in Stress Coat[®]
2489 (i.e. *Aloe vera* and PVP-I) are known for their beneficial immunoprotecting and neuroprotecting
2490 properties (Scarfe *et al.*, 2006; Zanuzzo *et al.*, 2015; Shivappa *et al.*, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2023) and
2491 therefore, open up the possibility for benefits in terms of injury/ disease treatment or recovery, as seen
2492 in other studies investigating the benefits of Stress Coat[®] during- and post-transport (Vanderzwalmen
2493 *et al.*, 2020a). Chapter 5 also looked at the potential benefits of using salt post-transport as it has
2494 previously been identified to mitigate the deterioration of water quality, hydromineral imbalance,
2495 immunosuppression and stress responses in common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) and protect skin mucosal
2496 responses in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) (Mirghaed & Ghelichpour, 2019 and Tacchi *et al.*,
2497 2015, respectively). However, in Chapter 5, no specific behavioural benefits of salt exposure were
2498 observed. The previously mentioned studies using Stress Coat[®] and salt all exposed the fish to the
2499 treatments prior to and/or during transport. Therefore, another avenue of further research using these
2500 treatments could be to identify at which point within the ornamental fish supply chain these treatments
2501 would be most useful in improving welfare.

2502 The effects of a novel water conditioner during transport were also investigated (Chapter 2). The main
2503 components within the novel water conditioner tested in Chapter 2 aim to improve water quality by
2504 removing heavy metals (Shalaby, 2007; Selwyn & Tse, 2008; McDougall *et al.*, 2020). In the origin
2505 country of the ornamental fish breeder or farmer, fishes are routinely raised in outdoor ponds. These
2506 outdoor ponds have the potential to become contaminated, for example by heavy metals (Emenike *et al.*,
2507 2021), which could compromise the welfare of the fish being maintained in them. No significant

2508 effects of the novel water additive were observed in relation to the behaviour of the fish exposed to
2509 national short-term transport or water quality. However, this is likely due to the quality of the water (i.e
2510 temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH and ammonia) that the fish were transported in being high
2511 throughout the experiment. Further research into the efficacy of the novel water conditioner in removing
2512 heavy metals by deliberately dosing water with heavy metals could be carried out. Alternatively, further
2513 research into the efficacy of the novel water conditioner could be conducted internationally for long-
2514 term transport as opposed to short-term national transport. This would involve dosing bags within the
2515 origin country of the fish being transported, where water quality may not be high and transportation
2516 times will be longer.

2517 Chapter 4 looked at the potential benefits of cannabidiol (CBD) for fish during transport. CBD is a non-
2518 psychotropic and non-psycho-active phytocannabinoid constituent that derives from the *Cannabis*
2519 *sativa* plant (Murkar *et al.*, 2019; Moltke & Hindocha, 2021). Natural products are becoming
2520 increasingly popular to reduce anxiety for both humans and domestic animals. CBD has multiple
2521 benefits including aiding in immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory and anxiolytic functioning in
2522 mammals (Murkar *et al.*, 2019). CBD had a significant effect on fish behaviour, with exposed fish
2523 exhibiting less stress-related behaviours and higher exploratory behaviours post-transport than the fish
2524 in the control groups, opening up the realistic opportunity for CBD to be included in a commercial water
2525 conditioner product. Further research into whether this ingredient could be used over a longer period of
2526 time during international transport would be beneficial, to determine whether use of CBD within a
2527 commercial product could ameliorate some of the stress associated with the transportation process for
2528 ornamental fishes. Further research into the chemistry of what CBD breaks down into in water and what
2529 the metabolites are would be useful to specifically identify which metabolites have an effect on fish
2530 behaviour and physiology.

2531 6.4. The effect of social enrichment post-transport

2532 The use of social enrichment to improve fish welfare has received limited scientific attention compared
2533 to the use of physical enrichment. Chapter 3 highlighted that post-transport, fish introduced into empty
2534 tanks or into tanks with resident fish of a different species exhibited significantly fewer stress-related
2535 behaviours than those placed into tanks containing resident fish of the same species. Fishes can learn
2536 through observing other individuals, a process referred to as ‘eavesdropping’ (McGregor, 1993; Heyes
2537 & Galef, 1996; Brown & Laland, 2003). ‘Social facilitation’ is also seen in fishes, where the behaviour
2538 of one individual induces the same response in the observer; the observer then learns through expressing
2539 this behaviour and experiencing the consequences in a particular context (Brown & Laland, 2003; Ward,

2540 2012). Emotional contagion, where emotional states are influenced and matched between an observer
2541 and demonstrator (Nakahashi & Ohtsuki, 2018; Lombana et al., 2021), has recently been studied in
2542 fishes (Faustino et al., 2017; Silva et al., 2019). While similar to social facilitation, emotional contagion
2543 focusses on emotional state and in fishes, individuals can become ‘fearful’ and exhibit behavioural
2544 stress when they are able to see other fish experiencing stressful situations (Silva et al., 2019). These
2545 theories all lend themselves to the potential benefits of fish being introduced into tanks containing con-
2546 or hetero-specifics post-transport. As previously discussed in Chapter 3, “social buffering”, the term
2547 used to describe a fish’s accelerated rate of recovery from a stressor when in the presence of an
2548 unstressed tank-mate, could potentially be a benefit of social enrichment. Consequently, it is reasonable
2549 to assume that this accelerated recovery from stress can facilitate a faster recovery of normal immune
2550 functioning following stress-induced immunodysfunction.

2551 Aggressive behaviours are a part of a fish’s natural behavioural repertoire, so as welfare-based concepts
2552 that state that organisms should be able to exhibit natural behaviours, it is necessary to understand what
2553 baseline of aggressive behaviour would be “acceptable”. The normal process within a retailer is to take
2554 newly arrived fish and to either place them into tanks that are empty or containing con- or hetero-
2555 specifics that have been within the tank for a variable amount of time. Put simply, there is currently no
2556 standard practice within the UK when it comes to introducing new fish into a system. The suggestions
2557 made in Chapter 3, that newly arrived fish should ideally be placed into empty tanks, could be difficult
2558 to implement as a standard practice in retailers due to space requirements. Therefore, it was suggested
2559 that if an empty tank is unavailable, placing newly arrived fish into tanks containing heterospecifics
2560 would also be acceptable. Further research is needed to identify which species would be compatible
2561 within mixed species tanks based on species requirements and sociality. The benefits to the industry of
2562 refining what happens to newly arrived fish could be numerous, not just by improving space efficiency.
2563 Improved stress recovery could result in improved immuno-functioning with direct financial benefits
2564 as diseased or injured fish require quarantine. Furthermore, with faster recovery from stress, fish may
2565 display a normal behavioural repertoire, potentially resulting in higher sales as the fish are essentially
2566 “advertising” what they would be like in a hobbyist tank.

2567 6.5. Improving welfare

2568 Definitions for positive animal welfare are similar to those used in human psychology, for example
2569 Maslow’s (1943) *Hierarchy of Needs*, where well-being is not just focused on treating pathologies but
2570 also emphasises positive experiences to enable thriving. The affective states of an organism are a result

2571 of external or internal stimuli (or both) which subsequently result in behavioural responses that are
2572 dependent upon the stimuli (positive or negative). There is still discussion over the ability of fishes to
2573 experience positive affective states however, there is a mounting body of evidence to support the theory
2574 that they do (Fife-Cook & Franks, 2019; Silva *et al.*, 2019; Sneddon *et al.*, 2020). In this thesis, the
2575 assumption is that fishes experience affective states such as pain, pleasure and fear, and unless the
2576 contrary is scientifically proven, animal welfare scientists should also assume the same. The five
2577 freedoms/ five domains are thought to be the gold standard in terms of the minimum welfare
2578 requirements for animals (Webster, 2016; Mellor *et al.*, 2020), however, if someone decides to trade or
2579 keep ornamental fishes they should aim to go beyond the minimum requirements and actively facilitate
2580 positive welfare conditions. The concept of positive welfare originates from the theory that if an
2581 organism can experience negative states (pain, fear, hunger/thirst etc.), then it is reasonable to assume,
2582 based on evolutionary theory, that these same organisms can experience positive states as well (Fraser
2583 and Duncan, 1998). Recognising that it is important to facilitate rewarding or even enjoyable
2584 experiences for captive animals beyond removing potentially welfare compromising conditions, is the
2585 first step in improving welfare for ornamental fishes (Fife-Cooke & Franks, 2019). The basic conditions
2586 for all of the studies in this thesis upheld the five freedoms/domains and all interventions studied aimed
2587 to actively improve welfare for ornamental fishes.

2588 Over the past few decades, there has been a marked increase in promoting both animal welfare and
2589 introducing positive welfare within animal husbandry guidelines. For example, prominent animal
2590 welfare researchers have advocated that positive welfare indicators should be included into the Five
2591 Freedoms/ Domains model (Mellor & Beausoleil, 2015; Mellor, 2016; Fife-Cook & Franks, 2019)
2592 arguing that the existing model ignores the psychological aspect of welfare. A further avenue of research
2593 in fish welfare, specifically ornamental fishes, could be to use physiological and behavioural metrics of
2594 positive emotional states. Anatomically and chemically, fishes have the necessary structures to
2595 experience emotion; the limbic and dopaminergic structures within telencephalon are homologous with
2596 the mammalian amygdala (Lal *et al.*, 2018), and consequently, appetitive (wanting) or incentive salience
2597 and consummatory (liking) behaviours have been observed in fishes (Kittilsen, 2013; Fife-Cooks &
2598 Franks, 2019; Soh *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, using emotional state analyses such as ventilatory rhythm
2599 and locomotion *via* analysing bioelectrical signals in the water (Soh *et al.*, 2021) in conjunction with
2600 additional research using immuno-promoting compounds or conditions could be especially beneficial
2601 (i.e. CBD (Chapter 4), Stress Coat[®] or salt (Chapter 5) or in combination with manipulating the social
2602 composition of a tank (Chapter 3)). In pigs, it has been found that positive and negative emotional
2603 experiences have a direct correlation with immune system parameters (s-IgA levels), which is analogous
2604 with studies investigating the relationship between emotional states and immune functioning in humans

2605 (Boissy *et al.*, 2007). To truly obtain positive welfare it ultimately needs to be down to the choice of
2606 the animal to identify whether the welfare interventions that are put in place are not just beneficial
2607 physiologically but also psychologically. Research into improving welfare should therefore also include
2608 an element of choice for the organisms used where possible, for example *via* the use of preference tests
2609 to identify whether they prefer one intervention to another or even none at all.

2610 6.6. Thesis limitations

2611 The primary limitation of the studies in this thesis was the lack of diversity in terms of physiological
2612 measurements of stress. Due to the relative deficit of information regarding welfare improvements
2613 within the ornamental fish trade, preliminary studies like the ones conducted for this thesis were needed.
2614 These can then be used in conjunction with further avenues of research that ground-truth the use of non-
2615 invasive behavioural measures with the use of physiological measurements. These measures do not
2616 need to be invasive as physiological measurements could potentially be *via* cortisol extraction from
2617 mucus either on a larger ornamental species or on a higher number of smaller species to get an adequate
2618 sample size or through faecal corticoid metabolite analysis (Ding *et al.*, 2023). Another measurement
2619 method could be through colourmetric analyses (eye darkening or hypo-/hyper-pigmentation)
2620 (Vanderzwalmen *et al.*, 2021), which could be used in a scientific setting by taking photographs and
2621 using image analysis software. Colourmetric analyses also could be used in a commercial or hobbyist
2622 setting where employees or customers are trained to identify differentiation in eye/skin colours that are
2623 synonymous with stress (Bäckstrom *et al.*, 2020). Once these methods have been validated in
2624 combination with behavioural measurements, it opens up the potential for there to be developments of
2625 new non-invasive welfare monitoring tools for industry, potentially using OWIs explored in Chapter 1.

2626 Another limitation of this thesis was that the conditions that fish were exposed to before arriving in the
2627 UK could not be confirmed by personal observations. For example, there was no way of knowing how
2628 the fish were treated at each stage of the transportation process due to the inability to access all of the
2629 stages of the transport process and therefore, some areas for improvement are probably being missed.
2630 Additionally, when conducting further experiments in the future, it would be beneficial to know whether
2631 there were conditions that the fish were exposed to that could elucidate reasons for atypical results.
2632 Furthermore, without seeing where the fish originate and the standard practices within the breeding
2633 facility or farm, it is unknown whether the fish that are studied are of the same strain. However, in an
2634 attempt to have some control over this, trusted and reputable suppliers and wholesalers were used for
2635 all fish acquisitions in this thesis. Similarly, if there is not a well-documented breeding programme,

2636 there could be the potential for fish to be compromised genetically *via* inbreeding, which could lead to
2637 atypical behaviours in experiments. I think that for someone to truly understand the whole process one
2638 would need to see all stages and conditions that fishes are routinely exposed to and to be able to identify
2639 specific areas where welfare considerations are lacking.

2640 6.7. Future directions

2641 Currently there are no welfare monitoring protocols for ornamental fishes. In order for there to be real
2642 change within the industry, monitoring protocols, such as OWIs (Chapter 1), need to be created and
2643 applied by the industry throughout every stage of the ornamental fish supply chain from origin to
2644 destination (Jones *et al.*, 2021). Stakeholders need to take ownership and responsibility of fishes while
2645 under their care and put in place routine monitoring techniques, both physical (i.e. regular extensive
2646 water quality testing) and behavioural.

2647 In Chapter 5, there was an outbreak of what was assumed to be white spot disease. In the ornamental
2648 fish trade, there are a number of diseases and parasites that fishes can be exposed to. One of the most
2649 prevalent infections, Ich or white spot disease, is caused by the *Ichthyophthirius multifiliis* parasite.
2650 Small numbers of this parasite are naturally present in most aquariums and are normally controlled by
2651 normal immune functioning. However, when a fish's immune system becomes compromised it opens
2652 the fish up to potential infection leading to illness and can ultimately lead to the mortality of infected
2653 fishes. Therefore, mitigating, removing or reducing the amount of stress that ornamental fishes are
2654 exposed to reduces the risk of infection and potentially death. Further research into potential treatments
2655 for these diseases and parasites, either prophylactic or curative, needs to be conducted alongside
2656 potentially identifying the behaviours that "unwell" fish exhibit. Understanding what to look for
2657 behaviourally in immunocompromised fish will help to create behavioural indicators for
2658 disease/infection that could act as early warning indicators. Stakeholders within the ornamental fish
2659 supply chain only get paid from the next stage within the chain if the fishes are healthy and in good
2660 condition. Therefore, there needs to be good communication between all stakeholders within the
2661 ornamental fish supply chain to ensure that the cause of any diseases or infections are identified and
2662 dealt with accordingly to avoid the potential for further infection. Additionally, there needs to be more
2663 momentum in the field of ornamental fish welfare research with a focus on positive welfare. The
2664 findings from Chapter 3 also highlight themselves as a future avenue for a substantial amount of
2665 research into compatible species for cohabitation to improve welfare for ornamental fishes.

2666 6.8. Conclusions

2667 Findings from this thesis have the potential to make significant improvements to the welfare of
2668 ornamental fishes within the trade. This work highlights the efficacy of using behaviour as a non-
2669 invasive measure of stress. It also shines a light on the lack of standardised industrial welfare monitoring
2670 protocols for ornamental fishes and as a result, suggests potential methods for how this can be changed.
2671 The aims of the research in this thesis were to investigate physical and social interventions that could
2672 be used to improve ornamental fish welfare. The research highlighted that through relatively minimal
2673 interventions, improvements can be made to the welfare of ornamental fishes. Furthermore, the use of
2674 behaviour as an indicator of welfare for ornamental fishes proved efficient in distinguishing between
2675 the welfare interventions investigated. Findings from this thesis highlight the benefits of behavioural
2676 analysis as a non-invasive measure of welfare as well as contributing towards the implementation of
2677 welfare interventions for ornamental fishes.

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